

**MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE OF UKRAINE
H. S. SKOVORODA KHARKIV NATIONAL PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY**

**Mid-West State University – UNICENTRO (Brazil)
Sinop University (Turkey)
Nanjing University (China)
Cardiff Metropolitan University, Cardiff School of Education
and Social Policy (the United Kingdom)
Supporting Ukrainian Editorial Staff (France)**

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS
**I International Youth Scientific &
Practical Conference**
LEARNING & TEACHING:
during War and Peace
(Kharkiv, Ukraine)
10 November, 2022

KHARKIV – 2022

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HUMANITARIAN SECTION

AKTAMIROV Ismail

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THEORY: DAO AS A GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

Purpose. This paper aims to describe the proposal of a new government system based on cryptographic technology that may bring more democracy and transparency in the exercise of power.

Results. The technical progress has touched almost every aspect of our lives. The code, the cryptography and other resulting technologies and their possibilities are an essential part to this progress. Why not apply this progress even more and aim to make really democratic and transparent governments? DAO is what we need for it.

First of all, let me introduce you to a more specific science, the cryptography. It transforms data into formats that can't be read by unauthorized parts. So, it secures the communication in the presence of a third party.

Another important technology is blockchain. There are multiple types, but the common part is that there is no intermediary between users. We will focus on hybrid type which is controlled by one authority and users are allowed to make some processes which they don't need permission for. It's the type of blockchain that suits better for our proposal.

Finally, the cryptocurrency is a protocol developed on blockchain technology. It's a smart contract that allows users to interact within a digital financial system and more. Ethereum is a crypto currency that provided a blockchain with built-in technology that allowed to create a large specter of applications, including DAO.

DAO stands for Decentralized Autonomous Organization. The concept deletes intermediary between people in P2P relations. In a DAO, members take collectively decisions and have equal power.

Let's now see what we could have if we apply the concept of DAO to the government system. We have to admit that in the current situation, the population is often in disagreement with political decisions. This is the case even in the most democratic governments of nowadays.

We can observe it by the manifestations and protests. In fact, the smaller the position of a politician is, the closer he is to the people. But, the more important the position is, the more the politician moves away from the people.

Thanks to DAO we could reduce that distance that separates highly placed politicians and the people's opinion.

Conclusions. An administrative authority would only control the processes and people would make their decisions collectively. This can be applied to all the important decisions. People would so in a way replace the parliament votes. This could avoid bad decisions, protests and certainly wars.

(Accepted: the 19th April, 2022)

ALEKSIEIEVA Nataliia

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USING THE KAHOOT PROGRAM AT ENGLISH LESSONS

The development of pupils' interest in learning plays an important role in the learning skills formation. If you rely on pupils' interests, you can arouse in them a desire to learn new things, enthusiasm for a certain topic, subject.

Purpose. This paper aims to show using the Kahoot program at English lessons. In modern conditions, there is a need to activate pupils' skills, to evaluate them objectively, to identify the positive things that affect the independent cognitive activity of schoolchildren. For this, a teacher uses new teaching methods, a new presentation of knowledge. With the advent of digital technologies, it became possible to change qualitatively the learning process.

There are many platforms that have an educational direction: LearningApps, ClassDojo, Kahoot. Kahoot is a popular educational platform for conducting quizzes, creating tests and educational games.

Results. On the Kahoot platform, it is possible to choose different task formats. The most popular: True/ False, Quiz, where from two to four options are offered, you can choose one or more answers that are correct. But there are also paid ones, such as: Type answer, Puzzle, Poll, Word cloud, Open-ended.

Approbation of the Kahoot program in foreign language classes and extracurricular activities in elementary school allowed to come to a conclusion about its effectiveness as a tool for assessing pupils' knowledge. Since this program is colorful, it is very attractive and interesting to the pupils.

The use of Kahoot at English lessons allows you to vary the channels of pupils' perception. It contributes to the effective assimilation of the curriculum and the activation of pupils' independent activities.

The use of Kahoot and digital tools in education helps a teacher to solve such teaching tasks as:

- sustainable motivation formation;
- activation of pupils' cognitive abilities; involvement of passive pupils;
- increasing the intensity of the educational process;
- provision of live communication with representatives of other countries and cultures;
- ensuring the flexibility of the learning process.

Conclusions. Digital technologies provide training in competent communication of a pupil, contribute to increasing the efficiency of the educational process, create an atmosphere of psychological comfort, lead to success, and most importantly expand the possibilities of independent educational learning.

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INFLUENCE OF MODERN LIVING CONDITIONS ON THE PROCESS OF CHILDREN’S EDUCATION

Nowadays, there are a lot of factors that affect children’s education. Children are emotionally unstable members of society, as they are more vulnerable to the influence of external factors. These factors include special conditions of education during the war, organization of distance education and need to create a positive atmosphere for children’s education when learning online and staying at home.

Distance learning became a challenge for all participants of educational process and it affects the daily life and well-being of children. Distance learning cannot provide a sense of cohesion, whereas a sense of belonging to a group is important for children. When a child attends school classes, he feels the rules and obligations, and this helps him adapt to educational process and organize his work. In online learning, the holistic perception of educational situations is lost and becomes fragmented. At the same time, some children do not have developed self-organization skills, so teachers provide support and control at school. In online learning, it is difficult to implement such control and children have to control and organize themselves.

When the war broke out, the educational process temporarily stopped. When it started again, not all schools were ready to provide education because of security problems, poor access to the Internet, destructions etc. Since the beginning of the war, 1,611 educational institutions have been damaged and 161 institutions have been completely destroyed. Children survived shelling, hid in bomb shelters or were forced to move somewhere from home – far from their friends, sometimes to a new language environment. And as a result, they experience serious stressful situations which affect their education significantly. The issues of safety and life come to the fore.

Taking this into account, it is important to create a positive, warm atmosphere for learning and raising children. In order to achieve it, adults should establish an emotional bond with a child, create conditions for comfortable and safe learning and favourable emotional atmosphere in the family, facilitate communication of children with peers, formation of their social skills and positive personality traits, etc.

So, there are many factors that affect children’s education in different ways. The comfort and convenience of the educational process for children, their success and mental well-being depend on appropriate activities carried out by adults (parents, teachers, psychologists, etc.) who support and take care of children.

BEZLAKOVSKA Svitlana

*Municipal Establishment "Kharkiv Humanitarian-Pedagogical Academy"
of Kharkiv Regional Council, Ukraine*

DISADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE LEARNING DURING WARTIME

With the beginning of the full-scale invasion of the Russian army on the Ukrainian land, our life has radically changed and become more complicated in all aspects, including the educational space. The educational process has experienced many challenges and obstacles, starting from the logistical issue.

The purpose of the research is to study the problems encountered by students of general secondary education institutions, who are forced to study online due to the beginning of the war in Ukraine.

One of the most common technical problems of students staying in Ukraine today is the lack of the Internet and electricity. In this case, children are forced to miss lessons, it leads to deterioration of knowledge and the need for individual classes with the teacher to revise the material.

Due to the forced form of distance learning, the problem of weaker integration between students, or its absence at all, is quite relevant. Live communication and interaction with peers is one of the most important factors in human development, and the modern conditions in which today's generation grows up make this factor impossible, which leads to emotional isolation in children and the inability to interact with the team.

During distance learning, children not only learn new material, but also learn self-organization. It is quite difficult for students to abstract from constant news about the current situation in the country and dangerous living conditions, so most of them cannot adjust to the educational process and focus on productive work.

The lack of live communication, the need to leave home and attend school, additional classes, extracurricular activities caused the deterioration of children's physical and mental health. Pupils' leisure and recreation is realized thanks to gadgets and the Internet.

Distance learning is not a new phenomenon in the education system, because there was already experience during the coronavirus pandemic, but during the martial law, online learning led to the emergence of new challenges, namely: the unstable emotional state of children - feelings of depression, fear, insecurity, depression, sometimes embitterment or apathy. With this in mind, school teachers should constantly improve their methodology of working with students, be understanding of children's inattention and lack of self-discipline and motivation to study.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE WAR IN UKRAINE

The research material is based on the works of domestic and foreign scholars in such fields as the theory and practice of blended learning. The basic **purpose** of the article is to distinguish the main research methods, namely: theoretical (analysis of scientific literature on blended learning), empirical (questioning, testing, conversation, pedagogical observation, pedagogical experiment) that can be applied in terms of the war in Ukraine.

Results. Even before the pandemic, the world's population faced significant difficulties in realizing the right to education as a fundamental human right. Nowadays in the circumstances caused by the war in Ukraine, this problem has become more urgent. Despite the difficulties, the educational system of our country tries to do its best to overcome all the obstacles that can preclude getting the equal right for every citizen of our Motherland to have quality education.

That is why special attention is paid to different educational modes that can provide the process of education such as blended learning. Blended learning is a rather innovative mode for Ukraine. It incorporates a combination of remote and face-to-face forms: students can deal with part of the essential material online and have the possibility to manage their time independently. Due to this approach, students can get a holistic learning experience.

Enumerating the advantages of modern blended learning, let's name an individualized and differentiated approach to students compared to traditional classroom learning, when the teacher is forced to focus on the average student, ignoring his individual needs.

The results of the research indicate an increase in success in the case of blended learning mode, as the availability of materials and feedback from the teacher increases, and the skills of independent problem-solving are developed. Students gradually become subjects of the learning process, choosing the components of the blended model according to an individual schedule independently.

Conclusions. The research shows that blended learning allows a flexible response to various life circumstances affecting individuals, educational institutions and society in general. This factor is especially important right now for every participant in the educational process, giving the new challenges such as the destruction of schools, forcibly relocated students and teachers who study and work in new schools throughout Ukraine and beyond, "dropping out" of the educational process of individual children and entire classes due to air raids, combat actions and other causes connected with war.

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TRANSFORMATION OF WESTERNIZATION-INFLUENCED NATIONAL AND GENDER STEREOTYPES IN MASS MEDIA

The paper is **purposed** to study the transformation of Westernization-influenced national and gender stereotypes in mass media products that describe the conflict between Western and Eastern worldviews.

Results. The concept of the “stereotype” refers to a constant, overgeneralized perception of a certain strata of people. Reviewing the functioning of mass media, as a form of mass consciousness, authors revealed its significant influence on the perception of the objective reality by creating in people’s minds certain stereotypes about the cultural characteristics of a country or a nation. National, racial and ethnic stereotypes compile the class of stereotypes that disfavour people, who belong to national, racial or ethnic minorities.

Scientists distinguished the following four stages of emerging national stereotypes in mass media products: non-recognition (the complete exclusion of racial or ethnic minorities from mass media, in particular, in television, cinema, press, etc.); ridicule (the glorification of the dominant group of their own image by humiliating and stereotyping minorities, portraying them as incompetent or badly educated), regulation (depicting minorities, who appear as defenders of the existing order, for example, police, detectives, spies); respect (giving national and racial minorities the full range of roles, both positive and negative, inherent in most heroes). The concept of “gender” refers to an interdisciplinary postmodern notion, that singles out the socio-gender features of sex with its essential traces of lifestyle modes, feelings, actions, expectations, etc.

Besides, regarding various specifications (namely, the concepts of female or male person identifications, “feminine” or “masculine” style of presenting and writing, provision of female or male life experience, the predominance of a certain type of behaviour mode, reflexion, imagery, etc.), the gender identifies a dramatis personae or a creator of a mass media product.

We single out the typical stereotypes about women and femininity: objectification of the female body (women are often portrayed as beauties, who must remain always young and attractive to satisfy men, this is the most evident in advertising), infantilization (transmission of femininity as the manifestation of virginity, vulnerability, naivety), “glass ceiling” (the difficulty of women to reach higher positions in the careers, which are usually occupied by men), the image of the “woman-guardian of the family hearth” (women who dedicate their lives to their husbands and families, performing unpaid reproductive work).

Conclusions. The stereotype of an inferior position of women is frequently rooted in society’s cultural background. Patriarchal society’s attitude towards women is characterized by violence, devaluation and rejection of their own “I” due to the desire to be accepted by others. Nevertheless, the authors explored Westernization-influenced ways to portray women in mass media, who are striving to remove their social, cultural, and religious limitations, imposed upon them by convictions and taboos of their own culture as the only comprehension of life and reality.

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FORMATION OF COGNITIVE INTEREST OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS TO STUDY COMPUTER SCIENCE

The problem of motivating students to learn has existed at all times. More motivated students find it easier to memorize material, take the initiative in learning, and require less effort from the teacher. The main point of the development of students' learning motivation is to transfer students from the levels of negative and indifferent attitude to learning to the forms of positive attitude to learning – effective, conscious, responsible. For successful learning it is important for the student to be positive about the perception of the material, to actively participate in cognitive activities. To form a positive attitude to the study of computer science, it is necessary to understand how the teacher can influence the development of students' cognitive interest.

So, the **aim** of the work is to substantiate the ways of formation of cognitive interest. In our work, we consider four types of stimulation of cognitive interests: content of educational material, organization of educational activities, learning tools, communication and relationships that develop in the learning process between students and teachers, as well as students among themselves.

Results. The content of the educational material includes such factors as novelty of the content, the practical need for knowledge for life, and updating already known information. It is also useful to use the effect of paradoxical information, “wow effect”, as well as emotionality and “closeness” of the content to the life and experience of students to increase cognitive interest.

The second type is the organization of educational activities. The way to influence the cognitive interest of students is to create a didactic situation that would arouse the desire to participate in it, for example, situations of solving cognitive problems, situations of active search, assumptions, mental tension, conflict of opinion. Also, the lack of overload is important, as well as independent work of students, the ability to make choices in educational activities, and situations of success in the classroom.

An important factor is comprehensibility for the student of what is happening in the lesson (i.e., tasks, requirements, etc.). It is also useful to use cognitive games, creative tasks so that students can express themselves. The third type of influence on cognitive interest is a variety of learning tools, for example, the use of visual materials (images, layouts), experiments (physical and computer), construction and use of models, etc. The last type is communication and relations between the participants of the educational process. Positive, emotionally warm atmosphere in the classroom, risk-free learning environment, mutual support, a sense of unity with the group, and cooperation are important for the development of students' cognitive interest. The teacher should pay attention to the emotionality of teaching, as well as believe in the student, in his cognitive strength and abilities.

Conclusions. The paper considers ways to develop students' cognitive interest in the study of computer science, gives recommendations and examples of exercises to improve the content of the educational material, the emotional atmosphere in the classroom, and the organization of cognitive activity of students.

BONDARENKO Diana*Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Faculty of Prosecution, Ukraine***ORGANIZATION OF STUDYING IN WARTIME IN
THE DISCIPLINE OF CONSTITUTIONAL LAW**

To begin with, it is necessary to notice how much teaching methods have changed since the beginning of the war in Ukraine. Unfortunately, the system of our education did not foresee the starting of such a difficult period. Nevertheless, teachers understand the importance of properly organizing their work at this time. Even though the war there are special educational initiatives that allow to continue the educational process according to state standards. It can be applied to both those who have gone abroad and those who have remained in the country. The **aim** is to show the organization of studying in wartime in the discipline of constitutional law.

Results. Surprisingly, even now students enjoy visiting lessons with great pleasure. Moreover, they join additional types of studying specifically writing abstracts and articles, participation in online scientific conferences. Indeed, such a thirst for learning is manifested in connection with the psychological need to distract from scary thoughts. At the same time, there are those students who do not have inner strength to gather their thoughts in a heap and start working. However, it is impossible to scold a person for this because everyone has their own psychotype and all people react differently to critical situations. It is important to pay tribute to teachers who treat each student with understanding. Undoubtedly, the ways of presenting information have changed somewhat since the beginning of the war against Ukraine.

The first thing that needs to be stated is that all teachers have slightly changed the presentation of information on their subject. It is very evident in the legal sphere. We would like to show this fact in more detail on the example of teaching the subject of constitutional law.

On the one hand, from now on, we compare almost any legal phenomenon in Ukraine with the situation in the state, which is our main enemy at the moment. Such a comparison makes it clear what the organization of the state should not be.

On the other hand, the teacher often arranges discussions on the subject of constitutional law. Thus, each student can express their position on a particular issue without fear of condemnation because in fact every Ukrainian has a single position now, but formulated in different forms. The organization of such debates also gives psychological relief to students. This is due to the fact that they can express everything that really worries them politically and spiritually. For example, the students considered the right to freedom of speech and thought not so long ago. And the students compared the application of this right in Ukraine and in a country that is our enemy. The students come to the conclusion that in the aggressor country freedom of speech and thought can be forgotten because this right exists there only *de jure*.

Conclusions. Thus, the organization of studying in wartime in the discipline of constitutional law were considered. Students' attitude to learning at this difficult time were described. Features of the organization of work on lessons in the conditions of war were revealed.

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REVISITING TERMS APPLIED TO LANGUAGE EDUCATION: CONTRIBUTIONS FROM THE WHOLISTIC VIEW OF BILINGUALISM

Fractional approaches to bilingualism (also known as the monolingual view) have been largely refuted over the years, as well as the understanding of bilingual individuals supporting two isolated language systems. Instead of being recognized as two monolinguals in one, people who demonstrate competencies in more than one language have been proven to be under a constant process of language interaction (Grosjean, 2008).

The **purpose** of this study is to reflect on how these findings from cognitive and behavioural science influence the terminology adopted in the educational field, mainly that is engaged in learning English.

As a **result**, the Second Language Acquisition (SLA) model, English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) parameters had to be reviewed to refute the idea of separation among languages these acronyms may introduce. English Language Learners (ELL) was also a target term that we suggest being replaced by Emergent Bilinguals (EB) to avoid attention to the unknown and to empower the student (Poza, 2018). In addition, Clark (2020) explains three other reasons why EB seems to describe these individuals more appropriately: because they are exposed to a different language, not English while growing up; they have been designated as EL at school; and their bilingualism is still and continuously in progress.

As claimed by Ünsal and others (2018) mother tongue, first language, second language and additional language are categorizations from a monolingual method that should be replaced by a minority and majority language. It is important to note languages may represent major or minor use according to the local circumstances, which means they do not assume a strict standard.

We **conclude** that besides the bilingual model, professionals immersed in the field of language education may consider EB, minority and majority language as suitable jargon to describe updated pedagogical practices towards English teaching.

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THE PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH DURING WARTIME

Nowadays Ukraine is experiencing the hardest times ever in its history. The events caused by the armed aggression of the Russian Federation and the declaration of martial law in Ukraine have become a rather serious test for all participants of the educational process. It has devastatingly affected all spheres of Ukrainians' usual life.

The paper **aims** to highlight the peculiarities of teaching and learning English during wartime.

Results. When Ukraine is at war with the Russian Federation, educational institutions must become centers that enable students to obtain not only knowledge, but also get emotional support, not to lose a sense of belonging to the community, and believe in their own strength. Special attention at the lessons should be paid to teaching students to understand, express and manage their own emotions.

The implementation of educational programs in foreign languages in remote formats can take place in synchronous and asynchronous modes (depending on the training formats agreed upon with the military-civilian administration, the technical capabilities of the participants in the educational process, the availability of electricity, the Internet, etc.

Priority activities during online foreign language lessons should be oral communication between the teacher and students in dialogic and monologic modes, explanation of new material, etc. It is advisable to offer reading and writing exercises for students' individual work. Students have become eyewitnesses of events that cannot be ignored or hidden.

Therefore, for the development of civic competence, military topics can be recommended for discussion at the lesson. New military vocabulary (martial law, air-raid siren, missile, missile attack, curfew, shelter, refugee, *HIMARS* - High Mobility Artillery Rocket System, *MLRS* - Multiple Launch Rocket System, etc. can be introduced in class.

Conclusions. Students need support, confidence and faith. Thus, teaching students under martial law is a challenge and at the same time important work of teachers in the overall contribution to the victory in Ukraine!

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“WHITE BIRD WITH A BLACK SIGN” AS THE SYMBOL OF SOVIET PROPAGANDA

Purpose. Two films of the poetic wave “White Bird with a Black Sign” directed by Yuri Ilyenko, and “Zakhar Berkut” by director Leonid Osyka, both screened in 1971, were the ones the Ukrainian diaspora in the USA could not see, but which nevertheless were carefully scrutinized in its newspaper *Svoboda*. The paper aims to highlight the critical views and statements made by American Ukrainians on the former one.

Results. The film “White Bird with a Black Sign” was first mentioned in the August 12, 1971 issue of the *Svoboda* diaspora newspaper. The article “*Moscow Celebrates Film Against Ukrainian Bourgeois Nationalists*” was dedicated to the 1971 International Moscow Film Festival, which was attended by foreign journalists and film critics. According to *Svoboda* editorial, Western journalists found out that the film “White Bird with a Black Sign”, shot by the Kyiv Film Studio, shared the first prize with three other Soviet films. The diaspora’s newspaper reports that Ukrainians in exile learned about the film before the film festival, thanks to Kyiv Radio for Migrants.

The author of the review depicts the plot of the film, noticing its propagandistically marked idea to show the reunification of the lands of Ukraine within the USSR. The reviewer uses sarcastic tone while commenting on the plot and the idea in general, emphasizing the tendency of its creators to show Bukovina during the “boyars” and the conflict between two brothers, one of whom became a Soviet guerrilla during the occupation of Bukovina by Nazi troops.

Besides, *Svoboda* comments the review of a London journalist of the *Daily Telegraph*, who was present at the Moscow International Film Festival, which was published on August 3, 1971. It was noted that the film “White Bird with Black Wings’ was very popular on the eve of the screening. According to the British correspondent, the film does not have a coherent plot and is based on a visual basis, which is full of impressive but meaningless pictures, like a fusion of logs and dancing.

He concludes that the film came out “gray and vulgar”, like all the others presented at the Moscow festival in 1971. In his opinion, the jury should not have awarded anyone the first prize, which was won by four films of that year, and among which was “White Bird...” by Yuri Ilyenko.

Conclusions. The representatives of the Ukrainian diaspora in the USA unanimously agreed that the film “White Bird with a Black Sign” directed by Yuri Ilyenko was an anti-Ukrainian depiction of Bukovina during World War II, that was in line with the Soviet propagandist ideology of the time.

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MEDICAL LANGUAGE CULTURE AS AN INTEGRAL COMPONENT OF MEDICAL DEONTOLOGY

Aim. The transition to the *state language* is an issue of the All-Ukrainian level, which directly affects medical terminology. The native language began to be heard in all aspects of our lives, but, unfortunately, the professional speech of health care representatives lags behind in this regard. The question arises, especially for doctors, how to speed up the transition to the Ukrainian language.

The problem of Russification was considered in the works of such researchers as N. Zhovtobriukh, I. Zalipska, V. Levchenko, R.-Yu. Perkhach, M. Saiko. The researchers suggest focusing on the Russian-Ukrainian translation. They determine the relevance of this problem, as well as its importance and prospects.

Since there is a need to translate professional medical terminology from Russian into Ukrainian, it is necessary to involve as many linguists as possible to solve this problem.

The modern development of the Ukrainian language, in various spheres of our life, causes the need to highlight the problems of Russification in the field of medicine and to emphasize the urgency of the transition to the state language, taking into account the specificity of the terminology of doctors.

Results. The legislative and regulatory document – Article 30 of the Law of Ukraine “On Ensuring the Functioning of the Ukrainian Language as the State Language” outlines the obligation of all medical workers to provide patient care in the state language. The identified factors and conditions for the formation of the content of medical communication allow us to determine the content of the necessary future doctor’s professional competence.

A modern doctor is not only a carrier of a set of special knowledge, but also a constantly developing personality with certain moral and ethical principles and models of communication. Therefore, in the field of medical education, a relevant aspect is the formation of professional communicative competences in the context of training a highly qualified doctor. The work of medical workers involves not only providing assistance to patients, but also the ability to understand them. A lot of demands are placed on the modern doctor regarding professional speech, but the difficulty is that most of the terminology remains Russified.

Currently, the principles of the transition of the medical vocabulary to the state vocabulary are being defined.

In the process of solving the specified task, the key positions of the research were taken into account: **1)** Study of Russified medical terms; **2)** Analysis of studies by scientists who considered the issue of translation of terms.

Conclusions. So, after analyzing all the problematic issues, it can be concluded that the transition of medical terminology is really important.

Prospects for further research are the development of a high-quality translation to facilitate the work process of Ukrainian doctors.

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TEACHING ENGLISH IN A SPECIAL PERIOD OF HOSTILITIES

The **purpose** of the article is to investigate theoretical and practical conceptual foundations of the studied theme in the conditions of such a tough time for the Ukrainian educational system.

Results. As part of our research, we analyse the process of teaching English at the Donetsk State University of Internal Affairs. Two components, such as distance and classical teaching and all their pros and cons have been considered.

In the conditions of the terrible military actions of the racists against the Ukrainian nation, many of our fellow citizens with their children were forced to leave the borders of their existence, and even abroad. Many institutions of higher education left the occupied territories for safer ones. As an example, the Donetsk State University of Internal Affairs moved with its teachers and students to Kropyvnytskyi. A characteristic feature of this institution is that 95% of students are from the occupied Donbas. Therefore, distance teaching is of utmost importance for them.

PROS:

- safer component;
- no need to be present at the university.

CONS:

- different problems with the internet;
- difficulties with explaining new topics/grammar themes;
- a lot of difficulties with free speaking (monological, dialogical, polylogical);
- wasting time staying in bomb shelters while air alarm (no teaching).

A distinctive characteristic of this educational institution is that almost all cadets live in barracks and dormitories, and teachers live next to the university, therefore, at this time, a decision was made to implement the **classical system** in this institution.

PROS:

- must be present at each lesson;
- no problem with the internet;
- no problem with explaining new topics/grammar themes;
- no problem with free speaking (monological, dialogical, polylogical);
- no wasting time during air alarm because the lesson continues in shelter conditions.

CONS:

- more dangerous component;
- each teacher is personally responsible for all students/cadets during class and an air alarm (in the bomb shelter).

Conclusions. Summarizing all the above mentioned, we must note that each component has its pros and cons, but we are more inclined to the *classical* one, as it allows the students to obtain more thorough knowledge with much better conditions for fluent English communication and activation of study and improvement of the formed skills and abilities.

CHETVERYK Victor<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2137-2095>*H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***EXPRESSIVENESS OF OCCASIONAL DEGREES OF
COMPARISON IN POETIC WORKS**

Aim. The aim is to review the functioning of occasional degrees of comparison and the actualization of their poetic potential in the language of poetry.

Results. For the modern field of philology, the poetic text has become the object of analysis not only in the direction of literary studies but is also considered as the field of active linguistic processes. Morphological field of linguistic science points out that a poetic text is a space of active language processes, in particular, the formation of non-normative and occasional forms. Such lexical units attract attention and are remembered by the reader for their originality and unusualness. Non-traditional and non-normative occasional processes, being actualized in poetic texts, actively contribute to the expansion of the possibilities of non-traditional implementations of the language system and frequently influence the further development of the language normativity.

Based on the analysis of several poetic works and their fragments it was noted that *occasional forms* are quite actively implemented in the poetic text. This phenomenon is facilitated by the fact that only in poetry the language reveals all its possibilities. Several facts contribute to the functioning of such units: *firstly*, the language of poetry itself allows the implementation of non-normative gradation; *secondly*, according to many scientists, degrees of comparison can be formed on the basis of units, the semantics of which allows it (however, for traditional views, such formations remain non-normative).

The most common phenomenon of grammatical occasionalism in the plane of degrees of comparison is the formation of degrees of comparison from qualitative adjectives because traditionally grammar denies the formation of such forms. However, the grammatical occasionalisms are the most expressive ones, namely the degrees of comparison formed from parts of speech that normatively can't form such lexemes. It should be noted that quite often the formation of such grammatical occasionalisms based on *juxtaposition* as on one of the most productive ways of grammatical actualization and highlighting the expressive and figurative potential of morphological meanings and forms (Chetveryk, 2022).

Conclusions. Such units, functioning in a poetic text, become the center of expressiveness of the artistic work. However, occasional formations also can become a kind of "variant of the norm" in the language development process because they show language ability in forming new lexical units and their creative potential. And frequent use of non-normative forms gradually begins to be perceived as a part of the literary norm, not an element of expressiveness or a language game. It makes it possible to consider adjective's degrees of comparison as a tool for language development. That is why a detailed study of non-normative degrees of comparison that function in the language of poetry is a perspective for further research.

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THE ESSENCE OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF JUNIOR SCHOOLCHILDREN

Purpose. An urgent issue today is the intensification of cognitive activity of students and expanding the scope of their interests. Modern students have access to a variety of sources of information, but often the availability of ready-made information contributes to the development of passivity, and, consequently, levels out the desire to search, to know, to create, i.e. to act in general. This paper focuses on the strategies of returning students to active cognitive activity; on the ways to make the learning process as close as possible to the demands and capabilities of the child.

Results. The problem of development of activation of cognitive activity was studied by O. Zhorzhik, O. Savchenko, I. Shamova, L. Shushora, G. Shchukina and others. The importance of intensifying cognitive activity was emphasized by prominent teachers of the past such as A. Disterweg, J. Comenius, V. Sukhomlinsky.

Learning activities are cognitive, because they are aimed at changing the personal experience of the student. This is one of the main types of human activities aimed at self-development, in the process of which is the mastery of the content of subjects and the necessary means or skills and abilities by which the student receives education. The processes of thinking, attention, memory, and will are involved in cognitive activity. During this activity, the attitude of the individual to the surrounding phenomena is always expressed.

The purposefulness of mental activity and innate talents of students directly depends on the effectiveness of cognitive activity and is the key to the effectiveness of educational activities and the learning process of primary school children. The desire and ability to acquire knowledge independently, to show a creative approach to activity indicates a developed cognitive interest, cognitive activity and independence.

Note that the modern primary school is designed to identify and develop the abilities of students, to form skills and desire to learn. And these tasks can be realized by means of formation of cognitive activity of younger schoolboys. Therefore, it is advisable to consider the classification of teaching methods by type of cognitive activity of students, which characterizes the level of independence of students and cognitive activity during learning. According to this, the following teaching methods are distinguished: explanatory-illustrative, reproductive, method of problem presentation of knowledge, partial-search and research.

Conclusions. Thus, the effectiveness of education in a modern school depends on the teacher's ability to choose the right methods and techniques of teaching in specific conditions for each lesson. Teaching methods by type of cognitive activity reveal the dynamics of cognitive activity of students from the perception of ready-made knowledge, their memorization and reproduction to creative cognitive work, which provides independent mastery of new knowledge. Cognitive activity is the unity of perception, theoretical thinking and practical activity.

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DIGITALIZATION OF LEARNING PROCESS IN UKRAINE

The aim of the research is to analyze some theoretical aspects of the development of digital technologies in the learning process in higher educational establishments in Ukraine.

Results. The growth of modern digital technologies usage has made it possible to apply them in many spheres of life: business sphere, education, private life, etc. A contemporary higher educational establishment is a digital space where learning process can be conducted with the help of diverse online-platforms that are rather effective for both learning and assessment (e.g., the implementation of separate applications or platforms for delivering lectures/practical hours and final testing). During the research of this issue theme, it was found out that the use of digital technologies improves the individualization of the learning process and offers many opportunities for higher educational establishments (e.g., constant online access to all educational resources, the transparency of educational process, etc.).

Many scientists pay attention to the question of digitalization all over the world. Among Ukrainian scientists, we can name V. Kovalchuk, R. Kukhar, O. Tokarchuk, A. Zaliskyand and others who investigate digitalization of the learning process, methodological aspects of their usage in higher education and, thus, highlight the importance and the necessity of the implementation of digital technologies because of coronavirus and the impossibility to have face-to-face lessons in some parts of the country (martial law).

The analysis of the literature made it possible to state that there are already formed compulsory requirements towards the digital competences of the citizens (based on the research of Ukrainian Institute of the Future), namely: computer literacy, content and online security knowledge, digital content creation, communication and online interaction, information literacy.

Moreover, the application of digital technologies in the learning process let us increase the speed and quality of education. Digital and interactive technologies facilitate the use of such method as case study, project methods or scientific-research work. So, the level of understanding of information motivates further learning of the discussed theme, but in Ukraine, we can see insufficient level of digital technologies usage in learning process on a wide scale.

Conclusions. We can say that the digitalization of learning process gives the opportunity to improve the process, makes learning more flexible and student-centered, and accompanies more favourable conditions for further development of the country.

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TASKS AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY: INVESTIGATING ENGLISH LEARNING IN THE THIRD AGE

The present work reports the final results of a piece of research on the Scientific Initiation (IC) modality, PICIN/CNPQ, developed from 2020 to 2021, whose **main goal** was to investigate and systematize published studies regarding the teaching and/or learning of additional languages (L2) for senior learners, seeking in particular to analyze research that has made use of the task-based language teaching approach (ELLIS, 2003; SKEHAN, 1996), combined with the use of new technologies, having the elderly as a target audience.

Results. In order to map the studies in the area, we carried out a systematic review of the literature in three electronic database platforms – Portal de Periódicos da CAPES, RevistaReCALL, and Revista CALICO – having a ten-year time frame as a filter, and using “Older learners AND second language learning AND technology” and “elderly AND second language” as searching terms.

In general, the results suggest that, despite the apparent scarcity of research focused on this topic, some researchers employ different methodologies and methods that aim to help the learning process of these learners, in addition to the consideration of some advantages and challenges of learning an L2 at this age.

It was also observed how important living in society is, since “participation in social activities after old age significantly reduces the risk of functional disability and dependence on other people for everyday life” (BAILDON, 2018, p. 259).

Additionally, participating in activities such as learning a new language can offer, in the long term, direct physiological benefits, decreasing stress and loneliness, for example, and reducing the appearance of genes and disease-related traits (BAILDON, 2018).

Conclusions. With social exposure through language learning, the tendency is for older learners to be more confident and willing (e.g., BAILDON, 2018), more autonomous (e.g., OLIVARES-CUHAT, 2018) and more motivated (e.g. YAO, 2019).

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THE TASK-BASED APPROACH: A TEACHING PRACTICUM ANALYSIS IN AN EFL BRAZILIAN CONTEXT

The present article **aims** to discuss and analyze, under the light of the task-based approach (e.g., ELLIS, 2003; SKEHAN, 1996; NUNAN, 2004), one intervention proposal of “Estágio Supervisionado II”/ Supervised Practicum II from a group of students of the English Teaching Program Letras, Língua Inglesa e suas Literaturas – at UNEB (Bahia State University, Campus IV – Jacobina, Brazil) of the year of 2021. The research was developed through the analysis of several workshop materials and teaching (practicum) trainee productions (class plans, workshop proposal, webpage and padlets, activities, workshop’s Instagram, final reports) proposed and made available by English (as a foreign language (EFL)) teachers-to-be.

Results. The main goal was to identify whether any proposals were aligned with the task-based language teaching (TBLT) approach (and if so, verify which task characteristics were predominant in them), and how they integrated digital technologies, considering their implementation happened during the COVID-19 pandemic. The TBLT approach emphasizes pedagogical work focused on the student and the use of language for communication (ELLIS, 2003) that allows for more meaningful and dynamic learning (TREVISOL, 2019). Therefore, an investigation of Practicum productions – which may be linked to the language teaching approach with tasks – is relevant to know the different types of activities that could be done in the foreign language classroom. Though we had previously analyzed a total of four (4) Practicum intervention works, here we delve deeper into one of them: “*Lightning*, oficina de microcontos mais rápidos que a luz”. This workshop aimed to explore the practice of reading and writing with the “micro-conto” (microstory) genre – based on the task-based language approach – with the purpose of developing lexicon through creative writing. Regarding *Lightning*, the teachers of the workshop claim that TBLT made it possible for them to work with a free and diverse audience (ranging in age from fourteen to twenty-five), in addition to placing the student at the center of the proposal's development. Also, it gave students the opportunity to participate in tasks whose main purpose was the development of writing skills (through fiction) in the English language.

The final products of the workshop were nine “micro-contos” (short stories) produced by the students. The teachers explained in the final report that they could perceive the reflection of the theoretical material used during the writing of the stories and that the goal of exploring creativity through writing while using the English language was satisfactorily fulfilled. Overall then, it could be noticed that tasks have been present in these initial experiences of future English teachers at the context investigated.

Conclusions. Furthermore, this teaching methodology may also favor students' writing engagement, encourages them to be significantly involved in the task and it may perhaps even increase their motivation for learning English.

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CRITICAL THINKING AS A TOKEN OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER CULTURE OF THE FUTURE OFFICER

The purpose of the study is to highlight the role of critical thinking in the formation and development of gender culture of the future officer in the process of studying in a higher military educational institution.

Results. Addressing the issue is caused by material changes in the understanding of men's and women's roles in the modern society and rising of roles of unimitative, individual and unique manifestations of human personalities. A person's gender culture includes gender competence, gender ideas, notions, expectations, values, stereotypes, specific gender models of conduct, needs, interests, forms and results of activity.

Gender socialization of cadets mostly happens in dominating conditions of the traditional gender stereotypes and recommendations as to the gender role behavior, standardized notions of men's and women's traits of character and models of conduct. The majority of cadets do not demonstrate any thoughtfulness or interest in their attitude towards gender patterns of the world structure or towards issues of gender identity.

From the traditional point of view, female personality traits are rated as less prestigious in the society as they are associated with orientation to tertiary activities, fulfilling of matrimonial and family duties. On the contrary, male traits are associated with social and political initiative and vigor, professional success and efficiency. Such stereotypes provide for unequal social rating of men and women, orient them to different predetermined life strategies, ways and methods of self-realization, and serve as specific background for their conduct.

Breaking the bounds of such stereotyped perception of social reality presupposes the availability of a matured analytical thinking, of such features of critical thinking as flexibility in the consideration of alternatives and thoughts, readiness to reconsider and change the views in cases when such changes are reasonable. Critical thinking consists in the ability to resist the influence of the imposed thoughts and, on the contrary, to be able to evaluate them, to distinguish strong and weak sides, to pick the essential implication out of the general content and reveal the available errors of judgment. Critical thinking is tightly connected with personal reflection which testifies to a high level of the person's psychological maturity and his or her level of self-actualization.

Conclusions. So, the maturity of critical thinking is a very important criterion of the level of personality development, a strategic goal of the higher education process and a background of gender culture of the future officer. In this regard the determining factors are not limited to studying the subjects of gender thematic range but also include integration of gender issues into existing programs of academic subjects and periodic monitoring of the maturity level of the cadets' gender culture with the aim of its further correction.

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THE ROLE OF MULTIMEDIA IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING

An important factor determining the progress of the education system is scientific and technical development, in particular, the wide use of information technologies in learning and teaching. Thus, the **purpose** of this research is to highlight the advantages and explain the advisability of using multimedia learning tools in foreign language lessons.

Results. Multimedia may be defined as an integration of text, colour, graphical images, animation, audio sound, and full-motion video in a single application. Examples of multimedia products can be presentations, movies, cartoons, and games. Multimedia can be divided into linear and non-linear depending on the method of providing information.

An example of a linear way of providing information is a movie, where the person who just watches the movie plays a passive role. A non-linear way of providing information allows a person to participate by cooperating with a means of displaying multimedia data, for example, in a computer game. Human participation in this process is called interactivity. In addition to that, multimedia products that are designed and developed when studying educational material are the most effective, because it develops thinking skills, cognitive activity and the ability to conduct independent research. It is known, that the use of video has been found to effectively promote the development of grammatical skills and listening comprehension. In a multimedia environment, those who study a foreign language will be engaged in learning effectively via the attractive pictures, sound or animation component, becoming more active and autonomous.

When considering the use of multimedia in teaching and learning foreign languages, one can observe both positive and negative aspects. As for the positive points, the following can be highlighted: multimedia enables to apply an individual approach; multimedia provides modern material that meets the interests and needs of those who study a foreign language; multimedia promotes motivation and independent study of the material; multimedia contributes to the achievement of one of the main goals of learning a foreign language - the formation of communicative competence.

Regarding the existing disadvantages, there are several of them: insufficient computer literacy and lack of time to prepare for the lesson; loss of concentration due to insufficient motivation to study. As we can see from the above, there are many more positive aspects, which expose the expediency of using multimedia in the educational process.

Conclusions. Consequently, it can be noted that multimedia creates the opportunity to improve one's learning effectively. However, it is important to state that multimedia does not replace the teacher. Multimedia is a tool that helps to find an effective way of learning for two participants of the educational process.

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FOLK IMAGES-SYMBOLS IN THE SONG “RED FLOWER” (“CHERVONA RUTA”) BY V. IVASIUK

Purpose: The topicality of the research lies in the fact that today there is no thorough study of folklore images-symbols in the work of Volodymyr Ivasiuk, due to the fact that the genre of mass song was rather the subject of interest of Soviet musicologists, that was explained by mass song’s entertainment function, the simplicity and accessibility of its musical language.

Results: “Red Flower” (“Chervona Ruta”) is the author’s most famous song, which, like the image itself, became a symbol of all the best and purest in modern music. Every nation that does not develop its culture in all dimensions is doomed to spiritual impoverishment. And when we say that the Ukrainian song of the USSR era was somewhat one-sided, we must not forget that, despite all the prohibitions of the Stalinist-Brezhnev denationalizers, the folklore wealth of the people found the strength to make its way to people’s hearts.

Folk images-symbols in the song “Red Flower” by V. Ivasiuk had not only a traditional interpretation but also an interpretation by the author himself.

For example, the “red flower”, according to the artist’s idea, is not just a sincere love between two young people. It has an unfathomable depth, a higher secret. In the text, the author draws attention to girls’ charms, because it has long been believed that a woman is the guardian of rites and beliefs – “Where you get those charms?” The young people’s feelings are combined by a single symbol, which is the “char-zillia” (“magic herbs”) in the text. According to folk tales, it is a symbol of eternal and pure love. For a long time, people continuously try to find the single and native soul, just like the heroes of the analyzed song, “sontse-ruta” (“sun-gold flower”) which is a symbol of discovery, the discovery of happiness and love – “You found the sun-gold flower”.

In most Ukrainian songs, the girl’s beauty is presented through various symbols that can best convey the woman’s charm, and in the song, the author used the cosmogonic symbol of “pure water” / “crystal clear water” / “spring water”, which in folklore mean the extraordinary beauty and chastity of a young girl – “your beauty is crystal clear water”.

In the song, there are motifs of the natural girl’s beauty, which acts like a charm on a young man. Two young people discover for themselves the purity and happiness of eternal love, as a precious and unattainable wealth, which is the main problem of the song – its unattainability.

Conclusions: The usage of folklore images-symbols in the song “Red Flower” (“Chervona Ruta”) form in the text a deep cultural reflection of the Ukrainian people’s souls.

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UTILIZATION OF MOBILE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING UKRAINIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Mobile technologies have become an integral part of modern society and are actively utilized in the educational process, in particular, for learning foreign languages. The paper is **aimed** to identify the didactic characteristics of mobile technologies for learning Ukrainian as a foreign language.

Results. Applying various gadgets in the learning process is becoming especially relevant nowadays, during the Russian war in Ukraine, when international students had to leave Ukraine. Therefore, in these conditions, educators actively implement mobile technologies. Currently, this is the only means of communication and information exchange with groupmates and the instructor, involvement in the educational process.

Therefore, applying mobile technologies in the process of studying a foreign language has some advantages:

- quick access to a variety of information, namely accessing resources in a short time;
- the availability of mobile devices in the educational process;
- the possibility of interaction and information exchange of materials and correspondence.

When learning Ukrainian as a foreign language, it is advisable to use such mobile technologies as e-mail, mobile dictionaries, podcasts, mobile reference resources, mobile learning applications, etc. Thus, in the absence of paper textbooks, international students utilize their electronic version on smartphones or tablets. Using mobile devices, the students search for additional information available on the Internet to deepen their understanding of the learning material. With the help of e-mail, feedback is provided to the students, and written messages are exchanged. Viber and WhatsApp are used for sending assignments to students, as well as for conducting feedback with students, transferring files from one device to another.

Mobile electronic dictionaries (Lingvo, Google Translate, etc.) are undoubtedly indispensable assistants in the process of learning Ukrainian as a foreign language. They help not only quickly find the translation of the desired word or phrase, but also often offer a dictionary article with examples of usage, a variant of pronunciation. In this way, students develop skills for independent educational activities and enrich their vocabulary. International students who are just starting to learn the Ukrainian language (level A1-A2) can use such mobile applications as Duolingo, Busuu, etc. For example, applying Mondly: Learn Ukrainian Easily, the students have the opportunity to master core Ukrainian words, form sentences, learn to speak Ukrainian phrases and take part in conversations.

Conclusions. Thus, mobile technologies provide many opportunities for improving the quality of the process of learning Ukrainian as a foreign language and the independent activity of international students.

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PECULIARITIES OF LEARNING AND TEACHING ENGLISH DURING THE WAR

Even during the war, Ukrainian students return to distance learning and continue to study various foreign languages, including English. That is why **the purpose** of this work is to consider the peculiarities of learning and teaching English in the conditions of war with the help of computer and telecommunication technologies.

Results. First of all, it should be noted that the study of the English language in the conditions of war in Ukrainian educational institutions is carried out in a distance format with the help of various online learning platforms. In our opinion, the choice of a platform for online learning, tools and resources for distance learning of the English language should be made taking into account the expected results, universality – the possibility of using one platform for all classes, the clarity of the interface for learners of different ages, accessibility for children with special educational needs, usability on devices with different operating systems and security.

Distance learning and teaching of foreign languages take place with the help of a set of measures: means of providing educational materials to students, monitoring their success, consultation with the program pedagogue, interactive cooperation of the subjects of the educational process, the possibility of updating, supplementing the educational course with new information, correcting errors.

The modern educational process of teaching foreign languages takes place using distance learning platforms, among which the most common are: Moodle, Google Classroom, Cisco Webex and Lino. In addition, an important modern effective tool for remote learning of English, like any foreign language, is electronic interactive whiteboards, which are good assistants for conducting training sessions, conferences and presentations.

It should be remembered that helping students to discover their potential through motivation and expanding their opportunities, checking the studied material and homework, setting grades and helping students to pass exams well is of particular importance during distance learning of the English language.

Conclusions. Therefore, in the conditions of war, English language learning in Ukrainian educational institutions is carried out remotely, and therefore it is important for the teacher to correctly choose the online learning platform, distance learning tools and resources, and properly organize the learning process.

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PRACIA, A UKRAINIAN BRAZILIAN NEWSPAPER: PRESERVATION, DIGITIZATION AND RESEARCH POSSIBILITIES

The **aim** of this paper is to present the project entitled “Brazil/Ukraine Press: The Pracia Newspaper and the Ukrainian Immigration in Brazil”, carried out by the Documentation and Memory Center (CEDOC/I) from *Universidade Estadual do Centro-Oeste* (Midwest State University), Irati Campus, Brazil. The Pracia newspaper, targeted at “Ruthenians” in Brazil, was founded in 1912 in Prudentópolis, Paraná, where Ukrainian immigrants have settled since 1895. In 1913, when its editor passed away, priests from the Order of Saint Basil took on its publication. Until April 1915, the eight - pages paper had been published twice a month; and then, a four-page issue has been published once a week. They have also published *Boletim Missionário Ucraino no Brasil* (Ukrainian Missionary Newsletter in Brazil) and a religious almanac, also named Pracia.

Results. By publishing the newspaper, the priests exchanged material with other newspapers in Ukrainian language published abroad, mostly from Ukraine, USA and Canada, but also from Germany, France, and Argentina. Collections of these newspapers and mentioned above local periodical publications are preserved by CEDOC/I. In a joint project together with the *Universidade Federal do Paraná* (Federal University of Paraná) and the *Faculdade São Basílio Magno* (São Basílio Magno Faculty), an institution that also keeps a collection of the paper, CEDOC/I is coordinating the digitization of Pracia’s first publishing period (1912-1941).

From 1941 to 1946, Pracia was not published due to WW II. Since 1993, Pracia has been published both in Portuguese and Ukrainian, and after 2016, only online. The main goal of the project is to create a digital repository to make Pracia available for researchers. Besides the digitization, CEDOC/I is researching bibliography on the Ukrainian language press, the Ukrainian immigration in Brazil and the “Ukrainian Brazilian” culture, language and history, in order to make it available in the digital repository. A third goal of is to create an open access catalogue by indexing the content of each issue (1912-1922).

Conclusions. The project started in May 2022 and will have the duration of 2 years. Based on the already digitized newspaper issues, readers can realize the main aim of the Basilian priests to spread and strengthen the catholic faith and to promote the use of the Ukrainian language in the community. They were also cultural mediators, as they translated and spread news about the political, social and economic situation in Parana state and Brazil and, at the same time, published material on the political situation in Central Europe, in order to (re)connect immigrants and descendants to their territory of origin and to (re)build their ethnic identity.

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THE ENGLISH TEACHER IN THE CONTEXT OF IRATI-PR: CHALLENGES AND POSSIBILITIES FOR AN ENDANGERED SPECIES

This seminar consists in a brief reflection upon the university extension project called *Em tom de língua franca: O curso de Letras Inglês no contexto social de Irati e região* (In a lingua franca tone: English Language Studies course in the social context of Irati and its surroundings). Participants are three English Language and Literatures professors from the Languages Department of UNICENTRO/I, two undergraduate (from the first and fourth year of studying) and one egressed student. The **purpose** was to establish a dialogue between the university teachers and students with the local community regarding the profile of graduate professionals, also taking into account the demands and interests of postgraduates as well as, secondarily, studying the possibility of implementing translation studies as a complementary training within the course, in order to attract more candidates.

Results. Therefore, project proponents have conducted a survey of high school students from two State Schools, one in Irati and the other in nearby town Rebouças, as well as university freshmen, sophomore, and egressed students' impressions, opinions, and suggestions concerning the course and the teacher's profession. In the end, 18 university students, 20 egressed students, and 80 high school students (53 from Irati and 27 from Rebouças) took part in the survey.

The participants created a workshop on translation studies to be carried out in high school classrooms. During these workshops, insights emerging from students' answers to the surveys have taken place in a light, ludic, interactive, and informative manner, integrating internal and external community. As expected, results were satisfying: students, teachers, and proponents have enjoyed the experience and were able to think of what it could mean to the future of the course. Nevertheless, project members also discussed about teacher training in an era of crises in the profession and the humanities, as well as about how contents studied in the course are distant from the reality of residents from Irati and its surroundings.

Conclusions. Survey also shows: **1)** most students and egressed students are from other towns, **2)** the majority of them work during the course in order to pay for their expenses, and most of them do not work as teachers, **3)** even though some do identify with the profession, most prefer other fields such as translation, **4)** just one high school student considers becoming a teacher, while none of them considers becoming an English teacher, **5)** About 30% of high school students find translation interesting, while less than 10% find teaching interesting, **6)** 25% of high school students have no interest in taking any graduate course at all after they finish school. Findings, however, are but a fragment of a bigger picture which needs to be further investigated, perhaps in more schools, as to help us effectively understand and address the problems raised.

GULICH Olena*H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***EDUCATIONAL FRONT OF UKRAINIAN STUDENTS**

The educational system of Ukraine already had experience of distance learning due to the periods of quarantine caused by the *COVID-19 pandemic*. Nevertheless, distance learning during the quarantine period was not burdened by all the challenges that were caused by military actions on the territory of our country. The **purpose** is to show educational front of Ukrainian students.

Results. The stress caused by war which all the citizens of our country had those days was one of the most terrible challenges. Each Ukrainian understood that each of us must contribute to the approaching of victory. For us teachers, Education has become such a front as our country needs educated, skilled specialists in different fields. Educational process was continued: at schools, institutes and universities.

Despite the fact that many buildings of universities, schools and colleges were seriously damaged or practically destroyed and are still being destroyed a lot of teachers and students have published on their social network pages: "Buildings are not a soul! Buildings can be destroyed, but our spirit, our desire for education and freedom, cannot be broken!" The educational process in a distance format was not stopped and the academic year was successfully completed in a regular mode throughout Ukraine.

However, the war scattered Ukrainian pupils and students not only all over Europe, but all over the world. Many of them had their homes destroyed, many fled the occupied territories, and many still have their homes in unsafe areas, many students are forced to remain in foreign countries as refugees. The educational system of Ukraine is trying to balance and is doing everything possible not to lose the educated elite, the future of our country - our students. We appreciate our patriotic students who, being in a foreign land, continue to organize all kinds of events in support of Ukraine, and are determined to continue their education in Ukrainian universities in a distance form.

It must be said that students who were forced to stay abroad were once again convinced that knowledge of the English language turned out to be a useful skill not only for everyday communication, but also became an obligatory "attribute" for every specialist in chosen field. That is why the Department of Theory and Practice of the English Language of H.S. Skovoroda KhNPU developed a number of disciplines, aiming both to improve communication skills, e.g. "The English language for everyday use", and disciplines that will help to achieve the goals in chosen specialty: "The English language for a future profession", "The English language in professional situations", "The English language in the sphere of professional communication", "The English language workshop on business and scientific writing".

Conclusions. Bachelors and Masters of the Faculty of Physics and Mathematics of H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University are constantly working to improve their English language skills in their educational area. Their research results are presented in this section.

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THE CHALLENGES BEFORE UKRAINIAN EDUCATION: FROM THE PANDEMIC INTO THE WAR

Purpose. This paper aims to highlight the urgent tasks that the Ukrainian higher education has run into during the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020-2022, and the war which started on 24 February 2022, with the focus on the principal transformations in the teaching strategies and approaches.

Results. In 2016, before the Covid-19 pandemic, the Ukrainian state investigation of the level of digital competence of the population and its impact on the country's economy showed low e-skills, no e-health, low trust to e-services, and no smart living. The educational sector also demonstrated low e-skills of its participants – both students' and the teaching staff's – and accordingly required further digitalization of schools and universities, renewal of the content, providing general access to online resources.

The global pandemic of 2020/21, caused by Covid-19, in addition to its catastrophic consequences in Ukraine as well as in other countries, has had a reverse side, as it contributed to the incredible velocity of the digitalization of the population, and particularly those who involved into the educational process. The digital transformation of the society accordingly has driven the growth of new educational strategies and altered the priorities.

The Ukrainian universities rapidly responded to the changing social conditions and students' individual needs. Speaking about foreign language teaching strategies, I should say, that the turn to the online teaching, both synchronic and diachronic, on the ZOOM and MOODLE platforms, the use of electronic devices (often simultaneous), attention to the development of critical thinking, communication competence, 'soft skills' and creative thinking have become the errands of today's Ukrainian educational agenda.

The teaching experience acquired during the pandemic overall lockdown, with acquisition of new information technologies and development of necessary skills by both teachers and students helps Ukrainian education withstand today the Russian aggression and continue the educational process. Scattered all over Ukraine and Europe, both the University teaching staff and our students carry on active and efficacious collaboration, synchronically and diachronically.

Conclusions. The transition to online teaching requires both educational service providers and users, regardless of their age, the acquisition of skills and abilities to use digital technologies, the development of 'soft skills', creative thinking, and communication competence. "Digital transformation is a matter of survival" has become the motto and the feature of the nowadays. The current challenges that the Ukrainian society had been experiencing require further development and enhancement of teaching strategies and approaches.

HREBESHKOVA Anastasiia*H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***THE USE INFOGRAPHICS IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**

The current generation of children perceives graphic images much better than textual information, so visualization of learning is gradually becoming a priority. Research shows that creating visual explanations improves learning. This paper **aims** to highlight the use infographics in educational process.

Results. Creating infographics is one of the primary teaching tools for promoting and expanding visual literacy. It helps you communicate with each other, make sense of and seek different perspectives, meet technical literacy standards, improve your research papers and find reliable sources of information, and demonstrate your understanding of the subject in a variety of ways. It also helps teachers save time creating visual aids, especially when using infographic templates. Using infographics helps students think critically about a subject, data set or complex ideas and it also helps students organize information in a logical way

One of the modern tools aimed at effective visual presentation of information is infographics. Infographics are: a way to convey a large amount of information using simple and clear visual methods; modern teaching method; form of information design; a type of educational creativity that involves combining graphics with text in a wide variety of proportions. Infographic technology based on the fact that images make data more attractive for perception, contribute to its effective memorization, increase its persuasiveness. Visual communication tools use when you need compact and logical provide a large amount of information, because up to 90% of information is a pupil perceives with the eyes.

There are several types of infographics: by display method (static and dynamic with animated elements) and by source type (analytical, economic, for reporting news, event recovery infographics, etc.). Infographics make it possible to organize the educational process in two interdependent directions — from the general to the specific, and vice versa. the main benefits of using infographics for teaching are It aids students in organizing information in a logical way. Infographic creation helps meet tech literacy standards. The process of making infographics helps students improve their research chops and find trustworthy sources of information. It helps students exhibit their understanding of a subject in different ways.

There are many types of tasks for using infographics in the educational process. For example, to highlight the main concepts from infographic and tell the learned information. Appropriately, as homework, create your own narrative based on this infographic, or vice versa - create an infographic based on the provided text. In this way, students learn to highlight and analyze data. Also, one of the interesting tasks is to create a synopsis in the lesson using infographics.

Conclusions. Therefore, the use of infographics in the educational process significantly intensifies and optimizes the process of assimilation of new knowledge, and ultimately leads to better memorization of educational material.

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MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES USE FOR STUDENTS' TRAINING IN PLAYING SPORTS

It is difficult to imagine a modern strategy for students' training without using digital tools to be highly qualified athletes. The main place in a strategy implementation is given to the use of the latest technical and information tools in training: new high-tech sports equipment and inventory; modernization in competition and training venues; use of computer, information and multimedia technologies.

One of the conditions for education and training effectiveness is the use of modern technologies, in particular, multimedia tools, multimedia test programs, graphic modeling of training activities. The **purpose** is to show the role of multimedia in students' training to be highly qualified athletes.

Results. The important role in the digital facility in education and training is played by learning video materials that allow to provide visually the information related to dynamic processes, for example, when teaching various motor actions, analyzing biomechanical characteristics, tactical actions, etc.

Such materials can be used both independently as a separate thematic video film, and as the components of appropriate digit tools. With the advent of digital video cameras and special programs for processing digital video information (Windows Movie Maker, Adobe Premiere, Pinnacle Studio, Ulead VideoStudio, Sony Vegas, etc.), that allow capturing, editing and outputting video information to various media, the work of creating learning video materials for students has become much easier. In this regard, multimedia training and test programs for students are of some interest. The structure of educational programs is determined by their tasks, which in this case are as follows: 1. Presentation the main phases of athletes' movement by multimedia. 2. Modeling the athletes' effective technique taking into account biomechanical parameters. 3. Test and self-monitoring athletes' technical training. The use of such programs in the education and training has fundamental differences compared to traditional forms and methods, namely: the possibility of athletes' technical skill development by a directed coach activity; the use of mainly individual and group training forms; implementation of test and self-monitoring in mastering the techniques in a playing sport (especially it applies to the ability to view video fragments, including viewing in a normal mode, slow motion, and stop-frame mode).

Conclusion. Educational multimedia programs, depending on the tasks of the education and training, can be used both as a kind of simulators and educational tools, as well as for diagnosis and assessment of the level of knowledge and skills.

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EDUCATIONAL CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES DURING THE WAR

The war has completely changed our minds, encouraging us to appreciate every moment of life. Such ordinary things as reading your favourite book, peaceful conversations with your friends or relatives, walking in the park or chilling out in the nearby café have become so valuable because everything can disappear in a minute. Thus, our attitude to the education has also changed.

The **aim** of the abstract is to clarify the point of the educational challenges Ukrainian students are facing during the war, and to reveal the possible ways to continue studying through difficult times.

The **results** of the research have shown that the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine has paralyzed studying as most people have found it difficult to concentrate when the country is suffering from the rival, the cities are being badly damaged and, what is worse, innocent civilians are dying. Moreover, it seems impossible to think of studying when your house has been destroyed or in the case when somebody of your family has been killed by the occupiers. But our sadness won't improve the situation, and all that remains is to continue living despite of any difficulties.

The same point concerns education. Now, during the war, it is very important to carry on studying, to develop yourself in order to be able to restore the country after our victory. By the way, Serhiy Zhadan's novel «The boarding school» reveals the same problem: after Russian invasion of Donbas the education system was among those things that suffered first and foremost. But one of the main ideas, implemented by Zhadan, is that the intellectual front is as significant as the military, political or economic one. So, we should not lose spirit, but seek out the ways to educate ourselves by reading books, carrying out some scientific researches, communicating with our teachers or tutors discussing new ideas that may be implemented after the war or even now. Moreover, studying can be regarded as a good way to distract yourself from bad thoughts.

In addition, we have conducted the survey among students of various faculties on the importance of education during the war. One third of the respondents have chosen the option «Of course, education is crucial», almost 60 percent admitted it was difficult question for them, and the rest of students are convinced that education is not something valuable to think of in the case of war. As a result, a significant number of students have acknowledged that war is not an obstacle to intellectual development, and will, sheer determination and confidence in the future are the key to full life even during the difficult times.

In **conclusion**, the importance of education during war is undoubtable. It requires a great deal of effort, but we should realize that education is considered to be one of the efficient ways to promote peace, security and prevent the world from future conflicts.

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REMINISCENCE OF EDUCATION IN POST-WAR YEARS: SIERRA LEONE AS A CASE STUDY

The **aim** is to show reminiscence of education in post-war years.

Results. Historically, Sierra Leone has been hailed for being one of the first country in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) to experience the western type of education that is modelled on the curriculum of classical education – this typically include subjects like History, Geography, Latin, Greek, etc., in addition to the core curriculum of English Language, Mathematics and Sciences (incorporating Biology, Chemistry and Physics). Because of this, the country over the years became popularly known as the “*Athens of West Africa*”, signifying specialty in classical education. The continued influence of bad governance over the years destroyed the fabrics of high-quality education enjoyed by people even after independence in the early 1960s. Most importantly, during the latter part of 1980s to early 1990s, the economy was in a state where the World Bank modelled agenda of Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) was set in place to address some of the ills of poor macroeconomic management (Jackson & Jabbie, 2020).

However, good intent the program was as planned by the World Bank, it was not very well in favour to address challenges of poverty and also, fiscal challenges faced by the country (Warburton & Jackson, 2020). The gravity of economic malaise was also widespread around this period and particularly in the late 1980s, with the intervention of the rebel incursion by the Revolutionary United Front (RUF), headed by Foday Sankoh. This period was considered very traumatizing for the entire nation and particularly with its influence on the country’s educational system. The long-lasting nature of the civil crisis dented every aspect of economic life, with temporary closure of educational system and the recruitment of younger boys into becoming armed fighters.

In view of the above simplified introduction, the objectives of the paper are set as follows: (i) to provide a historical narration of Sierra Leone’s educational system, (ii) Provide an assessment of the impact of war on the country’s educational system and pace of development in the current digital age; and finally, (iii) To proffer some discourses for policy dialogue in embracing the developmental landscape of the country.

Conclusion. In view of the above introduction and objectives, the rest of the conference paper will be structured as follows: **(1)** Introduction, **(2)** Pre-war narrative of education in Sierra Leone, **(3)** Impact of the war on educational fabrics, **(4)** Post-war structuring of the education system: Inclusivity and expansion, **(5)** Contested Terrain of Present-day Developments and **(6)** Conclusion and policy dialogue for embracing development.

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REMINISCENCE OF EDUCATION IN POST-WAR YEARS: SIERRA LEONE AS A CASE STUDY

PRESENTED BY: Emerson A Jackson and Hudson F. Jackson

INTRODUCTION

THE ATHENS OF WEST AFRICA

Sierra Leone is once the termed the Athens of West Africa – this epitomizes the culture of classical education taught in schools.

PRE-WAR

CHARACTERISTICS OF PRE-WAR SYSTEM

- High standard of education delivery;
- Internationally acceptable qualifications;
- High output from students;
- Existence of quality assurance.

THE WAR-TIME

- Destruction of the fabrics of quality education.
- Brain drain

IMPACT OF THE WAR

- Depletion of educational values;
- High rate of drop-out;
- Human resources constraints to support sustained development in institutions;
 - Corruption
- Misplacement of educational skills.

POST-WAR RECONSTRUCTION

Introduction of Free Education

Technical Skills development

Addressing brain-drain gap

Encouragement of STEM

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TASKS, CREATIVE WRITING AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY: EXPLORING FAN FICTION IN LANGUAGE LEARNING CONTEXTS

The present work **aims to** report the final results of a research developed through the Scientific Initiation (IC) program between 2021 and 2022, funded by PICIN/UNEB, and the main focus of it was to explore and analyze studies developed in the Applied Linguistics field that discussed about fan fiction as a creative writing practice in online spaces and its potential resources to language learning, prioritizing pieces of research that presented task-based language teaching as a methodological basis (ELLIS, 2003; NUNAN, 2004) and those who brought considerations about the challenges that permeate the use of digital technologies during these processes.

Results. From that, a systematic review of the literature was carried out in three online databases — Portal de Periódicos da CAPES, CALICO Journal and ReCALL Journal — using the search string ("fanfiction" OR "fanfic" OR "fan fiction") AND ("task" OR "tarefa" OR "task-based") for the first search base and the search term "fanfiction" for the last two. Data analysis was made possible by the full reading of the 11 articles selected. Results suggest there are several ways of understanding the potential of fan fictions in the learning processes, once being presented as an exponent of new literacies and new media resources in the classroom (SAURO, 2017; LEIGH, 2020), as well as a form of creative criticism from the process of adaptation through writing (ROMERO, 2021).

Its use linked to interactive narrative processes (CORNILLIE et al., 2021) was also presented, as well as collaborative writing and its potential in teaching literature while developing language skills (GARCIA, 2019; SAURO, SANDMARK, 2016). Among these skills, what stood out in the studies were: the improvement in the written ability using the target language, the increase of vocabulary self referring to the issues raised by the stories or text source, as well as the autonomy in writing and in the identity as a writer in an additional language.

Conclusion. As part of fan practices, fan fiction usually occurs independently of formal teaching environments and spontaneously; however, it is possible to introduce it in formal teaching contexts as long as it is well delimited its purpose and with a structured methodology to guide the student learning in the skills required by the tasks.

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TEACHING ENGLISH IN CHINA AND UKRAINE

The necessity of the research is determined by modern areas of active collaboration between the People's Republic of China and Ukraine. In the conditions of integration processes the need for comparative pedagogical researches of educational process of both countries is actualized.

The **aim** is to outline the basics of teaching English in China and Ukraine.

The content of the Recommendations of the European Council, the recommendations of the British Council on language education demand new requirements for the language quality teaching and learning, the development of new forms, methods and tools. In this regard, it is important to study the basics of teaching English in China and Ukraine.

Results. Since 2001, the National Curriculum in China has made English a compulsory subject for Chinese elementary schools. As a rule, English is studied in schools from the 2nd grade, from the age of 7, less often from the 4th grade, from the age of 9.

In middle and high schools, English continues to be studied in China, it is included in the National Curriculum as the main subject. In China, schoolchildren understand the motivation for learning English. To obtain a diploma of graduation from a college or University, an English language exam is required. All applicants to graduate school must pass an English language exam too. The level of English proficiency also affects career development in China, even being one of the necessary conditions.

In Ukraine, English is studied from the 1st grade according to the New Ukrainian School program. In 2017-2019, the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine together with international and national partners implemented a number of interrelated projects aimed at face-to-face and distance training teachers of 100 pilot Ukrainian schools to teach English in a new context.

The British Council in Ukraine took care of English teachers. 164 teachers of pilot schools and 25 methodologists of postgraduate pedagogical education took part in the training events with a total duration of 88 hours and received certificates. Also, 17 master-trainers and 120 teachers-agents of change were trained, who then trained more than 17 thousand English teachers in Ukraine who started teaching first-graders in the 2018-2019 school year.

Conclusion. China will become the world leader in the number of English learners. About 400 million Chinese learn English, there are more English learners in China than English speakers. Most Chinese insist that English is a necessary tool for bringing China closer to the world. Ukrainian teachers are trained very well to teach English as for the new demands.

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**PROBLEMS OF WAR AND PEACE IN THE
«PHILOSOPHY OF LAW» G.W.F. HEGEL**

The aim is to outline the problems of war and peace in the «Philosophy of law» G.W.F. Hegel. In our time, we face two important problems such as ensuring international security and peace between peoples. Unfortunately, there are also armed conflicts in our time. Today in our native Ukraine there is a military-political conflict, or rather a bloody war that claims thousands of lives.

Results. The geopolitical situation in and around Ukraine is influenced by global changes in the entire system of international relations. The situation around Ukraine is characterized by tension, aggravation of national-ethnic, and cultural and religious contradictions.

Now there is a struggle between two opposites, democratic and anti-democratic (state political, legal and anti-state, anti-Ukrainian separatist groups), which is waging an open war against the state.

The ideas of the German thinker Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel on the problems of war and peace, in our time, are extremely relevant, since they concern each of our fellow patriots who root for the independence and security of the state and society. G. Hegel's Philosophy of Law is one of the most famous works in the entire history of legal, political and social thought.

In the Philosophy of Law, the great German thinker pays considerable attention to the problem of the essence and functioning of the state, its domestic and foreign policy, as well as the problems of war and peace. "The state is the reality of the moral idea- morale, as the obvious self, the clear, substance will that thinks and knows itself, does what it knows", – Hegel wrote in Philosophy of Law.

Thinking about the history of war, Hegel concludes that the main reason that gives rise to them is contradiction, contradictions exist both in nature and in society, they are the source of all movement and development. "If there are states objectively there are contradictions between them that lead to conflicts and wars, wars arise where they lie in the nature of things."

Thus, in his work "Philosophy of Law", Hegel gave a deep description of such a social phenomenon as war, revealing the dialectic of the relationship between war and peace with its domestic and foreign policy.

Conclusion. The conceptual position of Hegel's understanding of war and peace is of important theoretical and methodological importance in the modern conditions of Ukraine's development and ensuring its defense capability.

KHODYRIEVA Oksana<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9761-4943>*H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***CREATION OF A COMMUNICATIVE SPACE IN MS TEAMS
FOR EFFECTIVE ONLINE LEARNING**

Aim. Distance learning involves several types of interactions between the student and the teacher with different goals (operational information; notification of new material; clarifying questions; comments on completed work, etc.). Therefore, it is important to create such a communication structure that would be flexible and multifaceted (Khomik et al., 2022; Ivankova, & Ryzhov, 2020).

Two main tasks that must be solved by communication systems are next: 1. Establishing primary communication between students and teachers. 2. Creation of space for the organization of distance learning.

Results. Taking into account the rapid development of various services, the appearance and involvement of new applications for the implementation of functions in IOS, Microsoft developed the MS Teams service, which includes social network functions with the possibility of adding new services, including Microsoft cloud applications. The basic structure of MS Teams is a team. For shared access of team members to information resources, it is suggested to use OneDrive services, MS SharePoint web services, which provide an opportunity to place educational and methodical e-content online. For the organization of distance learning in the online mode of video lectures and practical classes, it is suggested to use video communication services – Teams and Stream, in offline mode - chat or e-mail services – MS Outlook; to implement the independent work of students with the possibility of remote monitoring of tasks in the workbook, effectively use the ClassNotebook service; student knowledge control functions are implemented with the help of Assignments or MS Forms services; the function of managing the academic group takes place using the Calendar and Planner services.

Conclusion. Analyzing the properties and functions of MS Teams, it can be argued that this service provides an educator with the opportunity to create and manage a specialized “social network” on the basis of which a personal learning environment or a group environment can be built as subsystems of the pedagogical system. Using MS Teams, the teacher receives a flexible tool for forming an educational environment for various organizational forms of education (lecture, seminar, practical session, independent work, etc.) for each educational group.

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EXERCISES FOR TEACHING ENGLISH

Aim. There are many topics in English for elementary school children. Children are engaged in phonetics, grammar and vocabulary learning. They learn to speak and write monologues and dialogues. Many new words are also learned. I would like to show some exercises for teaching various topics for elementary school children.

Results. To learn the topic 'Animals' you can use the following exercise "Find an animal". Give children sentences about animals and animal pictures. Children should connect the sentences and the animal. With this exercise, we will test the knowledge of animal names and the ability to read.

To learn the topic 'Professions', I offer the exercise "Choose the correct option". Children are invited to choose a profession from the list and say how and why it is important. With this exercise, we develop the ability to express thoughts in English and check to what extent children have learned the names of professions.

To learn the topic 'Clothes', I offer "Find and Tell" exercise. Children are given a task, for example, find the boy in the picture and tell what he is wearing today.

Thanks to this exercise, we will learn the names of clothes and develop monologue speech.

To master the topic 'Health and disease', I offer the exercise "Set the match". We give the children the proverb beginning about health in one column, and another part of the proverb in the second column. Children have to read and guess how to match them correctly. This exercise can be performed both in a group and individually. This exercise helps to learn new words related to the topic of health and the ability to think logically.

To master the topic 'Theme of shopping', I suggest using the following exercise "Complete the dialogue". Children are given a table of words that should be filled in the gaps in the dialogue. Reading the dialogue about shopping, children fill in the required words into the gaps from the table. After that they complete the dialogue, they can play it in pairs.

Conclusion. All these exercises help to get knowledge about different topics and improve the ability to act out dialogues, read, speak. So, we can see that English is interesting and not boring.

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THE CONCEPT OF “ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETENCE”

Purpose. Environmental competence is specified in the State Standard of Primary School (2018) and is part of the key competences. It involves awareness of the basics of ecological nature management, compliance with the rules of environmental behaviour, economical use of natural resources with an understanding of the importance of nature conservation for sustainable development of society.

The purpose of natural education is the formation of competencies in the field of natural sciences, engineering and technology, environmental and other key competencies by mastering knowledge, skills and methods of development, developing skills that ensure successful interaction with nature, forming the basis of scientific worldview, critical thinking, responsible, safe and environmental behaviour of students in the world based on awareness of the principles of sustainable development.

Results. Environmental competence is manifested in the systematic decision-making to take into account the environmental consequences of their own activities, which has a certain impact on the environment. The basis of environmental competence is environmental knowledge, experience of practical activities in the environment. Acquired environmental knowledge is the personal property; it is formed under the influence of environmental information.

Ecological competence is awareness of the ecological state of our nature, the state. V. Guz considers ecological competence as the ability to “see”, formulate and solve an ecological problem in a specific educational or practical life situation. V. Danilenkova understands the ecological competence as “a predetermined requirement for environmental training”. In his research, A. Ryabov interprets environmental competence as “conscious ability and readiness for productive environmental activities aimed at improving the environment in the process of diagnosing, solving and preventing environmental problems”.

And environmental competence in his understanding is “a requirement for educational training in the field of environmental activities in connection with the growing human impact on the optimal flow of natural processes aimed at identifying, solving and preventing environmental problems”. Issues such as environmental culture, which is directly related to environmental competence, are also considered. Ecological culture is a direction of human activity and thinking, on which the natural existence of modern civilization and its sustainable development significantly depend.

Conclusions. The problem of environmental education and upbringing in Ukraine is extremely relevant and is of great importance for the present and the future. Therefore, it is necessary to combine efforts with the experience of educational institutions in solving problems of environmental education and upbringing in the country.

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HOW TO ORGANIZE THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN WARTIME

War is an extremely difficult time for everyone, and children suffer the most from it. In these circumstances, the school can become a kind of center that will unite students and teachers from the community, as well as children and teachers who have been forced to leave their homes. In many regions, this has already happened and schools have become centres for humanitarian assistance to internally displaced persons, which also accept internally displaced children.

Resuming remote school work in schools where the situation allows will be an important contribution to community life.

Tips for resuming the educational process in schools:

1) When resuming distance learning, the director should examine the capacity of the institution. It is important to support the teachers of your school, to study the situation in the team, the psychological readiness of teachers to work with children. Supporting teachers in this situation, helping them cope with stress is an important part of the principal's job.

2) Teachers who have been forcibly relocated from the war zone may also be involved in the educational process in the schools of the communities to which they have temporarily relocated. This can be both working with community children and giving these teachers the opportunity to use the school premises to work online with their students.

3) In times of war, it is important to adapt the educational process so that learning does not overload children and teachers. Homework in wartime will be inappropriate.

4) First of all, we should give preference to subjects, integrated courses that have relevant content in wartime content, as well as adapt the program of subjects, choosing topics that are interesting and useful to children today.

5) It is important to involve a school psychologist in the educational process.

6) The school, as a centre that today unites children and teachers from different regions, should create opportunities for students to communicate, in particular by organizing group work, volunteer projects, etc.

However, the role of the school during the war is much greater than education. Communicating with children will help them to distract themselves from tragic events, and will enable migrant children to adapt more easily to new living conditions, to join the community, to communicate.

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ONLINE HIGHER EDUCATION IN UKRAINE IN WARTIME

The war in Ukraine in 2022 has changed everything. And the higher education too. After the first shock from the Russian troop attack on February 24, 2022, air bombing and shelling, the higher education was frozen, so-called 'holidays' were announced. From April 1, 2022, teaching and learning at universities started again. Of course, it was online. The **purpose** is to show the resilience of online higher education in Ukraine in wartime.

Results. The first week of teaching, starting April 1, was the most difficult. Students and teachers were depressed, upset, somebody had a post-traumatic syndrome. However, online communication in classrooms became a kind of rehabilitation. Students shared their feelings, spoke about their emotional conditions, fears, anxieties, thoughts. And they felt better. Teachers tried to support the students, talk to them, ask them about their feelings and emotions. After the first week of learning students began to smile, joke, study the learning material, and do the home task. The students confessed that learning was the way out, the turn from heavy thoughts about the war.

So, the online learning started. Some students who had poor Internet got and sent the tasks individually via email. Teachers offered various activities of online learning. Undoubtedly, it is online education that ensured the continuity in wartime, "strengthen academic continuity in case of disaster". The Russian-Ukrainian war in 2022 is not even a disaster, it is planned murders and destructions by Russian troops. This is the human death, the destruction of university buildings, faculties, departments.

Undoubtedly, the main advantage of online education has been providing all students with online teaching nevertheless of their location or life circumstances. The majority of students and teachers talked about it. However, both students and teachers at the end of the semester highlighted that they already missed face-to-face communication and learning. Though everyone understands it is not possible while the Russian-Ukrainian war is going on. In my opinion, difficult times testify that in education not only knowledge or competences are important, but also social empathy, emotional intelligence, and supportive communication.

Conclusions. In order to have long-life education, the online learning will be continued. Online learning has gained some experience and advantages for almost three years (during two years the pandemic and over six months of the war). And, nevertheless of the war, education is going and will be going, because it is impossible to win educated, smart, intelligent people. The education light will conquer darkness. Glory to Ukraine!

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**INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS IN IVAN FRANKO'S DRAMATURGY
(on the example of the play «Stolen Happiness»)**

Purpose: to analyze the innovative solutions in I. Franko's dramaturgy, in particular in the play «Stolen Happiness».

Results: The drama «Stolen Happiness» is considered the most significant work of I. Franko and it belongs to the top works of Ukrainian classical drama. In the play, the author touched upon the topical ethical, moral and spiritual problems of the time, focusing the viewer's attention on the issues of the interaction of individual personal freedom and patriarchal morality, the power of a man over a man, a man over a woman, right and duty, breach of oath and treason, honour and human dignity.

In the play, the author raised topical ethical and moral-spiritual problems of the time, focusing the viewer's attention on problems of the interaction of individual personal freedom and patriarchal morality, the power of a man over a man, a man over a woman, rights and obligations, violation of an oath and treason of honour and human dignity, in general, the fate of women in an inhumane society.

One of the distinguishing features of «Stolen Happiness» is the overemphasis of the drama from the outside in, the shift of the dramatic plot towards psychologies, which, in turn, testifies to innovative searches in the drama of the 20th century.

The concept of Anna's image in I. Franko's «Stolen Happiness» was new in Ukrainian drama. In his opinion, women are characterized by the authenticity of human experiences, spiritual rebellion against hypocrisy, lack of freedom, the desire for happiness, and willpower. Her image is coloured with compassion, and humanistic pathos, which asserts the right of every person to be free. Anna's worldview is determined by cord centrism: she lives according to the call of her heart, realizing herself as a person, and building her hierarchy of life values.

The author, refuting Jean-Jacques Rousseau's socio-cultural concept of «femininity» and «masculinity», forms a new matrix of gender identification. Frank's heroines violate the canon of the dominant tradition, which, according to the philosopher N. Chukhym, has been unchanged for many centuries and positioned a woman as a being who should only, please and obey (a man in particular and society in general). Franko's models the paradigm of an alternative heroine – this is a woman who makes adjustments to the classic course of events. Alternative heroines can realize themselves even in conditions of social scepticism, and if they do not find a way to act within the framework of the «social norm», then they create their own, which are not always accepted within the framework of accepted laws and regulations.

Conclusions: In this context, the writer proved to be an innovator, because before him in the 19th century, no one had gone beyond the traditional and positive interpretation of the image of a beach girl. Ivan Franko's critical position regarding the «cult of protectionism» shows that he questioned «established truths» and was not inclined to construct stereotypical models of gender identity.

KRAVTSOVA Mariia*H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***DISTANCE LEARNING FOR 1-GRADES LIKE A REAL CHALLENGE**

“Is it distance learning? Children cannot study in such way!”. It’s widespread parents’ point of view in Ukraine. Even ten or even five years ago, no one could have imagined that studying with the help of a computer, mobile phones and other gadgets, sitting at home on the sofa in pajamas would become a reality. The **purpose is** to show the challenge of distance learning for 1-grades.

Results. For the first time distance learning was provided according to the law №1115 of Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine in 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic has forced teachers, students and their parents to adapt to a new form of educational process despite it was stressful and difficult for all participants.

In 2022 the organization of educational process is a meaningful issue because of the Russian invasion of Ukraine. All participants of studying must be in safety, have psychological support and ability for learning and teaching. Taking these requirements into account the distance learning is a real solution. Realization of this idea for the 1-st grades is the biggest challenge. It’s difficult to teach them reading, counting and writing not only because of lack of such experience with children who only start studying at school but also most of them are scared, far away from their homes and not all of them have resources for learning and own workplace. What can be done in this situation?

Let us consider the definition and main directions for solving these problems. The Cambridge dictionary says that it is a way of studying in which you do not attend a school, college, or university, but study from where you live, usually being taught and given work to do over the Internet.

Different forms of virtual education have emerged in the past. The most common form is called Massive Open Online Courses or MOOCs. Another method which is similar to asynchronous lessons was called correspondence education. Isaac Pitman, who is considered to be the pioneer of it, introduced this way of studying in England in 1840. In modern world teachers can use different resources for their students such as online books, interactive worksheets, videos and even games for involving children in this process.

If we consider planning online lessons for the first grades, we need to remember about their motivation to study, choose interesting resources, be ready to support them mentally and understand their lack of communication in society and their shyness during the lessons.

According to the educational program students have to learn the next themes: “Numbers and actions with them. Value”, “Geometric figures”, “Expressions, equality, inequality”, “Work with data”, “Mathematics tasks and researches” on the Math lessons. For developing these skills such aspects are important: quality, visualization, involvement, interesting resources for learning.

Teachers can use storytelling, special Internet platforms for primary school and visual online demonstration, real-time interaction between teachers and students. It helps to improve imagination remember and understand new material.

It can be **concluded** that teachers’ hard-working help 1-st grades to adapt to the studying process and get necessary skills during the Russian invasion of Ukraine.

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DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS AT IT LESSONS

Internet brings us a lot of information, every year it passes approximately eighteen and a half exabytes of data. We also can find there whatever we want, but in this case, we face up with the problem of the language. The most common language of the Internet is English and modern students of school have to be prepared for the usage of this language in IT environment. So, this abstract is **aimed** to show the problems of English communicative skills development at IT lessons.

Results. As Ukrainian Educational Standard says all the teachers should give basic terminological base of IT in English to make students more competitive in a real life. Here we give several forms of bringing it to lessons. First of all, it is possible to offer such activity as workshops and parts of lesson in English. Teacher offers topics in foreign language with translation of unknown words. This form of work gives a lot of practice in English communication, but, unfortunately, it brings some problems: it is no way to use it for little children, because of limitation of level of their skills in language; students in one class can have different level of knowledge. In our opinion, it is possible to use this form for such topics as “Informational processes and systems” for studying of components of PC and basic concepts of operating systems, “Algorithmicizing and programming” and “Multimedia processing”.

Another kind of form acceptable for achieving our purpose is working on student projects. This activity allows to teach student to find information in another language and process it to complete task. Also, it helps students to try topics which are wider of school course of IT. In addition, this functions as career guidance, and focuses students who are interested in this specialty on the topics and skills needed to succeed and to stay ahead in chosen career. Project work is very useful for school children; however, this collides teacher with limitations of previous form. The best influence on students it will give if we use the form for topics, where students can make something new by themselves.

The third form, which could be offered, is practical lessons where tasks in English can be given. This solves not only the problem of developing technological communicative skills, but also general English ones. Students interact with foreign language materials, and children must remember or find unknown words to complete the task. This type of activity can affect better if teacher answers the students’ questions in foreign language. And the best part of this is the possibility to use such form for each topic.

In **conclusion**, it needs to be said, English communicative skills are much required in modern world, because they give a lot of possibilities in learning and working. Development of technological communicative skills is needed not only for future IT specialists, but for all people, because personal computers took their place in real life and no one can avoid them. Such activities allow to build technological vocabulary and to practice in real usage of it.

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HELPING SERVICES AND APPLICATIONS FOR STUDYING DURING THE WAR

Last years with Corona pandemic and Russian-Ukrainian war have changed the educational system all around the world and especially in Ukraine. Educational institutions had to change classical in-class system to mixing or e-learning. And our researching **aim** is finding services and applications which can help studying during the war in nowadays educational situation.

Results. The most useful service for studying last years is Google services. A lot of educational institutions have applied Google products since the Corona pandemic started. This group of online services is easy, because you need only computer with internet, Google Chrome browser and Google account.

In Ukrainian schools teachers use Google meet for online lessons with video link, where students can ask questions immediately and solve problems together with teacher, teachers use Google Docs for making educational presentations or students can make projects or homework there and teacher can check it online and give some comments.

Google Forms is also a good service for lesson reflection or module test. Teacher can connect with students with Gmail, send something in Google drive or write the homework in Google Keep.

Also useful are playing services, which can be used for primary or middle school students. For example, Kahoot or Learning Apps are frequently used applications by Ukrainian teachers. Because of user-friendly interface making tests became in making interesting games. There are a lot of different variants of games and exercises.

Teachers can also use social media for educational purposes. There are a lot of educational content in Instagram, Pinterest or TikTok. They can make tasks when students have to make some content (video/photo).

To **conclude**, there are a lot of applications which can help in studying process during the war. One group of them can make studying process easier, the second group will interest and motivate students in difficult time.

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FANTASY and FAIRY-TALE: GENRE-STYLISTIC DIFFERENCES

The **purpose** of the paper is to analyse genre-stylistic differences between fantasy and fairy tales, as these two genres have certain general lines.

Results: It can be noticed that in a comparative analysis of genres of fantasy and fairy-tale the first distinguishing feature is the concept of "justice of protagonist". Based on the plot of both fairy-tale and fantasy, the usually fixed fight is kind and wicked which is presented by the fight between the hero and antagonist. In a fairy tale a protagonist comes forward as a transmitter of the best lines, it is on the side of good/of light, that allows him to search for justice. But in fantasy a protagonist not always comes forward on the side of good/of light, however, it interferes with his search for justice. But unlike a fairy-tale hero of fantasy, gaining victory/a justice dies often enough, here and there sacrificing life, for that humanity survived and could happily live farther, for example, in the novel "Ceramic Hearts" by Natalia Matolinets, Jarrak and Kanre helped the country, unriddled the secret of plot and mystic illness, but not able to save themselves from death. And in the trilogy "Varta in the Game" by the same author the main heroine from the beginning is on the "dark side", because she is a dark sorceress, though fights for justice. Interestingly, heroes of fantasy are not especially kind or bad. Everybody has a history, usually long and not simple. For example, dark magicians can rescue the world, as Varta and Zlatan (from the trilogy "Varta in the Game"), and the light magician can mercilessly take revenge on, and kill, proving to be correct the noble origin. A classic reception is the history of the antagonist, when an author shows, as from an ordinary man he became almost a monster.

Classification of heroes of fantasy has the so-called "transmigration man/woman" as a sign type, it is those that got from our world in the world of fantasy or vice versa. Indeed, mostly it touches foreign fantasy, and will remember the history of Piter, Susan, Edmund and Lucy even, that got through a closet in the magic world of Narnia, to save him ("The Chronicles of Narnia" by Clive Staples Lewis).

The next point of difference is the presence of magic. In a fairy-tale appearance of magic objects and sorceries is both for a reader and for a protagonist is something new and unusual. But in fantasy magic is the basic, motive force of the plot, which is perceived as part of the universe, partly explaining him.

Another point of difference is the aim of the creation of works of the marked genres. If a fairy-tale it instructive sense is hidden, then the work genre of fantasy is the interlacing of actual themes not only for a hero but also for a potential reader. Such themes the themes of parents and children, love between people of different layers of society, first love, the question of justice and revenge, the problem of identity of people of different ages, gender equality and others like that.

Conclusions: Thus, to sum up, it can be concluded, that regardless of which genre of the fairy tale can be considered as the basis of works fantasy, the analyzed genre has a range of distinguishing features that are predefined by the fast development of genre and orientation on an adult audience.

LASHKO Yulia

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THE CHILD'S RIGHT TO EDUCATION DURING THE WAR

The abstract **is aimed** to show the child's right to education during the war. With the beginning of the Russian invasion of Ukraine and the full-scale war, the issue of distance learning has become less relevant – our priorities have changed dramatically. The goals of every Ukrainian are: to survive, to transport themselves and their families to a safe place, to help the army and the country.

But it is important to remember that the most effective weapon for Ukraine's victory and reconstruction is education. Anyone, who deprives students of their inalienable rights, will be punished. Therefore, the purpose of work is to look into the legal settlement of children's rights to education during the war.

Results. In times of conflict, all civilians, including children, enjoy equal protection under international humanitarian law. The following are some of the key international legal instruments providing basis for the protection of children in situations of armed conflict: The Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Involvement of Children in armed conflict (2000), the International Labour Office Convention 182 on the Elimination of the Worst Forms of Child Labour (1999), the Geneva Convention (1949), and the Protocols Additional to the Geneva Convention (1977), the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (2002), number of Security Council resolutions adopted between 1999 and 2009.

Despite the existence of numerous international legal norms, the rights of millions of children around the world are still being violated. Therefore, national legislation is an important part of the legal system designed to protect children in conflict zones.

Currently, the Law of Ukraine "On Protection of Childhood" (№ 2402-III) is the basic law of Ukraine, which regulates the situation with children in armed conflicts.

Also in 2019, Ukraine joined the Safe Schools Declaration. The main idea of this document is that a properly organized education system can help protect children and young people from death, injury and exploitation. The provisions of the Declaration have not been implemented in Ukrainian legislation yet, but in August 2021 the Cabinet of Ministers approved an action plan for its implementation. Among the tasks are continuing education, monitoring attacks on educational institutions, protection against attacks and recovery in case of damage.

Conclusions. Thus, huge statistics on the vulnerability of children during armed conflict should force us to defend their rights. Generation of students will rebuild our country and contribute to the bright future of Ukraine, so our main task today is to provide them with a good level of knowledge. Promoting learning in such difficult times brings us closer to the victory, because the most effective weapon against the enemy is educated young people, who know what values and principles they are fighting for.

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THE ENGLISH CLASSES DURING THE WAR: TEACHING ON DISTANCE

February 24th 2022 Russia invaded Ukraine. This event has stirred the entire world, every single Ukrainian has been impacted by it. Many people have become refugees, meanwhile many families are still in danger.

According to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, every child has the right to study. The necessity of teaching children even during the military conflict is the work's relevance. Discussions regarding having English classes with Ukrainian students after the beginning of the war have dominated across the teachers' communities.

The **aim** of the thesis is to analyze lessons of English held by teachers of schools and higher education institutions in times of war, to highlight the distinction between classes taught during peace and war.

Results. Due to the content shared on various websites and social media, teachers meet the next difficulties: technical problems, lack of equipment, poor internet connection, lack of work environment, the need of providing asynchronous educational services, poor children's possibilities to connect to online classes.

Moreover, students meet psychological and physical consequences of the war. Students' short-term memory may be jumbled and confused, which makes it more difficult for a teacher to provide new information.

Based on our observations, students between the age of 7 to 12 appear to be the most vulnerable as they have difficulties with keeping their emotions and understanding the whole situation.

Some of them cry from time to time and parents report that children are stressed, depressed and suffer from anxiety. However, lessons help them to get distracted for the short time, get some stability and feel better.

In **conclusions**, there are a lot of differences between classes held during the war and in peace. Teaching in Ukraine nowadays is stressful, nevertheless education there has some other goals: not only to provide knowledge, but also psychological support. Life is going on and this is, unfortunately, the new reality for all of us.

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DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIA LITERACY IN UKRAINE'S HIGHER EDUCATION: THE EUROPEAN CONTEXT

In the conditions of Russia's unprovoked war against Ukraine, there is a need for people to have critical thinking to consciously respond to the influence of the media, Internet and telecommunications, to distinguish disinformation, to resist manipulation and to manifest themselves in a multicultural society. Therefore, HEIs of Ukraine can supplement the initiatives of state authorities and public organizations with measures that contribute to the involvement of the general public in the EU media space on the ground of strengthening democracy and European values.

The paper **aims** to highlight the main approaches to media literacy in European society based on core documents and the way for disseminating relevant experience on the example of the Jean-Monet project "EU strategies extrapolation for boosting students' media literacy in Ukrainian HE" at Sumy National Agrarian University.

Results. First of all, it should be noted that the European Parliament defined media literacy as "an essential key qualification in the information and communication society", emphasizing that it promotes the political maturity of citizens, underpins a democratic society, gives people a deeper insight into their rights and duties as well as the principles and values of ethical demeanour (*Media literacy in a digital world European Parliament resolution of December 16, 2008*). Besides, the development of media literacy is vital for protecting audiences, ensuring pluralism in the digital environment, as well as for struggling with social threats posed by disinformation (*Council conclusions on media literacy in an ever-changing world, 2020*). *European Digital Rights and Principles (2022)* define 6 basic principles of the future digital society, namely: putting people and their rights at the centre of the digital transformation; supporting solidarity and inclusion; ensuring freedom of choice online; fostering participation in the digital public space; increasing safety, security and empowerment of individuals; promoting the sustainability of the digital future.

Conclusions. So, the project "EU strategies extrapolation for boosting students' media literacy in Ukrainian HE" at SNAU aims to develop knowledge about the main directions of EU policy in the field of media education and the involvement of Ukraine's HEIs in the European discourse on media literacy through enlightening young people about the European media space and counteracting its manipulation, developing approaches, forms, methods, and tools that improve the development of media literacy and critical thinking under the main trends of EU program documents; dissemination of media awareness among citizens under the negative war impact on the example of the experience of EU countries in the context of promoting intercultural communication, supporting European integration and further international cooperation.

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DIGITALIZATION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE EDUCATION SPACE

Qualitative changes in the educational space are impossible without global transformations and digitization – introduction of modern digital technologies. However, often digitization is perceived only from the perspective of a fashionable educational trend, being satisfied with its superficial implementation, – using it with a purpose assessment of students' knowledge or visualization of the educational material of cloud functionality technologies, digital data processing, software.

Digital technologies make life easier, optimizing routine processes, leveling borders in the educational space that goes beyond the borders of one's country and continent. Digitization is a reflection of the modern paradigm of the development of society, when competitiveness and efficiency emerge as vital qualities.

Digitization of the educational process is caused by the need for a broad the introduction of innovative technologies, the emergence of new requirements for specialists, in particular, the formation of key competencies, and the new digital generation (with special socio-psychological characteristics). Thanks thoroughly organized digital environment makes education more accessible and comfortable, which is extremely important in conditions of minimal expenses - temporary, financial and human resources. And for today's youth, it is also commonplace a plane where there are all conditions for development, an opportunity for realization individuality of each person and comfortable implementation of innovations.

Not only the information technologies themselves are important, but also their correct use their selection, combination and management in order to establish an effective work The benefits of the digital transformation of education are obvious. In particular, this ensuring favorable conditions for:

- development of the ability to learn independently, to select the most valuable material for self-development;
- the formation of personal mobility, the ability to quickly adapt to changing conditions, unpredictably and rapidly;
- increasing motivation for self-education and self-development;
- reaching a diverse audience (content becomes personalized),
- ensuring cooperation and integrability;
- Construction of an individual educational trajectory;
- study in the most convenient conditions – at a comfortable pace, but with optimal use of the time allocated to certain tasks.

And, most importantly, digitalization provides a transition from "education for all to education for everyone".

Thus, a modern educational space is developing in which all the conditions are met to master basic (over professional) competencies. Digitization involves a fundamentally new educational format an environment based on digital technologies that provide convenient and available services and platforms to increase competitiveness, more effective interaction of all participants in the educational process, promotion its transparency, increasing the role of intellectual property, development digital skills.

So, thanks to digitalization, the educational process becomes more personalized, accessible and flexible. This, in turn, provides comfortable conditions for self-study, effective development and career growth. Today digitization appears as a key factor in improving the education system. Apart from it has a direct impact on the effectiveness of the educational process chain of indirect benefits, in particular, optimal use of time for more effective formation of key competencies.

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FULL-TIME AND DISTANCE LEARNING AT THE UNIVERSITY OF LAW

The paper **aims** to highlight full-time and distance learning at the university of law. Let us decide which format is better for studying law. In order to choose the best format for studying law, students need to understand the pluses and minuses of both formats. Students of law university studied full-time and distance in 2021-2022.

Results. There is a vast difference between these formats. It cannot be considered that learning online is much better than learning offline. If we compare learning outcomes in these two types, the effectiveness of learning in the classroom can be seen. The reason is that the main advantage of full-time studying is feeling of responsibility for students' results so students must learn all of their home tasks with high quality.

Moreover, offline studying requires discipline so all main time is spent to prepare for classes. Also, when students go to the university, they can discuss their own mistakes with teachers and get tips on how to work.

In addition, students' learning becomes more fascinating when they meet friends who support them and can share their thoughts, it helps students feel comfortable in the learning process. On top of that, students of law university have practice in the law profession where they improve their skills

However, the main disadvantage of offline learning is the lack of time for rest. When students study in another city they have a lot of responsibilities and tasks besides studying. Additionally, they cannot spend time with their families.

As for online learning, the pluses of distance learning are that students have more free time and their studying is simpler. They can attend classes wherever they are and teachers are more loyal if students cannot join the class. They can send their homework to the tutor later. Furthermore, students can spend more time with their families.

Speaking about the minuses of distance learning, many students are not disciplined and begin to be inactive, because they focus on other things far from learning, through its simplified form. What is more, students at the law university do not have practice in their profession, so it affects their future qualifications.

Conclusions. As a result, in our opinion, full-time learning is more effective than distance because students are focused only on learning, do not have time to be distracted, and improve their skills through practice. However, if the student is diligent, he will not be distracted and will receive quality knowledge even during distance learning.

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PROPAGANDA DURING THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR

The paper **aims** to highlight the points of propaganda during the Russian-Ukrainian war. To begin with, it should be noted that propaganda is one of the main means of political manipulation, especially in our time, when Ukraine and the Russian Federation are at war, it should also be added that propaganda can be divided into both positive and negative. To a greater extent, propaganda is used by politicians to impose destructive ideas aimed at inciting racial or ethnic hatred or military escalation.

Results. Let us try to discuss a few theses of Russian and Ukrainian propaganda, which sparkled with new colors during the war.

1) Nazism and radical nationalism flourish in Ukraine, and the Ukrainian government consists entirely of Nazis and Russophobes. These theses began to appear in the Russian media immediately after the Revolution of Dignity in 2014. For eight years, Russia has been claiming that a Nazi junta of murderers has come to power and poses a threat to the Russian-speaking population of Ukraine. This is just a myth for inciting hatred, how can the Ukrainian government be Nazi if the last two Presidents of Ukraine are Jews, and the dominant party in parliament, the Servant of the People, professes Liberal values that are close to the EU.

2) The rights of the Russian-speaking population are oppressed in Ukraine. It is also a common myth of the Russian propaganda machine. We are talking about the Law of Ukraine "On the Security of the Functioning of Ukrainian Language as a State Language." This law establishes the status of Ukrainian as the state language in our country. And there is no question of prohibiting or defeating the rights of Russian-speaking people.

3) Ukraine for 8 years bombed the Donbass and killed the civilian population of the so-called People's Republics. This statement became significant, since the thesis was the one that the Head of the Russian Federation appealed to announcing a special military operation to protect the population of the Donbass, as well as the denazification and demilitarization of Ukraine. This is a myth, since active hostilities in the territory of ORDLO ceased after the signing of the agreements Minsk-1 and Minsk-2. It is also worth noting that, of course, during the conflict in the Donbass, civilians also died, but this is a pure accident, as during the war there is a chance to get under fire and be killed in street fighting, but the APU did not have a specific goal of killing the civilian population.

Thus, we can **conclude** that propaganda affects the minds of people like poison, turning them into animals, so the population, and especially students, should read more, study history and try to think logically so as not to fall into the networks of propaganda and become a slave going to the right death. As Propaganda Minister Joseph Goebbels said, "The worst enemy of any propaganda is intellectualism."

MARTIROSIAN Ruben, YAKUNIN Anatolii

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TEXTS PROCESSING AS A COMPETENCE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES SPECIALISTS

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is used in most technological solutions as an element of artificial intelligence. The **goal** of this research is to analyze its components, as well as its place and role in the training of specialists of computer technologies.

Results. NLP is one aspect of pattern recognition, which includes the steps of cluster analysis and classification. Cluster analysis consists in dividing a given set of objects into clusters – classes of objects that are similar to each other according to the selected criterion, while each class is significantly different from the others. Clustering of Internet search results is used to “intelligently” group websites and other objects in order to quickly navigate, select a more relevant subset, and improve the user-friendliness of the interface. It used in marketing, distinguishing homogeneous groups of customers, buyers, products and developing appropriate strategies. Classification – assignment of the given object to one of the classes of the available set.

As a separate direction of artificial intelligence and mathematical linguistics, NLP is focused on the problems of computer analysis and synthesis of texts in natural languages. NLP uses machine learning algorithms for recognition of written text and spoken language. This allows the creation of systems such as speech recognition, document summarization, machine translation, spam detection, named entity recognition, predictive text input, etc. NLP algorithms are implemented in word processing software like Microsoft Word to correct spelling and check grammar. The quality of training of a future specialist is a complex of basic, general professional and special competencies aimed at the effectiveness of actions in solving significant professional tasks. Mathematical competence involves the synthesis of acquired knowledge and methods of mathematical activity and a valuable attitude towards them and towards yourself as a carrier of knowledge and experience.

To acquire synthesizing technologies of NLP, their further improvement, creation of new methods and algorithms, and the formation of advanced competencies, a thorough study of this topic by students of higher education institutions of computer majors is necessary. The corresponding educational material is quite complex, so it can be offered to students who already have sufficient training in higher mathematics, probability theory, and algorithm theory. In our opinion, NLP technologies can be studied no earlier than the second year of the bachelor's degree as a component of the variable discipline “Data processing. Machine learning”. The inclusion of this subject in the educational process will strengthen the practical orientation, expand the horizons of opportunities for the development of analytical thinking and creativity, starting from the preliminary analysis and structuring of data, pattern recognition and ending with the creation of artificial intelligence systems.

Conclusions. The offered discipline is multifaceted and can be taught over several semesters and will be useful for many future professionals.

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WHAT PROBLEMS STUDENTS OF CHERNIVTSY NATIONAL UNIVERSITY FACE IN DISTANCE LEARNING

All educational institutions in UA have been working online for 2 years already. Some participants of the educational process (students and teachers), as well as parents have always criticized the quality of knowledge that was received as a result of studying remotely via Internet using modern technology.

The war conditions which Ukraine was forced into, provided the grounds for understanding that online education will be here with us for years to come (especially in the Southern and Eastern parts of our country). There is an urgent **aim** and need now to develop the ways and methods to overcome and eliminate the problems faced by students studying online.

The empirical research "The teacher viewed by the eyes of the students" was conducted by the sociological laboratory of the university with the help of online questionnaire in April 2022. The answers of the students from 2 structural subdivisions of Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University (Faculty of Foreign Languages and the Institute of Physics and Technology and Computer Science (IFTKN) have been analysed.

The hypothesis of the research was the assumption that the means of communication and difficulties faced by students of these 2 faculties may differ significantly. This research gave an amazing opportunity to compare the peculiarities of using different educational platforms at the faculties.

According to the received **results**, the lecturers use a wide range of means of communication. The most actively used platforms are Google Meet, Moodle and Zoom. The comparison of students' answers showed that lecturers of the Faculty of Foreign Languages use Zoom more often (36,8%) whereas the lecturers of IFTKN almost 100 % use Google Meet (97%).

It can also be concluded that at the faculty of foreign languages more than a half of the lecturers prefer to place the homework and methodological courses at the Google Classroom (32,3%) while there are significantly fewer sympathizers of Google Classroom among IFTKN staff (7,2%).

It can be assumed that this choice is caused by the peculiarities of the study methods of different educational disciplines. In particular, Zoom allows to create the rooms for working in small groups that are vital for learning foreign languages. Instead, great advantage of Google Meet platforms is the ability to hold multiple conferences and to maintain high quality of picture and sound at the same time. It is important to ensure the stable connection among video conference participants.

Conclusions. Thus, we could prove the absence of significant differences in means of communication and difficulties faced by students during distance learning at the above-mentioned faculties. The advantages that these platforms offer are crucial to remember when choosing the technics and methods for the teaching process.

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THE PROBLEMS OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN UKRAINE DURING THE WAR

The evolution of the education system of any country depends significantly on socio-economic and demographic factors, which in turn are formed under the influence of socio-political situation in the country. It should be noted that education is considered the foundation of society, which will help improve the economic situation, social prosperity and political stability. It can help one's individual to avoid from poverty, build up harmony and democracy society, to give power for them to voice out.

It follows that **objective** to identify problems of the educational system during the war and find possible ways to solve them. Thus, the vile enemy is destroying not only houses, hospitals, bridges and churches, but also the future, because it deprives some of the opportunity to learn. That is why the continuation of the educational process is becoming a front and an important mission for educators. In addition to the usual lessons, just finding children with friends and peers and even virtual communication will give them an understanding that in their lives there is room for something permanent and familiar. Unfortunately, a number of problems arise during the resumption of the educational process.

Results. Firstly, the destruction of educational buildings as a result of enemy strikes leads to the loss of the developed base of materials during distance learning. An equally serious problem is the insufficient number of educators who have been evacuated. There is also a change of teachers, as a result of which students have to adapt to new people.

Secondly, one of the main problems is the lack of ability to connect to online classes on time due to problems with technology. To solve this problem, you can use a video of the lesson, which students will be able to use at any time. I also think it would be appropriate to draw up a program of training and tasks that would be disseminated.

No less important is the lack of motivation in connection with the psychological state. In situations of danger and stress, adults are a support for children, their emotional state – a landmark, an indicator of safety. A teacher can do a lot to reassure students, divert their attention, give them a sense of security, and reduce tension and stress. To correct this situation, you can spend with children exercises and tasks for psychological relief, to introduce techniques for regulating the emotional state, to communicate with children in messengers.

In **conclusion**, education is a basic element of development of any modern society, because there are no educated people makes the country's progress impossible. Certainly, an important function of education is the education of values, behavior, attitudes, reactions, and inherent in responsible citizens. But despite any obstacles, it is important to remember that reading books, solving problems, mastering skills – these are small steps towards a successful and happy future of our country.

NEVESELA Natalia*Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Ukraine***DEATH, LIFE AND WAR**

The **goal** of this research is to analyze concepts of death, life and war. Death is yet to become a chauvinist. It still cannot differ the color of our bodies, creed or what we have been doing for years. But human brain likes to judge and decide one's fate and lifetime. It is considered no one has a right to do that, but sometimes men choose to pretend like they do, maybe even have a strong belief in that.

Results. Today we notice how easy decisions like those can be made, how quickly life can be destroyed, when military starts bombing a city in the morning. That is the new reality of the Eastern European country. Ukrainians are no longer let plan their life in five years, they can only count seconds between "ex-brothers" fires.

Let us consider about what is going on during the war in everyone's mind. Phycologists distinguish three types of behavior that does not always depend on age: children, adolescent and adult`s behavior. People who have each of the type either ignore the problem or blame others for it or try to solve it in accordance. Looking at the lifestyles of citizens from different regions of Ukraine some strange things can be noticed. Some citizens are trying to move on that comparing to Mariupol looks surrealistic, not because they do not want to believe the evidence, facts, which they see, sounds they hear. Person feels this way because since his birth he knew about previous warships and previous generations told him the evil (embodied in Hitler) had been destroyed in bunker April 30, 1945. Since the beginning of this war people believe in two things: the first is evil always loses and the second is that the price of fighting is catastrophic.

Starting with the first second of the special operation Ukrainians may have two thoughts: they are in Remark`s book and their life is on indefinite pause. Nowadays writers desire to write books about our strict war and our "ex-brother", who appeared to be an occupant. Victims of the war believe, that there will be a new Miracle on the Vistula.

There is an interesting, but rather cynic photo of American soldiers made during WWI, where they smile and hold skulls (*See fig.*). The publisher tells that all of them arrived at the battle field in the end of the devil`s campaign, and if they were there earlier some of them could be the "decoration" for this photo. The tragedy is more about time, than the place. So, no one is able to guarantee the war will end in Ukraine or it will be somewhere else soon.

Conclusion. When the war starts, people may start believing in weapon's shape and sound of shooting more than in Bible. Not because they lost hope, but for the reason they believe in their hearing and counting seconds between fires, that usually have frequency. Siren becomes a kid's lullaby and the increasing number of dead aggressor's soldiers makes people happy. However, this must not exist in the world, but this is Ukraine's reality.

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DIGITAL STORIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING: A REVIEW

The **aim** of this research is to analyze digital stories in foreign language learning.

Results. Storytelling has been present in human history as a manner of transmitting information, ideas and culture and as a process of meaning construction (RAZMI, POURALI & NOZAD, 2014). In the past few years, the way stories have been told has been modified by the advances of technology and the increasing presence of digital resources in contemporary societies. Within this novel context, Digital Stories (DSs) emerge through the creation of the Center for Digital Storytelling in 1998 (e.g., LAMBERT, 2007), initially with social aims and the promotion of diversity (TUMOLO, 2015).

Digital Stories since then have spread themselves around the globe, reaching the field of education. In the foreign language (FL) teaching context, DSs have been investigated due to their potential of assisting students in the development of FL skills and vocabulary learning, together with communicative, creative and digital skills and all of that in an integrated manner (NISHIOKA, 2016; TREVISOL, 2019). Taking that into consideration, the present study, of an exploratory and bibliographic nature, aimed to investigate studies which have used DSs for the teaching and learning of FLs in Brazil and abroad. For that, a systematic review was carried out on the platform Portal de Periódicos da CAPES from 2012 to 2022.

The key terms used were: “Digital Storytelling”, “digital storytelling” OR “digital stories”, and “histórias digitais”. From a total of 117 articles, six studies were selected for the analysis. In general, results have shown that the use of digital storytelling could be a promising possibility to teach a FL in the classroom considering the short period of class time (in some contexts), and the fact that this tool could be effective to foster not only language development but also technological skills in a multimodal way.

Conclusions. The low number of works found may be due to the fact that the search was carried out only in the CAPES Periodicals Portal. Therefore, more studies (or reviews) need to be conducted so we can better understand the potentials of using digital stories for learning languages.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE WAR ON THE TEACHING AND LEARNING

The educational process underwent changes with the beginning of the war in Ukraine. The educational process can take place in the following forms: stationary, online or mixed. This gives an advantage to immigrants not to change the place of study. The Ministry of Education allowed the students to continue their studies in the places where they moved due to the war.

Aim. To analyze the impact of the war on pedagogical and educational processes in natural and mathematical disciplines.

Results. Using pedagogical autonomy, each teacher can conduct a «revision» of the curriculum and identify topics that are easily learned by students and those that will require additional effort. The practical part of the educational programs (practical, etc.) can be divided into two parts: 1) virtual (having the appropriate content, the teacher can conduct online classes with students or give them as independent work at home); 2) home (in this case, you can use improvised materials, it is important to create clear algorithms with mandatory instructions for students).

In addition to knowledge, support and contact with a teacher is also needed. This is now more necessary than ever, because in a state of anxiety, the brain does not learn new knowledge. This was the main reason for considering effective methods of conducting online classes to improve the efficiency of learning natural and mathematical subjects. First, count all the stages of training. The mind map of distance learning, the choice of platform, the schedule of live broadcasts, the format of submitting work – these are not just elements, but a system that works well if thought out in advance. If there are students from other regions who have just joined the study group, then special attention should be paid to them. Second, add the «win-win» element. Emphasis should be placed on difficult-to-understand topics of mathematical and natural disciplines. The teacher must develop special striking moments that students would pay attention to and have the most effective result. These can be exercises that students perform in real time, oral answers or short answers in the chat. Thirdly, it is necessary to ensure the balance of the online lesson. Due to the daily stress of war, it is recommended to focus on addressing the needs of students. Fourth, homework. It depends a lot on the teacher and the region. Determine the appropriateness and volume of homework individually, taking into account the psycho-emotional state of students.

Conclusion. In this difficult time, students need accompaniment and support. The main tool for distracting students from the flow of information about the war and panicked moods is «immersion» in learning using immersive technologies. Active and interactive learning methods are a priority during education.

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THE USE OF AMERICAN ENGLISH IN THE WORLD

The **aim** of the work is to state a place of American English in the world and to define its main features.

The English language is spoken in a number of different countries. The USA is one of them and probably it is one the most popular countries in the world with its culture and identity. Also, this country has strong political and economical influence on the great part of the world.

American English is the set of varieties of the English language native to the United States.

The exploration of British people for the American continent and later its colonization brought English to the modern territory of the United States.

Results. The English language that developed in the British Isles and American English, which separated and developed independently on the American continent, over time have acquired differences and began to exist as two major dialects of English.

Today, the main significant difference between British and American English is spelling. The British retain the spelling of words borrowed from French and German, while the Americans base the spelling on how these words sound when pronounced: defence (BrE), defense (AmE); centre (BrE), center (AmE).

Also, there are words which have the same spelling and pronunciation but the meaning is different. For instance, a trolley (BrE) is a shopping cart, a trolley (AmE) is a kind of electric transport; a solicitor (BrE) is a door-to-door salesperson, a solicitor (AmE) a term which refers to some kind of lawyers. But also, some of the same subjects have absolutely different spelling and pronunciation. For example, the coat which protects a person from rain is mackintosh in the UK, while in the USA it is a raincoat.

The difference is also noticeable in pronunciation, grammar, punctuation, idioms and wording of dates and numbers. However, the grammar differs not in structure, but in its use in daily life. For example, in the United States, the Present Perfect is almost never used. But London has always been and remains the center of English culture. Washington, New York City and other centers that have political and informational influence in the United States recognize this, and therefore adhere to the standards of British English, although they have differences. Due to the huge influence of American culture in the media space, the American version of English is more widespread and familiar.

Conclusion. To sum up, it is quite justified to note that American English is a recognized variant of English, not a separate language. Also, it can be learned separately like one of the variants of the English language. Due to the huge influence of American culture in the media space, American English is more widespread and familiar.

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IMPORTANCE OF TRAINING PUBLIC SPEECHES ON SCIENTIFIC TOPICS IN ENGLISH

The **aim** is to review the importance of the process of forming the ability of higher education students to prepare an English-language public speech on a scientific topic (and the formation of relevant competencies).

Results. The modern education in Ukraine is characterized by the modernization of the education system, which is aimed at the formation of optimal ways of improving foreign language learning, in particular, the formation of foreign language competence for professional and scientific activities.

At present, this process is closely related to high-quality opportunities for graduates to integrate into the international scientific community. In this direction, special attention should be paid to academic communication in the form of writing scientific research (articles, theses, reports, etc.) taking into account international scientific traditions and oral presentation of scientific achievements in the form of reports, oral public speeches, discussions, etc. All this is currently extremely relevant and puts the task of formation and development of students' foreign language academic skills in the field of foreign language education.

It should be noted that analyzing several English-language oral public reports of Ukrainian-speaking students, it was established that students face some difficulties when preparing oral presentations, including subjectivity or lack of references to authoritative sources, subjective argumentation of their own opinions, chaotic, lack of logic (which also contradicts the canons of scientific discourse, in particular, the English-speaking one). All this makes it difficult for listeners to perceive the main idea, which is the basis of a public speech/report.

Based on the experience of working with students, it can be argued that the most effective method is a two-stage work on the formation of the ability to speak in front of an audience with a scientific speech or report on a professional topic. Therefore, in the first stage, special attention should be paid to familiarization with the structure of modern public speeches (with widespread and simple structures). The second stage should be primarily focused on practising the skill of constructing oral public speeches on scientific topics and consolidating the knowledge acquired in the learning process.

Conclusions. Therefore, today, the development of foreign language competence for communication in the scientific field will enable students to carry out effective cross-cultural professional-oriented communication – to present the results of their scientific achievements in the international arena; organize the interaction with representatives of other countries and speakers of different cultures, taking into account modern directions of the scientific outlook, professional characteristics, national characteristics, international norms and ideas; to choose appropriate norms of behaviour based on relevant knowledge, and most importantly, to fully realize one's own scientific potential in the international scientific arena, raising the level of the state in the world.

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BELIEFS OF BRAZILIAN ENGLISH SCHOOLS: ANALYZING SCHOOLS' ADVERTISEMENT FOLDERS

The English language in Brazil is formally taught in different contexts, such as elementary and secondary schools, universities and private English schools (Marques, 2014). Among those, only the latter does not undergo governmental control through official teaching documents, which makes it difficult to study the teaching and learning processes offered by these institutions (Ferreira & Mozzillo, 2020). Moreover, there is a high increase in these teaching private contexts all over Brazil in the last decades.

The **aim** of the paper is to analyze schools' advertisement folders.

Results. A common phenomenon in private English schools is the use of advertisement folders in the media to sell their courses. In such materials, we find, through images and texts, a lot of information about English language learning and teaching, which usually contribute to the beliefs people in general have regarding English language learning and teaching. In this study, we understand beliefs as a cognitive and social concept, which is born from our experiences and problems, interaction with the context, and from our ability to reflect and think about everything around us (Barcelos, 2004).

The main issue is that some of the beliefs in the folders are not in line with the theories and studies of the language learning and teaching fields. Considering such a problem, the study described in this abstract aimed at investigating the beliefs related to language learning and teaching presented in the advertisement folders of Brazilian private English schools, so that we can understand what pieces of information are disseminated to the Brazilian public in general. To achieve such an objective, we collected and analyzed 45 advertisements through the Google Image platform, focusing on the recognition of the beliefs presented in them.

We identified 9 beliefs related to English language learning and teaching in the collected material, being the most frequent ones (i) learning English can be fast and easy and (ii) school teaching methodologies are responsible for English learning, occurring 12 and 14 times, respectively. Such beliefs do not meet the phenomena of learning and teaching, which involve a variety of processes and factors.

Conclusions. We understand that the information presented in the advertisement folders makes use of short sentences and catchphrases, not opening space for theoretical comprehension of the selling product. Nevertheless, beliefs such as those are not consistent with the discussion in the field of language learning and teaching, creating little dialogue between academia and society.

SHYSHKOVA Kateryna*H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***THE IMAGE OF THE MOTHER IN THE POETICAL
HERITAGE OF BORYS OLIINYK**

Purpose: The image of a mother-woman is one of the key elements in the work of many Ukrainian writers, who drew inspiration from their childhood memories, about their homeland and mother, because her face is the first thing a child sees after birth. The image of a mother – a sensible, kind, and at the same time strict housewife – is vividly depicted in Ukrainian literature. This image reached the pinnacle of artistic skill in the poetic works not only of the classical period of Ukrainian literature (the work by T. Shevchenko, I. Franko, Lesia Ukrainka, etc.), but also of the writers of the sixties (L. Kostenko, V. Symonenko, I. Drach, etc.). Borys Oliinyk also touched upon this topic in his creative heritage.

Results: Comparing the work by Borys Oliinyk with the poetic work of I. Drach and V. Symonenko, we can identify common features in the depiction of the mother's image: 1) the historical matriarchal nature of the Ukrainian family; 2) the glorification of the image of the mother as a holy martyr in connection with the loss of a significant number of men during the Second World War; 3) the desire of the sixties to restore the ethnogenetic memory of humanity, to establish the principles of humanistic content, to give them national significance.

In the poetic work of Borys Oliinyk, the archetype of the mother is embodied in the following images:

- the image of the suffering mother-earth, in which suffering is correlated with the decline of the plant world and the environment (“And everything was ... never”);
- the image of the suffering Mother-Ukraine, which is inextricably linked with the political oppression of the people (“Trubyt Trubizh”);
- the image of Mother Earth, which is closely related to populism, mythology, and appeal to historical memory (“Grey Swallow”);
- the image of a protective mother, with the help of which the hatred of the enemy in the souls and the nourishing feeling of human mutual assistance, moral purity, and unsullied conscience are revealed (“Trubyt Trubizh”);
- the image of a housewife mother, which is conditioned by the support of her kind for further existence (“In Defense of Bread”);
- the image of a mother-keeper, in which the mother is equated with saints due to her moral purity, the feat she accomplished after the war – she raised a child worthy of her parents herself (“In the Mirror of Words”);
- the image of the Mother-Beauty, which combines the understanding of the mother as a part of the universe and admiration for her inner beauty, high morality, and wisdom (“Song about the Mother”).

Conclusions: In the work by Borys Oliinyk, the image of a woman is endowed with special, individual features, among which it is worth noting the parable character of the story, “dialogicity”, cosmism, inner optimism, intuitive worldview, highlighting eternal themes and civic position with the help of the image of the mother, the attitude towards the mother as a Saint.

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PROBLEMS IN EDUCATION DURING THE WAR IN UKRAINE

Russian attack has dramatically slowed the ability of war-torn our country to certain reach. These challenges are enormous—in answer to the question, “How can country affected by war arrive at objectives?” In order to improve the planning of educational assistance in conditions of war it is necessary to take a view on some of the major factors that will shape educational development over the next decade.

The **aim** of the article is to clarify the main problems in education during the war in Ukraine, to offer useful advice for the successful organization of the educational process. In my opinion, the solution of education issues during the war is extremely important, because quality education is a strong foundation of the state economy.

Results. During the period of war, all infrastructures endure damage as a result of bombing, fires and combat. Educational establishments are no exception. Both schools and universities and other institutions. That is why one of the main problems is the proper organization of distance learning. It represents one of the main problems that the education system has to deal in a war context, alongside its own welfare and protection.

Also, the lack of educational staff increases the difficulty of responding to the educational needs of children and even reduces the possibility of access to education. Indeed, many future teachers have lost the opportunity to receive higher education and the right to study. Many employees lost their jobs and property and were forced to evacuate to a safer place. Undoubtedly, children often do not have teachers, the latter have fled to safer places; timetables are reduced or interrupted. Besides, there is a problem of moral exhaustion of students and lack of opportunities to combine attending university classes and personal work.

Another of the main consequences which derive from war are the psychological and mental disorders that lots of children and students suffer from during and after the war. Today participants of the educational process suffer from at least one form of trauma, such as distraction, emotional instability, bad sleeping, depression, irritability, nervousness, ability to concentrate, and others.

Conclusions. So, how to influence the improvement of the educational process during the war in Ukraine? I am convinced that solving educational problems during the war is possible. The family exerts a positive influence in terms of the psychological and social support with which they provide the child affected by armed conflicts. But furthermore, the family also has an influence on the decisions of children and consequently on their education. From one perspective, there is a positive influence, since in Ukraine education is something which is valued and respected, a factor which encourages children to study. Accordingly, you need to constantly communicate with parents. University teachers need to maintain friendly relations with students. That is why education therefore plays a very important role when the moment comes to help children and students reintegrate into the social environment. Everything will be Ukraine!

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INVESTIGATING EFL LEARNERS' PERCEPTIONS OF A DIGITAL STORYTELLING TASK: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY IN BRAZIL

The **aim** of the article is to clarify investigating EFL learners' perceptions of a digital storytelling task. Considering the importance of unveiling the potentials of adequately integrating digital technology through tasks in the foreign language (FL) learning classroom, this study aimed to investigate learners' perceptions of digital story construction in terms of technology use, foreign language learning and (prospective) teaching, among other aspects.

Results. Digital stories are understood as multimodal creations in the form of a short video which integrate voiceover narration, imagery, background music, as well as other elements, and which also incorporate different (language) skills in its construction (TREVISOL, 2019). In this study, participants were fourteen FL learners from an English teaching program at a public university in Bahia (Brazil). They were all enrolled in the English course at an intermediate level. The task cycle for the creation of the digital story – which was publically shared with the group at the end of the experiment – was conducted in a genuine (intact) classroom during a three-week period. Qualitative data were collected through several questionnaires – a profile, a during-task and a post-task perception questionnaire – all administered online in learners' first language (Portuguese).

Data from questionnaires were assessed in a subjective and exploratory manner. Overall, results suggest that creating a digital story in a FL may assist learners in fostering target language production, leading to noticing the gaps and critically reflecting about one's performance, especially in terms of speaking, considering the need of reviewing one's speech several times during the recording of the voiceover narration. In addition, learners perceived digital storytelling as a stimulating, thought-provoking and challenging task and were aware of the opportunities it gave them to effectively use (and practice) the FL through different modes of communication, as well as to reflect about their current FL competence and the linguistic areas in need of adjustment (i.e., gaps in speech).

Conclusions. Learners were able to develop autonomy and learn new digital skills (i.e., manipulating the video-editing program) so as to develop the task, in an independent and satisfactory manner. Hence, experimenting with such authentic multimodal creations like digital stories may be seen as a productive road to be taken in the attempt to adapt technology-mediated tasks into real and heterogeneous pedagogical spaces for the enhancement of FL development.

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A SAFE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AS A COMPONENT OF EUROPEAN VALUES

It is a matter of common knowledge that the world outlook of the European Union is based on six core values that every Ukrainian currently shares. These values unite us with Europeans more than even laws or intergovernmental agreements. Nowadays, the common educational policy is also at the forefront: from developing and implementing an internal safe educational space to the safety of education and culture of international importance. The paper **aims** to draw society's attention to the problems of a safe educational environment; spread awareness of the importance of security as an essential European value among higher education stakeholders and the Ukrainian public as a whole.

Results. It is worth pointing out that the modern research community of every knowledge area (particularly specialists in philosophical, economic and technical sciences, as well as law) focuses on studying such phenomenon as “safety”. Also, linguistics provides us with a sufficient number of dictionary entries explaining the concept of “safety”.

The fact of great importance is that the six core values of the EU are enshrined in Art. 2 of the Treaty on the European Union, based on respect for human dignity and rights, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and so on. The goals of the EU include the protection of peace and well-being of citizens, as well as freedom, safety and the rule of law without internal borders. Whereas freedom is the person's ability to make choices and decisions that affect his or her life or the life of a society, the right to safety is an integral part of freedom. Therefore, freedom is not just a free expression of one's opinion or protection from unfounded detention. It also includes the protection of personal data, a safe ecological and educational environment, reliable international educational programs (the right to study) and freedom of movement.

Conclusions. So, as mentioned above, the concept of “safety” is integral to European values. Moreover, it is necessary to emphasize that the main ideas and tasks of modern education, supported and distributed by the EU, are the ones aimed at ensuring the rights, freedoms and interests of higher education applicants, presented in the concept of creating a safe educational environment. The deeper insights have been gauged on the direction of education in Ukraine: an educational institution is not only a place where students are taught but, first of all, a space for their full cognitive and physical development, a centre established for successful and creative learners. It is worth concluding that higher education providers and all stakeholders should initiate providing their learners with a safe educational environment, introducing a safe education system and gaining effective tools for this activity.

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PSYCHODRAMA APPLICATIONS IN WAR

The **aim** of the study is to organize remote psychodrama with people fleeing the war. This study was designed as a basic qualitative research method. Eight young people who migrated from Syria to Turkey participated in the research. Eight sessions were held, each lasting ninety minutes. All the sessions were held with the internet Zoom meeting program. Drama techniques such as mirror, role switching, and matching were used in the sessions. In addition, remote warm-up games were used in the sessions. Maxqda social science computer program was used to analyze the qualitative data.

Results. Psychodrama is a method invented by Jacob Levy Moreno. Basically, psychodrama uses the therapeutic power of theatre. Psyche means "essence" (or "spirit"), it means "of" and drama means "event". As a result, it can be taken literally as "soul drama" or more simply and truly as "what happens to a person in the surrounding environment". It is a sociometric (interpersonal) strategy that requires a relationship between the self and the mundane world of people, objects, and animals.

Psychodrama can be used to explore a topic, celebrate something, or embark on a journey of discovery. It is not about finding a solution to a problem or discovering the truth. Psychodrama is an interaction that helps alleviate the pain of war. Mankind has been fighting since the day it appeared on the stage of history. People fight each other for food, land, and prestige.

However, there is no winner in the war, and it leaves behind death, injury, loss, and destruction. War is an armed conflict between nations, governments, society, or paramilitary organizations such as mercenaries, rebels, and militias. Extreme violence, aggression, damage, and death are common features and are carried out by conventional or special military forces. War refers to behaviours and characteristics common to different types of warfare or wars in general.

Total war is defined as a conflict that is not limited to legitimate military objectives and can result in significant civilian and non-combatant suffering and casualties. Some war researchers believe that war is a universal and ancestral component of human nature, while others believe that war is the result of specific socio-cultural, economic, or ecological conditions.

Conclusions. The categories of education, marriage, work, fear, pain, violence, loss, trust, peace, and happiness were created under three themes: pre-war, during the war and after the war. Codes such as school, work, salary, raid, injury, kidnapping, imprisonment, escape, settlement, aid were made.

Psychodrama provides an environment that gives both psychological and physical confidence to its participants. A bullet or bomb, from where it was fired, can mean the loss of human life at any time. Those who endure the negative pain of war can express themselves through psychodrama.

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QUEST TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VISUALIZATION PROCESS AT THE UKRAINIAN LITERATURE LESSONS IN GENERAL EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

Aim. At the current stage, quest technologies are actively used in the educational process. A quest is a variant of the game, in which players must follow step-by-step instructions, solve pre-prepared individual or collective tasks, and, in the end, receive a reward – a treasure, an artifact, or knowledge. In addition, a quest is considered as a literary plot in which the hero must pass certain tests, complete tasks, overcome obstacles and reach the goal, an example of which can be artistic texts from ancient literature (myths about Hercules, the Argonauts, Perseus, etc.) and up to modernity (fantasy literature, novels, for example, “Quest” by B. Akunin, S. Derkach, “Bread Quest” (“Khibnyi kvest”) by O. Fomin, etc.)

Results. As a pedagogical technology, the quest is a well-thought-out model of joint pedagogical activity in designing, organizing, and conducting the educational process with clearly defined goals, and diagnosis of current and final results, which has certain stages with distinct procedural characteristics.

The following types of quests can be used at the lessons of Ukrainian literature in General Educational Establishments:

– *video quests* – interactive video (for example, a final lesson based on Taras Shevchenko creative heritage in the form of a video quest (the 9th grade));

– *escape room* – a game that consists in finding an exit from a certain room or several rooms by completing tasks and receiving hints (in the 5th-8th grades while learning adventure literature or works about numerous adventures and children's tricks);

– the *quest in reality* is related to the immersion of players in the storyline, which is based on the artistic text being studied (a famous movie, a computer game). Among its varieties, researchers single out action quests (active actions of players aimed at achieving a goal) and horror quests (provide participants with thrills);

– *quest-performance* (while learning detective and fantasy literature, for example, when studying “The Devil’s Soul, or the Enchanted Treasure” by V. Arieniev, etc. (in the 8th grade));

– *single tasks* of a search nature, which require the participants to activate intellectual, critical, and creative thinking (literary puzzles, puzzles, crosswords, etc.).

Conclusions. Today, quest technologies are an innovative educational activity aimed simultaneously at the development of students' intellectual, creative, and critical abilities and skills. The quest is characterized by special principles of its creation, a successful combination of play and learning, contributing to the growth of interest in the educational topic and education results consolidation. It takes different forms at the lesson – from setting a problematic task and how to solve it to designing a whole lesson in the form of a quest with changing locations and the ability to move.

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CHALLENGES AND REALITY OF WARTIME EDUCATION

The **aim** of the study is to show challenges and reality of wartime education. Today, the events caused by the armed aggression of the Russian Federation and the declaration of martial law in Ukraine, have become a rather serious test for all participants in the educational process. It affected the usual way of life of everyone in our country. War and education are incompatible concepts, but today it is a reality.

Results. During the war, higher educational institution becomes a center that enables students to receive not only knowledge, but also psychological support, not to lose a sense of belonging to the community, to believe in their own strength. In the conditions of martial law, it is especially important to ensure the rights of students and give them the opportunity to continue their education. Since the beginning of the war, distance learning has become the main option for access to knowledge, and universities are trying to adapt their work to new conditions during the pandemic. Now, when Ukrainians are forced to study online because of the war, a logical question arises: what are the main advantages and disadvantages of distance learning in Ukraine, and how can the lessons learned during the pandemic help in wartime?

It is now much easier for teachers to apply new teaching methods and make their subjects more interesting. For example, a strong point of this training format is the prospect of inviting guest lecturers, as well as online professional development. Mainly, teachers gained these opportunities thanks to the integration of new technological resources. Furthermore, during the war, many educational institutions were given access to online platforms with educational courses, which greatly simplifies the work of the teacher and increases the probability that the student will master the material at any convenient time.

In addition to the obvious benefits for students and teachers of online education, such as saving time spent traveling from home to university and increasing free time for personal matters, an absolute advantage is that it has become easier for students to combine work and study and in this is a way to acquire practical skills while acquiring theoretical knowledge at the university.

According to the national survey results, one of the biggest challenges for teachers is that students are less actively involved in the educational process. And if earlier silence in the classroom meant only that the students did not prepare, or, on the contrary, were thinking about the teacher's task, now it can also mean the complete absence of the student from the lesson (although nominally he/she is at an online conference).

Conclusion. Nowadays, more than ever, students need support, confidence and faith. Therefore, teaching students under martial law is a challenge and at the same time an important work of teachers in the overall contribution to the victory in Ukraine!

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REMOTE ENGLISH LEARNING DURING THE WAR

The **aim** of the study is to show English learning during the war. The difficulty of teaching English in 2022 due to the martial law in Ukraine is that distance learning has fallen like snow on its head for most educational institutions.

Results. It is one thing when an educational institution was initially focused on the development of distance learning as a direction, and another thing when only external circumstances pushed for distance learning - an unplanned war. Alas, most schools, colleges, and universities turned out to be simply not ready for innovations. And the elementary “maybe” became the algorithm for solving the problem: “Let's install Zoom, and come what may: we will try to “reconstruct” classical classes in the classroom.” But for such a discipline as English, it turned out to be a failure from the very beginning. As for learning English, I will say this, war is not a reason to stop learning, no matter how painful and scary it may be. In the early days, I didn't want to think about any kind of training at all, it simply didn't fit into my head. I am a student, and because of Russian aggression, I lost what seemed to be the simplest thing – free access to study.

However, my university has gathered all its strength and resumed the educational process, and now we are working and uploading all completed tasks to the Moodle platform. It is much easier to sit English classes in the classroom than in front of a monitor at home. Yes, and homework has increased as never before. Well, on a positive note, I certainly cannot but say about such an advantage of distance learning as a couple in bed. You can wake up five minutes before the bet, connect, turn off the camera and listen to the teacher, but I don't think that something good will come of it. For this reason, it is becoming more and more important to know different languages, especially English.

One billion people speak English today. This is about 20% of the world's population. For 400 million people, English is their mother tongue. For the remaining 600 million people, it is either a second language or a foreign language.

Conclusion. Knowing English today is absolutely necessary for every educated person, for every good specialist. Learning a language is not easy. This is a long and slow process that takes a lot of time and patience. But it is necessary.

Especially for me, learning English, in my opinion, is not easy in the form of online learning, but I understand in my subconscious that at the moment the choice is not great, so distance learning is the only way not to forget the completed program. I am very grateful to my English teacher. She is in the same difficult conditions as all of us, but she does not forget us and continues to give us knowledge. By completing the tasks that she gives to consolidate knowledge, they help to get distracted for a moment and forget, that it's not quiet at all outside the window ...And despite the fact that now there is a difficulty in studying, we still should not give up and continue to study something new for ourselves.

YANCHUK Maria*H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***TEACHING AND LEARNING DURING WAR AND PEACE IN UKRAINE**

The **aim** of the paper is to analyze the quality of teaching and learning in war and peace in various educational institutions in Ukraine; describe the differences between teaching in war and peace; find out how students and teachers adapt to new educational conditions in Ukraine.

Results. today in Ukraine, teaching and learning are quite difficult processes, because when there is a war in the country, students and teachers do not think about education at all. Despite of this people continue to try to live a normal life and do their job. But the difference between life during peace and war is big. After analyzing the factors that affect the quality of education, it is obvious that it is better in peacetime than it is now. Even during the coronavirus pandemic, the quality of distance learning became worse, because students learned to facilitate their work and became lazier.

But then there were such rules as mandatory attendance in class, the reason for not attending had to be significant, mandatory homework, etc. The rules have been changed now. Presence at the lesson depends on the conditions in your place of stay. Students' homework and sending teachers materials for self-study are associated with a good or poor connection, too. The quality of teaching and learning depends on the quality of the Internet and the availability of electricity. Do not forget about security. In the area where hostilities take place they do not even talk about education, people think only about how to save their own lives.

Despite all these obstacles people are adapting to new conditions. At first, both teachers and students were confused, and because of this, learning might slow down a little. Then they got used to the new daily routine and even new housing began to improve this process. Everyone has his own pace. Someone adapts faster, someone slower. Some are even distracted from the present by learning.

Also, when people need to leave home to save their life, they usually take everything they need and forget about the materials for teaching and learning. This is a problem, too. Because of this, students and teachers have to get used to working with a limited number of materials.

Conclusions. Learning and teaching in times of war and peace are completely different things. Students and teachers need to get used to the changes that have taken place because of the war. The quality of education is significantly reduced because not everyone has good conditions for this.

Learning is slower than in peacetime and is not always accessible to teachers and students due to the conditions of the area where they are staying. But despite all the obstacles, the learning process continues and everyone is trying to take on responsibilities.

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THE CONCEPT OF DEVELOPING FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF FUTURE MEDICAL PROFESSIONALS

The **aim** of the article is to clarify the concept of training future specialists in foreign language communicative competence based on the definition of system-forming methodological and theoretical foundations of the concept "Concept of training foreign language communicative competence in the future specialists".

Results. Based on the study and research of the works of scientists B. Klimenko, E. Passov, M. Stepko, L. Tovazhnyansky, S. Tsokolov, L. L'Abate, M. Cusinato, E. Maino, W. Colesso, C. Scilletta, M. Halliday, A. McIntosh, M. Strevens, R. Abbuhl, A. Mackey, S. Krashen, H. Stern and others, as well as the language learning model developed by B. Spolsky, it was revealed that the basic fundamentals of the concept for the formation of foreign language communication skills of students: **1)** theories of education and training, methodological and didactic principles and approaches; **2)** psychological theories of learning and personality development; **3)** psycholinguistic theories of language teaching; **4)** sociolinguistic teachings about the use of languages; **5)** linguistic theories and approaches; **6)** philosophical theories of the development, interdependence and interdependence of the phenomena of objective reality.

In the light of a humanistic approach to organizing educational activities of students, the program for learning a foreign language should draw attention to the personality of the student, focus on the role of a foreign language as a means of communication in dialogue cultures. The humanistic approach to learning emphasizes the importance of each individual participant in the educational process. Studying a foreign language should be aimed at developing students' understanding of universal values, at the formation of their communication skills at an intercultural level. The student must have appropriate knowledge of the language system and have developed communicative, especially pragmatic, sociocultural and intercultural skills.

The organization of foreign language training of future specialists in medical specialties, taking into account solid conceptual provisions that synthesize the analyzed theories, doctrines, principles and approaches, will ensure the effectiveness of the process of forming the foreign language communicative competence of future specialists.

Conclusion. Optimization of the educational process of the foreign language communicative competence of students of medical faculties of higher education institutions of Ukraine depends on the provision of pedagogical conditions for the integrated systematic application of the basic provisions of the concept of forming a foreign language professional competence of future specialists medical specialties, in particular, the possibilities of implementing innovative pedagogical technologies and methods.

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"WHAT IS THE VALUE OF KNOWLEDGE OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN WAR PERIOD?"

The **purpose** of the article: to thoroughly analyze and investigate the relevance of using a foreign language, to reveal the advantages (reasons) of mastering this language, possible evidence of language learning in the everyday life of an individual in war period.

Presentation of the main material (results) of the study. Everyone knows that nowadays learning a foreign language is not only useful, but also popular. Knowledge of the English language can always come in handy in your life. Those who speak this language will have a successful future and good career growth.

So, I suggest reviewing a number of reasons or advantages of the importance and significance of mastering the English language:

- Ability to become better than others. After all, if we take two people as an example, one of them has a foreign language and the other does not, then accordingly, the first of them will feel confident and more advanced, which corresponds to the image of a modern successful personality, and the other will feel depressed due to a low-level education.

- Ability to read and listen to audiobooks, watch movies and listen to music in the original. Here you can develop even more intellectually, just "make yourself smart".

- Opportunity to travel to the dream cities of the world. In order to feel confident among the local population, knowledge of the language there is necessary. Learning foreign languages is an opportunity to travel around the world like a civilized person.

- The opportunity to expand one's own circle of communication. If only for the sake of being able to communicate freely and maintain relations with people from other countries, it makes sense to learn foreign languages.

- Opportunity to get a better paying job. Now, almost every financially attractive job requires English. If you know the language, you will be able to get a job in an international company, where the salary level is higher, besides you will have additional benefits (for example, a gym, insurance, reimbursement of travel expenses, medical care, etc.).

Conclusions. So, having listed a number of main reasons for the motivation of learning a foreign language, we can say that this is only the beginning, because nowadays English is needed everywhere. English is the native language of 500 million people in 12 countries of the world. Today, approximately 1.5 billion people speak English. 80% of information stored on computers around the world is in English.

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TEACHING AND LEARNING IN WARTIME

The **purpose** of the article is to show challenges in wartime. In the spring semester of 2022, a sudden war stopped students from attending school. The only solution to not missing school in times of war is to "stop classes and stop learning". So, what do students learn when they switch to online learning at home? How do they learn? What do teachers teach online? How do teachers teach? **Results.** These are some of the questions that will be discussed.

1. The need to continue teaching during the war. What do teachers actually teach? That is, what do students want to learn? I have wondered: why are students called 'students'? In the past, I always thought that 'student' meant to learn about life. But I have come to understand that students are called 'students' because life is education. If we start from this point of view, the question of "what to teach" is not difficult to solve. They should not be numb and indifferent in the face of war, because students are not outsiders, and war threatens them too. The war itself is therefore a "textbook", a "textbook" of life experiences.

In this "textbook", students learn to respect all life, learn to build ideals and beliefs, learn about self-protection, learn scientific and cultural skills, learn good moral character, learn to observe public order, learn to maintain an optimistic attitude, learn to feel family and friendship... ..all of which are compulsory lessons for students. In such "teaching materials", students will learn about the causes of war and therefore understand the relationship between the state and the country; they will learn about the army and the defence forces; they will realise how important peace is to our lives and thus establish a correct outlook on life and values They will learn how important it is for the country to be strong in the face of war; they will have more freedom in terms of time to study at home, they will learn to manage themselves, develop reading habits or interests; they will gradually learn to be alone and think without going out, without partners; they will have a new understanding of family and family love by being with their families all the time... ..this is perhaps what "life is education" means!

When I was clear about what I wanted to teach, I suddenly realised that teaching online would not affect the effectiveness of "teaching moral values" in any way. There are so many heroes in this war, and their stories make us clearer about what we need to "build morals" and "build people up", if we use the "teaching material" of the war, we believe that in the near future, we will see a number of patriotic and ambitious builders and successors.

2. How do teachers carry out their teaching activities?

How do teachers teach? Or how do they guide students to learn? Online teaching is a need during the war, for each front-line teachers is a new topic, but also an unprecedented challenge. Teachers need to organise the content and routine of their students' home learning, and pay attention to the state of learning in each subject and the emotional state of their students. At the same time, they must communicate with students, listen to their opinions and suggestions, and try to meet their needs and help them with their online learning difficulties. To do this, teachers need to plan and implement, pay attention to the results, take stock of problems, and listen to suggestions and adjustments.

It is important to note that as a teacher, you must educate yourself before you educate others. The students are required to be consistent in class and offline, online and offline, so they must do it first. After all, it is better to teach by example than by word. Therefore, during the online teaching period, as a teacher, I have to be more attentive and considerate to each and every student than ever before. In terms of teaching methods, I try to tailor my teaching to the students' needs; in terms of teaching style, I try to be different from each other. I will use my own personality to infect students and win them over, consciously set a good example, and be a person that students love, so as to achieve the best effect of "being close to their teachers and believing in their ways". During this time, the provision of quality online teaching and learning services will help to put "moral education" into practice. At the same time, it reduces students' anxiety and makes their online learning happy and meaningful.

3. Learning can be done even during war. War can block the road to school, but it cannot stop us from growing up. The growth of students is not delayed and neither is the growth of teachers. **Conclusion.** Seeing the teachers' dedication to their work and the students' positive feedback on their studies has been a rewarding experience for them and each other during this time online.

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LINGUISTIC ASPECT OF COMMUNICATIVE TACTICS AND STRATEGIES OF EXPRESSING CRITICISM IN ENGLISH

Purpose. Analyze some communicative tactics and strategies for expressing criticism in English, as well as the components of successful intercultural communication.

Results. Criticism is perceived differently in each culture, because it is influenced by the variety of traditions inherent in each country and the peculiarities of translating one language into another. Therefore, the expression of criticism in English should be considered through the prism of communicative tactics and strategies that make it better to understand what exactly the speaker wants to convey.

In order to express criticism in the English language, different tactics and strategies can be used, which differ somewhat in terms of argumentation and the way of conveying an opinion. Let's consider some of them: authority tactics, which are implemented due to attracting the opinions and positions of other authorities – opinion leaders, celebrities, quotes from authoritative sources. Subjectivity tactics are characterized by the fact that the speaker emphasizes his correct position and role in communication. Criticism tactics are characterized by a high degree of argumentativeness, namely, providing a negative assessment of actions, deeds, etc. Descriptive tactics, which in fact only show a list of certain events and phenomena without analysis and reasoning of the speaker. Regarding strategies, the following should be singled out: the strategy of discrediting, which is characterized by the use of evaluative vocabulary addressed to opponents. The strategy of disagreement consists in denying or criticizing the interlocutor and convincing the interlocutor of his own rightness.

Often, the use of such tactics can cause a conflict, or make a negative first impression on a new acquaintance. Criticisms can be expressed in different ways: weak, moderate and strong. Weak and moderate criticism is mostly used for scientific research, in communication in a more formal style. Strong criticism is often used in relationships with people and often at work or study. Therefore, in order to avoid disputes and a feeling of discomfort during communication, which can easily arise in an intercultural environment, it is worth using mitigation tactics. This tactic serves as an important means of conflict-free, cooperative communication. Mitigation can serve as so-called soft criticism, which is inoffensive but explains the critical remark in detail by expressing empathy, tact, appropriate arguments, etc. It is also worth remembering that language etiquette, despite the presence of common structural elements in many ethnic groups (formulas of greeting, farewell, expressions of sympathy, etc.), has national and cultural specificity. Understanding of this specificity that are planned to be used is a necessary component of successful intercultural communication.

Conclusions. Thus, when expressing criticism in English, it is necessary to take into account the national and cultural specificities and features of each tactic and strategy that is planned to be used. It is worth remembering about mitigation tactics, as such, which is perceived as mild criticism and prevents the emergence of conflicts.

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PROSPECTS OF PEDAGOGICAL PARTNERSHIP IN THE PROCESS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The **purpose** is to show prospects of pedagogical partnership in the process of inclusive education.

Results. According to UNESCO, more than 262 million children and young people are currently out of school, and 6 out of 10 have not acquired basic literacy and numeracy skills after several years of schooling, perpetuating poverty and marginalization. This is not just a marginal question of how some students can be integrated into the mainstream, it mainly focuses on how to globally transform education systems to meet the diversity and needs of students. Inclusive education is when a school educates all children, regardless of background, level of achievement or special educational needs. This means that children with additional learning needs and special educational needs study in a 'mainstream' learning environment rather than in a specialist school.

The main attention in the practice of partnership pedagogy should be paid to attitudes, views and perceptions of teachers of inclusive education in general and special schools. Educational inclusion policies of the EU (e.g. Sweden) include such important values as equality and inclusiveness; however, there is still a tendency to individualize the problems of some students. In the daily practice of inclusion, there is a problem of labeling students without special educational needs when they face organizational or social difficulties. Partnership pedagogy should ensure the solution of individual problems of children with special needs, without focusing on the problems of their development, which requires the use of new teaching methods.

Thus, interprofessional relations at both organizational and interpersonal levels are important for the cooperation of teachers and psychologists. To begin with, interprofessional teams are recognized as the basis for building relationships at the inter-organizational level. In particular, these collectives provide a mechanism for forming an understanding of the role and duties of teachers. However, even with the organizational support of school teachers and frequent meetings, different cultural values and ambiguity regarding professional roles take priority over psychological support. These cultural differences can affect the content, direction and results of the partnership. In practice, there is also a problem of over-discussing methods of supporting teachers instead of providing real support.

Conclusion. Partnership in inclusive education is a style of interaction characterized by voluntary participation. All parties involved in this process have equal status as they work towards a common goal. People who collaborate also share decisions about processes, resources, and accountability for results. It is important to know each other's professional characteristics and competencies for good cooperation, as well as to have an effective communication style (both formal and informal) and to have positive working and personal relationships. As collaboration progresses, new practices develop; while solving different problems together, team members learn and grow as individuals, as professionals and as a team.

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING AUTHENTIC AUDIOVISUAL RESOURCES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES DURING WARTIME

Ukraine is facing one of the biggest challenges of the 21st century. Russian aggression led to one of the fastest and largest movements of children since World War II. UNICEF reports that more than half of Ukrainian children – 4.3 out of 7.5 million – have been forced by war to leave their homes. 659 educational institutions had been damaged by bombing or shelling, and 74 had been destroyed completely.

In this difficult period, the entire educational community is consolidating for the introduction of new teaching methods and their implementation during the war. That is why the search for new methods and forms of work during the war, which would be convenient for ESL learners, became the purpose of our research.

It should be noted that for a long time, many teachers and lecturers used only printed materials as one of the available tools for working in class. In addition, many teachers have difficulties using online platforms, they consider offline learning to be the only effective way of learning. Such work methods may be boring for young learners and do not motivate students to study. In addition, most students don't have the opportunity to be physically present at school.

The great advantage of audiovisual materials is that they are freely accessible and that they are produced first for native speakers. That is why they provide an opportunity to master different accents, deepen socio-cultural skills and increase students' motivation.

The present study aimed to investigate the performance scores on a standardized proficiency test after two months of explicit training on language comprehension strategies. Two groups of learners of an upper intermediate level of Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University (30 students in total) took part in this study. The interviewees were divided into two groups. The experimental group (15 individuals in total) received two months of explicit training based on video and television authentic audiovisual materials. The control group (15 students) worked in the old mode without using authentic audiovisual resources.

We noticed that the used techniques and methods were effective and positive dynamics can be noticed. The efficiency of the students during the lesson increased by 20% in total. We also found that movies and television significantly improve the learning process during wartime:

- they contribute to stimulating interest in learning the language.
- contribute to increasing students' motivation.
- provide the opportunity to acquire socio-cultural competence.

So, the data obtained during the research confirm that effective learning during the war directly depends on the efficient use of video and television by the teacher in class, their correct selection, adaptation, and methods of working with them. The results of the study provide prospects for further research in this direction.

NATURAL & MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES SECTION

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QUESTION OF COMPETENCE IN EDUCATION OF MEDICAL STUDENTS: SHOULD WAR AFFECT THE MAIN AIMS OF MEDICAL EDUCATION?

The war unleashed by Russia against Ukraine on February 24, 2022 has deeply affected many sectors of Ukrainian society, including education. Forced adaptations that have occurred in the process of student learning, in the work plans of teachers, as well as in the work programs of higher educational institutions, all this will have long-term consequences. In particular, military aggression on the part of Russia led to the territorial relocation of teachers. The teachers were required to perform tasks that had never previously been expected to be performed and for which they had not been trained. Some readily completed the task, while others could not or did not want to. What is the basis of this situation, and were all university teachers really competent enough to perform such a difficult task? **The purpose** of our work is to study the qualitative component of digital competences acquired by foreign students of KhNMU at the Department of Medical and Biological Physics and Medical Informatics, using the example of acquiring digital competences while studying the educational component "Medical Informatics".

Results. The study involved 40 full-time students. The survey was conducted directly using the questionnaire, in May 2022. Respondents assessed their skills in the field of competences under study based on their own opinion. The participation of students in the survey was agreed at the beginning of the pedagogical experiment. The reliability of the questionnaire was checked using Alpha Cronbach ($\alpha=0.928$). A survey of students showed that 67% of the information about the subject received from teachers was not clearly communicated to students, and it was difficult for them to systematize them. 20% of the information received was assessed as satisfactory, and only 13% were assessed as sufficient to obtain the necessary competences in the study of this subject. The concept has always left space room for interpretation. Perhaps this is due to the fact that competence is partly context dependent and includes three components, or areas of competence: the classical professional area, defined by the theory of the concept; situational area determined by the context; and the personal domain, which explains the individual differences observed among professionals.

Conclusion. Under normal circumstances, most work in a stable and familiar environment where all standards and expectations are met. However, there is a limit to what can be formally defined as required competence. In this study, we did not focus on these adaptations, but rather on how the war fundamentally affected our thinking and the future competence of medical students.

BROSLAVSKA Halyna<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9839-4604>**FIL Liubov**<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0012-2994>*Municipal Establishment “Kharkiv Humanitarian-Pedagogical Academy” of the Kharkiv Regional Council, Ukraine,***A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND PHYSICS. CONNECTION BETWEEN THEM**

Physics is known as the science of nature. This means that all the processes and phenomena that occur around us are directly related to the above-mentioned educational component. Therefore, the authors of the theses believe that thanks to this, it is necessary to pay more attention to the study of this natural discipline, because the acquired physical knowledge will be able to be used by education seekers in their future practice, in their professional activity, life. The **aim** of these theses is to trace the connection between a foreign language and physics.

Results. In the connection with the fact that military operation continues in Ukraine, which causes devastation, tragedies, and suffering to the civilian population of our country, many Ukrainians were forced (for their own self-preservation, and protection of their families) to leave its borders. These theses deal with the information about education seekers, who temporarily live in the countries that have provided assistance and shelter to our refugees.

Young people who come from Ukraine must attend educational establishments in the country they live in (Germany, France, England, Poland, etc.). Our education seekers have difficulties studying without knowledge of a foreign language in another country. Therefore, today in Ukraine, great attention is paid to the study of many educational components (according to the curriculum of the educational establishment) in an integrated manner, in the combination with a foreign language (for example, English).

In particular, the military situation has led to the understanding of the need to learn a foreign language for young people, because it will allow them to use the acquired knowledge for active communication, receiving and transmitting information to education seekers and the population of other countries.

The authors of these theses, who teach education seekers physics and English, emphasize the importance of studying the above-mentioned discipline together with a foreign (for example, English) language. These educational components have a lot in common, namely:

- in physics, as in a foreign language, you need to study terminology. After all, a person cannot speak another language without knowing its terminology;
- physics has a lot of terms taken from the English language;
- in physics, to describe some phenomenon or process, you need to think clearly and logically, and know formulas; in a foreign language, like physics, almost all grammar is based on formulas.

The combination of teaching education seekers physics with the use of a foreign language in class will contribute to the improvement of the knowledge of the natural educational component and the more perfect study of a foreign language.

Conclusions. It should not be forgotten that before starting subject-language training, teachers of educational components (physics and a foreign language) need to determine the level of the education seekers' knowledge of a foreign language. Only after that, it can be used while studying physics.

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USAGE OF ICT TOOLS FOR INCREASING OF CLEARNESS IN STUDYING OF TRIGONOMETRIC FUNCTIONS IN COURSE OF 10TH GRADE MATHEMATICS

The article considers usage of visualization tools in order to simplify the perception of theoretical material at Mathematics lessons, while studying the topic "Trigonometric functions". Some Examples of partial implementation of using ICT tools are represented. **The purpose** of the article is to review means of visualizing the relationship between changes in the values of variables and coefficients of trigonometric functions, given analytically, and their graphs while studying Mathematics course (the 10th grade).

Results. "Trigonometric functions" is one of the topics studied in the course of Algebra and Beginnings of Analysis in the 10th grade of secondary school. The study of the topic "Trigonometric functions" requires students to have already formed knowledge of trigonometric formulas and the ability to apply them, as well as the development of spatial imagination. In case of insufficient formation of the listed components among students, it is possible to predict their poor assimilation of the topic "Trigonometric functions".

In this case, in order to increase the efficiency of learning the material of the topic "Trigonometric functions", it is advisable to use visualization tools, in particular specialized computer programs that allow you to display graphs of trigonometric functions and establish correspondence between changes in the values of variables and coefficients of trigonometric functions and the changes occurring on the graphs. Among such computer programs, the system of dynamic Geometry "GeoGebra", the graphic calculator "Desmos" can be recommended for use. After that you can proceed to the construction and analysis of graphs of trigonometric functions and their properties.

At the same time, constructing graphs and studying the properties of functions can be carried out in two ways: first, a graph is constructed by points, and then all the properties of the function are studied with the help of graphical interpretation, or the construction of the graph takes place after the study of the function, and students get a visual representation of the properties by analyzing the behavior of functions on unit circle. It is most expedient to use the second approach, as all properties of trigonometric functions are illustrated on both models (on a number circle and a graph).

Such approaches open up the possibility of using ICT tools to display the relationship between the unit circle model and the graph of the trigonometric function, and also contribute to encouraging students to use the graphical method when solving trigonometric equations during further study. Thus, the use of dynamic visual aids will allow to illustrate graphs of trigonometric functions and their elementary transformations, with less time spent than using traditional means of visualizing educational material.

Conclusion. Using the GeoGebra to visualize the relationship between the trigonometric circle model and the graph of the trigonometric function. The considered means of working with the elements of the topic "Trigonometric functions" can be useful when there is a shortage of time to practice the skills and abilities of constructing and transforming graphs of trigonometric functions, in the case of insufficient interest of students in studying the topic, and will also increase the level of students' assimilation of the topic material.

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GAMIFICATION: NEW GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

In modern conditions of rapid development of information technologies, the priority areas of education development are the introduction of innovations; intensive use of electronic resources, creation of an industry of modern teaching aids.

The purpose of the article is to analyze a gamification. One of the promising ways of innovative development of education is the introduction of game technologies and the implementation of game projects in educational activities of all levels.

Results. The main advantage of gamification is its motivational properties. Competitive nature, helps to increase the overall level of quality and speed of work. The practice of using games in education has already proven itself as an effective tool: during learning in the game format, a larger volume of information is absorbed, and it is longer retained in memory (Uvarov, 2018). So, gamification is a tool to facilitate content learning.

Within the context of online learning, gamification creates additional incentives that help students maintain intrinsic motivation. High-quality gamification will allow learning platforms (LMS) using these technologies to gain competitive advantages compared to traditional approaches. In online education, gamification can be used both for the user's mastery of the learning management system and for increasing involvement in the learning process.

Transferring elements of the game to a non-game environment not only improves the motivation to learn for learners, but also opens up new opportunities. One of such innovations is the introduction of gamification elements into the discipline "Systems of technical vision of robots" in the modern educational programs of the department of MEIRES (NURE).

Computer vision is a general set of techniques that enable computers to see. Technical (or machine) vision focuses on applications, mainly industrial, such as autonomous robots and vision inspection and measurement systems. This means that image sensor technologies and control theories are related to video data processing for robot control, and real-time data processing is performed by hardware or software (Savchuk, 2017).

Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics is one of the profile universities of Ukraine, where information technologies and innovations are given the main attention. So, the problem of studying technical vision is in the field of scientific interests of several departments of higher education at once, among them the department of Media Engineering and Information Radioelectronic Systems.

The scientific experience of researchers of the department (MEIRES) found a practical application of technical vision in the detection and classification of UAVs (Kartashov, 2019). Over the past few years, master's theses have been defended on this topic.

But the war has made adjustments to the goals and objectives set by the researchers. Now gamification has been replaced by harsh reality and it turned out that studying the use of technical vision to detect unmanned aerial vehicle is absolutely necessary for the fulfillment of combat tasks of the Armed Forces. So, from the game to reality – we need to improve the system of detection of UAVs by video stream, increase the database of digital images of moving objects.

Conclusion. The work of each of us is subordinated to one goal – victory. Our research turned out to be extremely relevant and important now, because it can save people's lives and bring the day of victory closer.

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USE OF EIDETIC TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

Purpose. The task of modern primary school is to provide high quality education and personal development of each student. It is known that children perceive and remember information through the world of images and associations.

To form students' figurative thinking means to educate the need for knowledge, to enrich children with a system of knowledge, skills and abilities in modern ways of learning about the world around them.

It is important and necessary to help younger students use different ways of memorizing the necessary information, to master those that seem to be the most effective for each child. One of the ways to implement this task is to use the techniques of eidetics.

Results. The term "eidetics" was first coined by German psychologist Eric Jensch in the period from 1920s to 1940s, who proved that figurative thinking is a natural stage in a child's development. Dissemination and deep study of the techniques of eidetics were carried out in the studies of such prominent psychologists as O. Luria, P. Blonsky, L. Vygotsky, I. Matyugin. Today we can talk about the formation of the Ukrainian school of eidetics (O. Dmytrenko, V. Davydenko, I. Kazeichev, V. Primakov, O. Pryshchep, V. Shpakov, etc.), which takes into account the peculiarities of national psychology and mentality. An important distinction of the Ukrainian school of eidetics is its focus on the child's positive perception of the environment.

Eidetic techniques are based on knowledge of the physiology of the human brain: the right hemisphere of the brain is a "figurative" hemisphere that remembers emotions, and the left one is "verbal", intelligent, analytical. Perceiving something, the human brain in the right hemisphere makes an image-model, and in the left picks up the words corresponding to it.

Eidetics uses the features of memory to more vividly capture an object filled with emotional and sensory saturation, so that the object after disappearance in a few minutes can be reproduced in memory. Information that is memorized through association images is stored for a very long time because it is organic and natural. Techniques of eidetics are used in mathematics lessons during the formation of students' ideas about number and digit, the ratio of number and digit, the composition of numbers.

Conclusions. Thus, the use of eidetic techniques in the teaching of mathematics to primary school students lets each student easily and with pleasure acquire knowledge, enjoy the realization of their abilities.

Eidetic techniques teach you to use your memory correctly, to remember and reproduce the necessary information quickly, and this is directly related to the imagination and fantasy of the child which are important components of creative thinking. The student becomes more able to work, learns better, his memory and ability to concentrate increase.

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ANALYSIS OF CURRENT REQUIREMENTS REGARDING THE CONDUCT OF A PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSON IN THE NEW UKRAINIAN SCHOOL

Aim. To study the peculiarities of conducting a physical education lesson according to the modern requirements of the "New Ukrainian School".

Results. In September 2017, the Law "On Education" was adopted, which regulates the principles of the updated education system. The main reforms were implemented and outlined in the concept of the "New Ukrainian School" (NUS), where the main thing is to change the approaches to learning and the content of education. In connection with this reformation, there were changes regarding the conduct of a modern lesson at the NUS. The task of NUS is to educate a patriot of Ukraine, an innovator, a creative and proactive person. In this regard, the requirements for conducting a physical education lesson, for the competences of the teacher and for the students have become very high. The teacher must think creatively and be an innovator to make the physical education lesson interesting and useful. A teacher's creativity is an invaluable work, which he performs while departing from his usual everyday duties. The mastery of a teacher is manifested in his ability to improve teaching and upbringing methods successfully, creative thinking, rational guidance of practical-cognitive activities of students and their intellectual development, application of the latest pedagogical achievements and acquired pedagogical experience. The following technologies are relevant for use in the lesson of physical education of the National Academy of Sciences: project method; information and computer technologies; technologies of special orientation training. Today, a physical education teacher in a secondary education institution faces an important task – to form a healthy, culturally aware, comprehensively developed citizen of our state.

The main goal of the lesson remains the physical development of the individual. For now, we can formulate the main modern requirements for the lesson "Physical Education": 1. Take into account the interests and motives of students when choosing physical exercises; 2. Completion of the main tasks of the lesson (educational, educative, recreational); 3. Ensuring optimization of the educational process; 4. Use of innovative methods of conducting classes; 5. Formation of students' abilities and skills to independently engage in physical exercises; 6. The teacher's use of various forms, means and methods, organizational methods of conducting the lesson; 7. Providing a differentiated approach to the organization of the educational process, taking into account the state of health, motor readiness, gender of the child, as well as the level of physical development. Achieving optimal motor development in each lesson, taking into account the state of health of each student. Evaluation and compilation of standards are now not the main goal and task of students. It is designed so that children are motivated by the result and success of their progress, the desire to learn and exercise at home. In the case of lagging behind peers in the development of physical qualities, the teacher draws up an individual program of physical and recreational classes and monitors their implementation.

Conclusions. Therefore, the new standards of physical culture at school are aimed at the development of the educational process taking into account the needs of each student, for the effective formation of skills and knowledge, interaction with students and parents. Do not limit yourself to just issuing a grade for "evaluating" students. Each student should be an active participant in the educational process, not a passive "recipient" of grades and knowledge.

KONDRATENKO Ann

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THE ROLE OF PROBLEMATIC SITUATIONS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS

The aim is to show the role of problematic situations. Usually, the task is understood as the purpose of the activity, which is given under certain conditions (for example, in a problematic situation), and must be achieved by transforming them according to a certain procedure.

An analysis of existing textbooks suggests that school math is about half the time in math classes in middle school, so «learning by doing» is naturally considered a method of teaching math.

Results. In the educational process in mathematics, tasks perform such important functions as: educational, cognitive, developmental, educative and control (G. Bevez, J. Zhovnir, Z. Slepkan and others). In order to facilitate the introduction (or consolidation) of theoretical positions, basic concepts and facts, problems with didactic functions are used. Tasks with cognitive functions require in-depth mastering of the basic educational material of modern SCM, and tasks with developmental functions involve the development of intuition, spatial, logical thinking, intelligence and more.

At the same time, it should be noted that mathematical problems have an educational impact on students through the plot, the plot of the problem, so the plot of problems changes significantly in different periods of society.

It is known that the development of interest in mathematics is facilitated by solving exciting, interesting ancient problems, as well as problems that precede the study of new material that creates a problem situation. Thus, mathematical problems play an important role in stimulating students' interest in mathematics and in educating students who are interested in mathematics.

Methodically correct organization of problem solving brings up in students such positive personality traits as diligence, attentiveness, concentration, persistence in overcoming difficulties, a sense of duty, responsibility for the quality of mathematical knowledge, etc. At the same time, almost all mathematical problems have the purpose of current control or self-control, which is their control function. In tests, the main purpose of the tasks is the final control of the correctness of the method of teaching and knowledge of certain sections of mathematics students have received.

Conclusion. Thus, mathematical problems are both a subject and a means of learning, as they are aimed at mastering the concepts of mathematics and mathematical methods of cognition of reality, the formation of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, involve the development of mathematical thinking. Problem solving requires students to analyze the situation, identify conditions and conclusions, find analogies, compare and contrast. This process (unless it is a formal repetition of a known algorithm) is always creative and is performed by students themselves with the necessary support from the teacher.

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LEARNING TO SOLVE EQUATIONS AND INEQUALITIES WITH PARAMETERS AT SCHOOL

The abstract **aims** the essence of the problem of preparing high school students to solve problems with parameters, highlights some ways of solving it in the initial process of mathematics in general secondary education institutions.

Results. Most of the students plan to enter one of the higher education institutions after finishing school and study with state funds. There are not enough budget places for everyone and you have to fight, namely to score the maximum number of points on the external independent assessment. For graduates, this is a great stress. The analysis of the official report of the Ukrainian Center for the Evaluation of the Quality of Education on the results of the external examination in 2021 provides an opportunity to testify that for the task with the parameter 90.2% of the participants scored 0 points, and only 0.2% scored the maximum number of points. Therefore, today the problem of increasing the effectiveness of teaching students to solve problems with parameters in the school mathematics course is very relevant.

One of the ways to solve this problem is the introduction of electives, elective courses, and special courses in mathematics into the educational process for students to master the methods of solving equations and inequalities with parameters of various types in order to meet the differentiated needs and requests of students.

That is why the special course "Solving problems with parameters" for 10th graders was introduced into the educational process of the Balakliyivsky lyceum of Kharkiv region.

The main competencies that are formed in the study of the special course are: mathematical (students mastering the methods and techniques of solving equations and inequalities with parameters of various types, forming the skills of competent writing of solving such tasks); etc.

Solving a problem with a parameter means that it is necessary to provide a family of solutions relative to the unknown quantity (unknown quantities) for all possible consideration of constant quantities (parameters) in the answer.

Conclusion. The analysis of literary sources confirms that the general recommendations to students for solving typical tasks with a parameter usually contain the following steps (G. Apostolova, A. Prus, V. Shvets and others):

1. Determine the type of equation, inequality or their system (linear, quadratic, irrational, exponential, logarithmic, trigonometric, etc.).
2. Write the equation (inequality, system) in standard form.
3. Choose, depending on the type, the appropriate solution method and implement an approximate solution plan.
4. Sometimes it is recommended not to solve tasks with parameters, but to investigate them using certain guidelines.

KOVICHYNSKA Kateryna*H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***IMPROVING THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PHYSICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS THROUGH THE USE OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES**

The paper **aims** the essence of the use of interactive learning technology in physics lessons, its place in the educational process, as well as identifying ways to expand students' cognitive abilities and form a deep inner motivation in each student in the use of this learning technology, natural sciences, and school course of physics. The author explains in great detail the term "interactive pedagogy". Interactivity in learning can be explained as the interaction of students, their integration in the mode of conversation, dialogue, joint action. Development of interactive elements training can be found in the works of V. Sukhomlinsky, in the work of teachers – innovators 70- 80's.

Results. It is stressed that in the process of organizing interactive learning to achieve the best results you need to follow the requirements and rules:

- all students in the class should be involved in the work;
- active participation of each student in the work should be encouraged;
- students must develop independently and implement rules of work in small groups;
- there should be no more than 30 students in a group (class), because only in this case productive work is possible;
- students in the class should be prepared to work in small groups.

Therefore, the planning of interactive learning in physics teacher's activities should be conducted in the following two directions. The first involves a series of teacher actions for effective learning, and in particular:

- give tasks to children for preliminary preparation: read, think through, perform independent exercises, preparatory tasks;
- when solving interactive exercises, give students time to think about the content of the task so that they can take it seriously;
- you can use one (max. - two) interactive exercise in one lesson;
- it is very important to conduct a calm in-depth analysis and discuss the results of the interactive exercise;
- conduct a quick survey, independent homework with a variety of topic materials that were not related to interactive tasks.

The second area of the teacher's activity is related to control planning:

- deeply study and think through the material; carefully plan classes;
- motivate students to study the material by selecting the most interesting cases and problems for students;
- announcement of criteria for assessing student performance;
- provide a variety of methods to attract students' attention, set them up for work, maintain discipline.

The **conclusion** dwells upon the expediency of using interactive learning technology in physics lessons. The analysis of interactive learning technology allows us to summarize that this technology helps to expand students' cognitive abilities, and in the formation of deep inner motivation and provides opportunities to transfer knowledge, skills, abilities and ways of working to physics lessons and in the process of daily life of students.

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CYLINDRICAL SURFACES IN APPLIED PROBLEMS OF HIGHER MATHEMATICS

The **aim** is to show cylindrical surfaces in applied problems. The focus of teaching on practical tasks of professional content helps to increase the level of mathematical training of specialists. These problems reveal the essence of theoretical material and methods of operating with the corresponding mathematical objects. Solving applied problems allows for the development of modern mathematical culture: mathematical formulation of a real problem, selection of equivalent mathematical tools and its algorithmic and software implementation, bringing the result to a practically acceptable form with the use of computing tools, subject analysis and recommendations for use. When choosing a number of applied problems, it is necessary to focus on the main mathematical objects and work on them the main questions of the mathematical apparatus.

Results. Cylindrical surfaces and their sweeps are encountered throughout the course of higher mathematics, starting with analytic geometry. Spatial bodies bounded by cylindrical surfaces (tanks, pipes, building structures, etc.) appear in problems of optimizing dimensions using differential calculus, in problems of calculating volume and area by means of integral calculus, in problems of studying their dynamic properties based on differential equations. The work provides an analysis of typical problems where cylindrical surfaces are encountered, and recommendations are given regarding the place and forms of their inclusion in the course of higher mathematics.

The implementation of applied problems improves the educational process due to the following factors: 1) as a rule, these tasks are of a problematic nature, which encourages the expansion and deepening of knowledge and skills, their integration with the material of related and professional disciplines; 2) helps to overcome formalism and formulaicity, since solving most of such problems requires independently adapting existing knowledge to the analysis of specific situations and making a weighted choice of instrumentarium; 3) allows you to focus on analyzing the essence of the problem and finding the appropriate mathematical apparatus, and not on routine calculations, which increases the interest and activity of students; 4) problems with real objects stimulate motivation to study higher mathematics, as they show its practical importance and generality of conclusions; 5) working out applied problems forms in the student valuable mental qualities for the future – systematic, creative thinking, the ability to reasonably choose a solution and optimize it, perseverance, hard work and responsibility.

Conclusion. The implementation of the applied orientation of the study of higher mathematics plays a significant role in the formation of a future specialist, the education of a positive attitude towards the chosen profession, the development of interest and abilities in it. This contributes to the integration of mathematics with related and specialized disciplines, the penetration of modern mathematical tools into the engineering and technical sphere from the first courses of study.

PONOMAROVA Vlada*H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***HISTORICAL MATERIALS AS A MEANS OF
DEVELOPING INTEREST IN LEARNING**

Mathematical foundations of computer science are a component of a modern school course of informatics, the program of which provides for the possibility of studying the corresponding optional module in 10-11 classes of general secondary education institutions (Informatics, n.d.). The content of the optional module includes, in particular, the study of numbers, counting systems and their place in the history of mankind. **The aim** is to show historical materials as a means of developing interest in learning.

According to teachers and methodologists, in this perspective, the use of historical material will allow students to be introduced to the path, logic, interconnection and interpenetration of mathematical and information sciences and is an effective means of motivation to study them (Sira, 2013).

Results. First of all, it seems appropriate to acquaint students with facts from the history of numbers. Number is one of the most important concepts in mathematics, which in many cases can act as a measure of the amount of something. In ancient times, in Slavic languages, the word "number" meant "sign", "symbol", "concept", "idea". The word "number" was understood to mean "mark", "think", as well as "write something down with the help of signs", "do certain actions with signs".

Later, with the spread of arithmetic and exact sciences, numbers began to be understood primarily as signs to indicate certain quantities. In the 19th and 20th centuries, with the development of higher mathematics, the word "number" began to be used more widely again - for the name of signs, designations and concepts that denote not only quantities, the concept of counting was formed (Number, n.d.).

The typology of numbers is of particular interest to informatics. The appearance of new types of numbers and counting is closely related to the development of human society. Yes, regarding natural numbers ("natural") there is a saying that they are created by God, and other numbers are a product of human imagination.

Historically, first the set of natural numbers (along with zero) was extended to the set of non-negative rational numbers, and only then did negative numbers appear. The name of real numbers reflects the idea that it is they that make it possible to describe reality (reality), since rational numbers did not make it possible to solve all the problems that humanity faced. When studying the mathematical foundations of informatics, it is also useful to show students complex numbers, quaternions and octonions as examples of hypercomplex numbers.

As for the history of the methods of writing and marking numbers, here you can offer students as independent work the search for answers to the following specially selected questions: "Who is considered the inventor of signs for marking numbers?", "Where was the method of marking numbers with the help of fingers used and what was its name?" the largest number could be represented by it?", "Which digital signs are considered the oldest?", "What numbers did the Romans call their children?", "Which people first invented signs in the form of pieces of rope to indicate each number?", "How did an ancient record of Arabic numerals with the number they represent", "What is Shunya?", "What is darkness, legion, lord, raven, deck?", "Order the numbers: million, quintillion, septillion, trillion, sextillion, thousand, octillion, unit, billion, quadrillion", "From what word does the name "Calculator" come from and how is it related to numbers and calculations?".

Interesting facts about numbers traditionally arouse considerable interest among students. Examples of these can be found on many educational websites that can be used to learn about the unusual history of mathematics and numbers in lessons on the mathematical foundations of computer science (Olar, Fediv, & Mykytiuk, 2016; Interesting Numbers, n.d.).

Conclusion. Thus, the use of historical material from the mathematical foundations of informatics (about the history and typology of numbers, the history of notation and recording of numbers, interesting facts about numbers) will contribute to the increase of students' interest in science and learning, their understanding of the importance of mastering modern mathematics and informatics as important components of universal human culture .

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POTAPOVA Tetiana*H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***WAYS OF FORMING COMPETENCE IN PHYSICS**

Today there is a rapid development of technology, changing requirements for the education: to prepare secondary school and high school students for modern living conditions on the basis of competency-based approach. Also, the process of teaching physics and the requirements for compulsory learning outcomes should be determined on the basis of a competency-based approach.

The aim is to show the ways of forming competence in physics. Given the extreme importance of the issue of the competence approach, in the process of studying physics, it is advisable to consider the formation of one of the most important competencies is subject (industry) competence.

Results. Subject competence is acquired skills, methods of activity, students' experience gained during training, through the acquisition, formation and application of knowledge that is specific to a particular subject. Subject competence in physics is the ability of students to see and use, to master the conceptual apparatus and basic knowledge of physics, to explain the world of nature, it is the ability to conduct experiments and physical experiment, to solve problems, to suggest new ways of working, to build graphs, models of a physical phenomenon or process, etc.

The formation of subject competence in students in physics lessons can be implemented as follows: conducting non-standard physics lessons, project development, performing various homework assignments, conducting research and experiments, etc. It should be noted that for the effective formation of subject competence of students in physics, it may be useful to use information and communication technologies, modern devices, robotics and more. This can significantly increase the motivation of students, learners' interest to learn and understand in detail a law or phenomenon. Particular attention should be paid to solving competency-oriented problems in physics for the formation of subject competence of students.

The physics curriculum outlines "problem solving" as one of the most important components in the system of teaching physics to students in general secondary education. Within the requirements of the competence approach, the condition of the task should be formed and close to the real living conditions of the individual, to encourage students to apply physical knowledge in life situations.

Conclusion. Thus, when composing or selecting a set of tasks to be solved, the teacher must take into account typical everyday situations, the production plot, the operation of certain devices or equipment, the impact of natural phenomena, and so on. Thus, there are many ways to form the subject competence of students in physics. Their choice depends on the teacher, the level of knowledge of students, the type of lesson and so on. Solving competence-oriented problems is a universal way to establish the level of formation of subject competence in students.

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USING THE OPPORTUNITIES OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN MASTERING MATHEMATICAL COMPETENCE IN SCHOOL

The **aim** is to show the opportunities of social networks. Contemporary education is aimed at forming a comprehensively developed personality capable of self-improvement in the 21st century. It is mathematical education that contributes to the development of logical thinking, memory, attention, imagination, deductive and inductive thinking, forms the ability to analyze, draw analogies, generalize and draw conclusions. Therefore, the formation of mathematical competence of schoolchildren is relevant.

Mathematics is mostly perceived by children as a boring and uninteresting subject. Therefore, teachers at schools are actively searching for effective forms and methods of teaching Mathematics that will arouse interest in this science.

The world of information and communication technologies and the Internet have already become part of everyday life. However, social networks are practically not used in the educational process, so this issue is relevant too.

Results. The analysis of previous studies shows that a lot of attention is paid to the problems of using social networks in the field of education. The possibility of introducing social networks into the educational space attracted the attention of a number of scientists, in particular: Kuchakovska, Nesterenko, Tyshkova, Radchenko.

Today, such social networks and messengers as: Instagram, Tik-Tok, YouTube, Telegram and Facebook are particularly popular among schoolchildren. The use of such social networks in the educational process promotes the exchange of information, increases motivation in educational activities, stimulates the development of creative abilities and cognitive interest.

So, for example, in the Telegram network, the main sources of information are educational information channels and bots, which can be configured in the form of a personal math tutor capable to respond around the clock. There is also an opportunity to run your own blog and create a closed group for communication and exchange of information resources, for example, mathematical curiosities. Yatsyshyn suggests using the Facebook social network for group training; self-education; internal school training (use for the purpose of informing about the functioning of the educational institution and related activities).

Meanwhile, the Tik-Tok platform and YouTube provide video content: by making a video with an interesting presentation about mathematical facts, rules or theorems, you can greatly interest children. The Instagram network can be used to host math quizzes in the format of Stories, which can only be viewed for 24 hours. For example, a competition can serve as a motivation for educational and cognitive activity: whoever passes the quiz faster will receive an additional point. Also, this platform can be used for blogging, information sharing and as a means of communication.

Conclusion. Social networks can significantly increase communication opportunities, interest listeners and promote their more active participation in the educational process. Thus, social networks have a huge potential in forming the cognitive skills of schoolchildren during their mastery of mathematical competence.

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EUCLID'S "ELEMENTS" AS AN OUTSTANDING WORK OF GREEK MATHEMATICS

Aim. In this research the content of the «Euclid's Elements» has been considered, its role in Mathematics, advantages and disadvantages.

Results. Despite the fact that attempts to express important mathematical knowledge as a known whole in a certain order, connection and sequence were already made by many Greek scientists, only Euclid had the opportunity to complete the "Elements". As with the lives of most of the great mathematicians of Ancient Times, not much information has been preserved about the Euclid's life.

It's known that he lived in Alexandria under Ptolemy I (306-283 BC). Proclus said that Ptolemy had asked Euclid if there was a shorter way for understanding geometry than that is in the Elements, to which Euclid replied: "There are no royal roads in geometry".

Although Euclid is the author of a number of works, he entered the history of mathematics first of all as the author of "The elements" (Elementa from Latin), in which he organized all the accumulated, at that time, geometric material in "The elements", where he mostly followed the principles constructions of geometry according to Aristotle.

Euclid's "Elements" are divided into 13 books:

- I-VI – planimetry;
- VII-IX – arithmetic in a geometric presentation;
- X is an exposition of the Eudoxian theory of incompatible segments;
- XI-XIII – stereometry.

"Elements" were noted for their immaculate logic, which is why they belonged to a course of lectures for a higher school, which was aimed at a philosophical nature, and not to school textbooks.

The logical structure of geometry, derived by Euclid, is something extraordinary for his time, but in view of modern mathematics, it contains a number of shortcomings.

1. Basic concepts are not highlighted in the "Elements".
2. There is no clear distinction between postulates and axioms.
3. Some axioms are redundant because they are proved on other postulates and axioms. Also, some postulates contain redundant requirements.

Conclusions. Therefore, Euclid's "Principles" played a huge role in the history of mathematics and the entire world culture and gave a great impetus to the further development of mathematics and its teaching. Until the beginning of the XIX century. Euclid's "Principles" was a seminal work for the study of geometry, a testament to Euclid's genius.

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PROJECT EDUCATIONAL AND COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF SCHOOLCHILDREN IN THE STUDY OF MATHEMATICS

The **aim** is to explain a project educational and cognitive activity. In the process of learning, cognition takes the form of educational and cognitive activity. Learning in the project activity of schoolchildren is especially valuable, because it: first, it is implemented indirectly in the process of mastering the design experience (during the project) under the condition of cooperation, and secondly, it is based on self-regulation by the student of his educational and cognitive activity, when he "teaches himself", and the teacher through the creation of problem situations provides interaction aimed at active, research assimilation of knowledge, skills, their creative mastering during motivated, purposeful problem solving; third, knowledge acquires personal significance for the student, since project activity has a significant impact on the formation of regulatory components of self-consciousness, the creation of mechanisms for regulating personal behavior. Therefore, we agree with the opinion of scientists (V. Deinichenko, N. Matyash), who believe that the very concept of "design" is key for the correct understanding of all components of the project activity of schoolchildren.

Results. Clarification of the essence of such a multidimensional and multifaceted phenomenon as design is facilitated by the analysis of its structure. The analysis of literature sources provides grounds to show that most scientists focus on the problem-activity nature of design, that is, design assumes the presence of a problem that is practical in nature and is solved in the process of organizing various types of activities.

The essence of designing from the point of view of this approach is the gradual awareness of the problem by the individual and the search for ways to solve it, because the problem in ancient Greek ($\pi\rho\acute{o}\beta\lambda\eta\mu\alpha$) is a task that needs to be completed. At the same time, the peculiarity of design is the presence in its structure of thought activity of such a stage as reflection, since the design process involves moving from a problem situation through the correction of one's own actions to further reflection of activity.

The analysis of scientific works on the problem under consideration made it possible to identify the sequence of actions of students in the implementation of project activities: goal setting (determining the goal and significant motives of project participants); forecasting (research of the current situation; identifying the problem; formulating expected results); modeling (a certain option or method of solving the problem; setting tasks; planning activities); effectiveness (identifying risks, potential difficulties; determining resources; implementing the planned plan); assessment (interim assessment; making necessary adjustments; summing up the results, comparing the achieved results with the expected ones); reflection (analysis of one's own activities).

Therefore, the design structure clearly shows purely design (thought activity) and project implementation (transformative activity in the material sphere).

The disclosure of the multidimensional design in the educational activities of schoolchildren is facilitated by the identification of such pertinent concepts (pertinent – appropriate, appropriate), such as: "Project situation", defined as a project activity related to solving problem situations in the design process (N. Matyash); "project task" or "project task", understood as a specific design goal (V. Deinichenko).

The solution to the problem posed in the project task involves describing a certain algorithm of actions that need to be performed to get the planned result, such as: describe the sequence of steps for constructing a polyhedron section with a plane defined in a certain way; the result of the solution is presented in the form of a flowchart.

The key concept in design and its result is "Project", which in a general scientific sense is interpreted as a complex, time-limited activity aimed at achieving certain goals through the implementation of desired changes as a result of this activity, which requires the definition and implementation of certain stages of its implementation.

The analysis of literature sources provides grounds to show that scientists (N. Matyash, N. Pakhomova, O. Pekhota, E. Polat and many others) offer different classifications of educational projects according to certain typological features, but in practice, they most often use mixed types of projects. For example, for 6th grade students, we developed a mixed-type project on the topic "golden proportion", which is research and search in terms of the purpose and nature of the project activity; in terms of content – intersubject; in terms of the number of participants – group; in terms of the term of execution – long-term, designed for a month.

During the implementation of the project, students learned to plan their work; put forward hypotheses; searched, analyzed, systematized information, created a "Bank" of sources and resources; conducted research and solved problems together in micro groups; summarized and defended the results of the project; evaluated themselves and the team; summed up the results.

Conclusion. So, the outcomes of numerous scientific studies, their own work experience provide grounds to indicate that organizational, search, communication, presentation, reflexive and special subject skills are developed in the project activities of schoolchildren. At the same time, the organization of project activities of students requires careful preparation and additional time spent by the teacher.

The article clarifies the essence of project educational and cognitive activity reveals its structure, describes such pertinent concepts as "Project situation", "Project task", "project".

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**MATHEMATICAL MODELS AS A BASIS
FOR IMPLEMENTING THE REQUIREMENTS
OF THE BASIC STANDARDS OF
SECONDARY EDUCATION**

Modeling as a theoretical teaching method plays a significant role in the educational process, since it is of fundamental importance not only for subjects of a natural direction, but also has a general scientific character.

The successful use of the properties of the model and reliance on them in the development of teaching methods will contribute to a more successful assimilation of educational material by students, the formation of their competencies, abilities and skills. The problem of using the modeling method in the learning process was investigated in this work.

The **purpose** of the study is to clarify the method of use mathematical modeling in the learning process of students to solve test tasks.

The work is considered as a presentation of the modeling of students' educational tasks in the part of studying mathematics, as it is relevant in view of the importance of students acquiring the skills of relating an applied problem to the field from which it is correlated and finding a mathematical model for its solution.

Results. In the course of work, in particular after the analysis of research, scientific and methodological literature and educational process at school demonstrates the need for a methodological provision of the process formation of students' skills in mathematical modeling while studying algebras in primary and secondary schools.

Mathematical modeling will resolve the urgent the task of forming the relevant key and subject competency. The study of mathematical modeling is a promising area of study for educational mathematicians, which can facilitate and interest children in the study of mathematics from elementary school. Such experiments conducted by native and foreign methodologists have proved this.

Conclusion. The method of using mathematical modeling in the process of teaching students to solve test problems is very relevant in connection with the training of high school students for external independent testing in Mathematics, which since this year has become a prerequisite for entering any Higher Educational Institution in Ukraine.

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GEOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BÉZIER CURVES

The **aim** is to consider the geometric characteristics of Bézier curves. Until the end of the 50s of the 20th century, the process of designing and manufacturing cars was divided into two components. The first is working with relatively simple parts (bolts, nuts, springs, that is, circles, polygons and other shapes). The second – elements of the body and interior, which were sometimes drawn entirely by hand. Distortions are subjective – it created great problems in the manufacture of real parts. For this, Bézier curves were invented, which are quite simple to implement and are considered “aesthetic” lines.

Results. The Bézier curve is built on the reference points – the vertices of the convex polygon inside which it is placed. It necessarily passes through the first and last vertices of the reference polygon. The Bézier curve, which is determined by n points, has the $(n - 1)$ th order. A Bézier curve is a smooth line that lies entirely within the convex hull of its reference points. Adjusting the position of at least one of the reference points leads to a change in the entire Bézier curve. A Bézier curve is symmetric – that is, a change in direction does not affect its shape, and any of its arcs is also a Bézier curve.

The most common are Bézier curves of the second and third orders. Curves of higher degrees require large computing resources for their processing. The Bézier curve is given by a vector-parametric equation, where Bernstein polynomials serve as basis functions. Most often, the de Casteljau recursive algorithm is used to calculate Bézier curves. The advantage of this algorithm is its higher computational stability compared to the direct construction method. To display complex smooth lines, separate Bézier curves are successively combined into a Bézier spline according to the desired degree of smoothness.

Knowledge of the geometric characteristics of Bézier curves will be useful in solving problems related to the optimization of object profiles or trajectories of their movement. For example, in animation or computer user interface design. To smooth the trajectory of the cursor or to control the speed of icon movement. In robotics, where the movement of the welding arm must be smooth to avoid excessive tool wear. In aircraft construction when determining wing aerodynamics to reduce wind resistance. In the automotive industry when creating body surfaces and in construction when defining architectural forms to avoid negative effects, in particular “crooked mirrors”. In the production of various tools to improve their ergonomic properties. Numerical values of geometric characteristics of Bézier curves can be used to form classification features for diagnosing technical objects.

Conclusions. The abstract gives relations for determining such geometric properties of Bézier curves as: tangent at an arbitrary point; curvature at an arbitrary point; radius of curvature at an arbitrary point; coordinates of the center of curvature; the amount of twist; elasticity of function by parameter. Attention is on the dependence of the specified characteristics on the degree of Bézier curve. Other properties of Bézier curve were also analyzed: the range of the parameter change, and what happens if it goes beyond its limits; ways to visualization of these curves, exponentiation and other manipulations.

ART SECTION

MA KAI

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ASPECTS OF FORMING DIGITAL COMPETENCE OF PRE-SERVICE INTERIOR DESIGNERS

Modern professional activity of a designer cannot be imagined without the use of computer programs, which are essential and key means of implementing any design ideas. Today, it is very difficult for a future designer to navigate freely in the world of new digital opportunities, but this is necessary in order to be competitive and in demand in the labor market and meet the requirements of professional standards and representatives of business structures to as specialist in the field of interior design.

The **aim** of the article reveals the aspects of training pre-service interior designers with the help of modern computer technology.

Results: The formation of digital competence of future specialists in the field of design begins during the period of professional training of personnel in educational institutions. The relevance of the formation of digital competence in future specialists is confirmed by many studies, for example, L. Kartashova, N. Bakhmat, I. Plish studied the development of digital competence of a teacher in the informational and educational environment of the institution. O. Zhernovnikova, L. Peretyaga, A. Kovtun, M. Korduban, O. Nalyvayko, N. Nalyvayko studied the technology of forming digital competence of future teachers using the means of gamification. Today there are many software products and enough a large number of online tools that can be successfully used in design activities. However, the effective use of such software products and online services is possible only if the designer knows how to navigate such a variety of tools, understand their capabilities, know their specifics and be able to use them to achieve the set goal. The competitiveness of the future designer depends on the quality of the work that he will perform. For the qualitative implementation of the set design task, it is necessary to have basic key competencies, that is, to be competent in their field of activity. However, in the modern world, in the context of the development of the design sphere, computer technology is becoming increasingly important. Such changes prioritize the formation of digital competence of the future specialist.

The development of digital competence in the process of preparing designers will contribute to the study of the following computer programs: graphic editors (Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Illustrator, Adobe Photoshop Lightroom, Autodesk 3ds Max, Autodesk AutoCAD and etc.). Wide opportunities for the development of digital competence are opened up by the use of cloud services (<https://color.adobe.com>, <https://ugol.me>, <https://www.homestyler.com> and etc.) that allow you to quickly and easily implement intermediate tasks that are necessary to achieve the final result of a design product.

Conclusions. For a modern designer, mastering computer programs and online services are necessary condition for the effectiveness of his professional activity. However, the use of such a powerful toolkit requires thorough training of the future designer and the formation of digital competence.

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INTEGRATED METHODS OF TEACHING MUSIC IN UNIVERSITIES OF CHINA

The standardization of music education in China involves the formation of potential music teachers' ability to think in categories that characterize the concept of the synthesis of arts, reveal the principles of the relationship of various musical subjects, and in practice help to master integrated courses from the cycle of professionally-oriented artistic disciplines of the curriculum.

The **aim** is to describe the integrated methods of teaching music in universities of China.

The **results**. In this regard, the educational programs of bachelors of musical and pedagogical specialties of Chinese universities give preference to the study of the best systems of musical education, among which stand out the system of K. Orff, J. Dalcroze, Z. Kodai.

In China, the "New System of Music Education" has been introduced, which puts up a goal to shape the emotional intelligence of the potential music teacher. In the concept, an important place is given to the learning of the compositions of traditional Chinese music, and among the leading methods of music pedagogy, there is a highlighted method of perception and creative mastery of the best samples of the folk and composer's heritage, according to the region. Among the main pedagogical guidelines for the students' training, three systems of musical education can be distinguished, which were implemented in Germany (K. Orff), Switzerland (J. Dalcroze), and Hungary (Z. Kodai).

The basis of the integrated methods of schoolchildren teaching, proposed by J. Dalcroze, is the interrelationship between music and dance. Observation of a piece of music acquires a "feeling of happiness and pleasure" in schoolchildren due to the intonation of the figurative content of the melody. By imitating body movements, students are able to perceive the rhythmic colouring of a piece of art and the properties of its musical language. An acquaintance of the students of musical and pedagogical specialties with K.Orf's "Shulwerk" provides an opportunity to carry out practical work with students to analyze instrumental music from the point of view of their creative music making. Learning of groups of musical instruments and methods of selection of educational material open a new perspective on the rhythmic basis of the musical nature and the role of timbre in the artistic and figurative content of the studied works.

Practical methods of involving students in artistic and creative activities are mastered by potential music teachers studying in Chinese universities using the integrated Z. Kodai's method. The experience of the famous Hungarian composer contributes to the students' awareness of the sequence of formation of their pupils' musical literacy through the construction of musical education according to the principle from simple to complex, the basis of which is the synthesis of music and dance. Integrated methods reveal to the potential teachers the possibilities of polyartistic music teaching at school.

The **conclusions**. The integrated methods of teaching music in universities of China have been described and analyzed.

STEPANOVA Anna

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POLYCULTURAL GUIDELINES FOR THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF MUSIC

The **purpose** of the article is to determine the main orientations of multicultural music teacher training.

In conditions of intensive development of international relations, cultural exchange takes place at the national and international levels between the countries of the world. As scientists note, for successful intercultural interaction with representatives of different nationalities, not only academic knowledge of musical art is necessary, but also an understanding of value orientations, the national mentality of another state, which determines the dominance of multicultural education, which is aimed at forming a personality capable of active and effective life activities in a multinational and multicultural environment, has a developed sense of understanding and tolerance for the cultures of other countries, the ability to successfully interact with representatives of different nationalities, beliefs and cultures.

Multiculturalism is the object of research in the works of such scientists as V. Bolgarina, L. Gorbunova, G. Dmitriev, V. Kovtun, I. Loschenova, O. Milyutina, A. Solodka. In particular, the study of multiculturalism in the context of school education is devoted to the work of V. Boychenko, L. Volyk. L. Peretyagy and others.

The **results**. Multicultural art education is characterized by the spread of information space in which cultures interpenetrate, and the formation of multicultural value orientations of future music teachers, since it is the music teacher who is the translator of multicultural values to the future generation. This confirms the basic idea of the globalized world, the essence of which is that the definition and solution of many problems is possible only through global processes, and not at the level of an individual country.

Conclusions. In this regard, it is extremely important to train future teachers of musical art of Ukraine, specialists of a new generation who are able to adequately perceive, subtly and highly evaluate art, preserve national traditions and multiply spiritual and material assets at the intercultural level. One of the key tasks of modern professional training of teachers is the problem of forming the multicultural competence of future music teachers.

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CHOREOGRAPHIC CULTURE AS A MEANS OF INFLUENCING THE ETHICAL OUTLOOK OF THE MODERN GENERATION

The **aim** is to consider the choreographic culture as a means of influencing the ethical outlook. In the conditions of the modernization of the education system in Ukraine, the issue of forming an ethical worldview through the means of choreographic art of the modern generation, which would be able to appreciate the great heritage of the world and national art, remains essential. Ethical culture under the Cossacks was distinguished in the field of religious culture. It was implemented as a platform for forming a civic position as a condition for ethical decency in education. The religious culture was at the level of understanding philosophical, cultural, legal, Ukrainian studies, and socio-pedagogical concepts at the level of ethics of interaction.

Results. A person living among other people is in communication and relationships between people. In its activity, it is guided by the specific behavior activity with an orientation to its own needs and collective interests. Choreographic culture is one of the languages of teaching self-expression. The readiness for choreographic culture is not exhausted by a certain amount of knowledge acquired at school, abilities, and skills. This readiness includes the desire for self-realization, the desire to learn further and to develop the individual's physical and mental-cognitive powers, abilities, morals, and other qualities. The modern generation gladly accepts ritual choreographic culture in extracurricular work. In the sections on Cossack and ethical, pedagogical culture, it is now worth analyzing the rich spiritual and correctional experience that is currently interpreted by jurists, philosophers, sociologists, psychologists, teachers, social pedagogues, ethnologists, ethnographers, writers, folklorists, ethnopsychologists, ethnopedagogues through the criteria of social norms and foundations of religious and state holidays.

At the core of teaching Cossack ethical values is attention to dignified, benevolent, responsible relationships of individuals in the community who determined their destiny and faith based on their own freedom of choice. Cossack's pedagogy can form stable, benevolent relationships between individuals in a group; to teach charity in the family, to the neighbor (forms different feelings), to teach to rejoice at the appearance of true love, a hardworking family, and self-improved children. National rituals presented the motivation for happiness through successful facts from a person's family and public life.

Conclusion. The means of Cossack religious holidays prevented the general punishment of a child, a person, and corrected his development, behavior, and desire for self-improvement through the centuries-old practice of public and family education. At the heart of general control was attention to the transmission of a better collection experience. Christian values served as an orientation towards the social and humane ideal. Choreographic culture is of great importance in the formation of the ethical worldview of a modern person; using dance art inculcates a love for beauty, stimulates pedagogical competence, and gives birth to originality.

PANASENKO Yuliia

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ART THERAPY AS A TECHNOLOGY OF ART PEDAGOGY

The **purpose** of this study is to define art therapy as a technology of art pedagogy.

The **result** of this study is that art therapy can be defined as a technology of art pedagogy. After all, the child's personality develops in it on the basis of art in the process of drawing, dancing, creating fairy tales, sculpting from plasticine, dough, or working with sand. Namely, any creative activity that helps to manifest and express one's emotions.

Art pedagogy is a special direction in pedagogy that helps to teach, develop and nurture a child's personality on the basis of art while teaching any discipline. So this is a synthesis of two branches of scientific knowledge (pedagogy and art), which ensure the development of the theory and practice of the pedagogical process of children's artistic development and provide answers to the questions of the formation of the foundations of artistic culture through art and artistic and creative activities (musical, visual, artistic and speech, theatrical -game).

Technology is understood as a set of knowledge, information about the sequence of individual production operations in the process of producing something.

Art therapy is a therapy of art that allows you to experience internal conflicts, anxiety, and fears that disturb the child with the help of creativity. Considering all this, we can say that art therapy is indeed partially a technology of art pedagogy, as it can be used for both children and adults. After all, it was first used in work with adults. Also, art therapy is not only a manifestation of creativity, but also treatment with the help of art. It is the formation of activation of a person's creative potential, internal mechanisms of self-regulation and healing, and helps a person to reveal his new possibilities and affirm his individual and unique way of being in the world.

The process itself is important in art therapy. And in working with children, it is important to express what worries her inside through play and creativity: through the type of paint, colors, the plot she wants to portray, etc.

Conclusions. Art therapy is a technology of art pedagogy, because it teaches, develops and nurtures a child's personality on the basis of art with the help of musical, visual, art-speech, dance, theatrical and game activities.

POSTER SESION

ANDRUSHCHENKO Olesya

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IS IT POSSIBLE TO HAVE THE RIGHTS TO LIFE IN CONDITION OF WAR?

IS IT POSSIBLE TO HAVE THE RIGHT TO LIFE IN CONDITIONS OF WAR?

On February 24, 2022, after the start of a full-scale attack by the Russian Federation on Ukraine, the life of the world and Ukrainians changed. Among the mass violations of human rights that appeared in the conflict area, the most vulnerable was the RIGHT TO LIFE...

INTRODUCTION

Today, the relevance and importance of the right to human life, its implementation and protection are obvious, because without such a fundamental right, all other rights cease to have any meaning. Life is a prerequisite for the realization of all human rights and freedoms. This right is enshrined in all human rights treaties and is part of general international law. Despite this, the right to life has a relative nature and, under certain legal and factual conditions, may be legitimately limited. In practice, armed conflicts and situations of violence within the state become the main threat and obstacle to the realization of this right.

RESULTS

However, the war led to massive human rights violations of both civilians and combatants, especially their rights to life, liberty, and personal integrity. OHCHR has dealt with numerous allegations of extrajudicial killings and executions, arbitrary detentions and enforced disappearances, torture and ill-treatment, and war-related sexual violence. Most of the violations of the right to life, caused by the use of explosive weapons, cluster munitions or unguided missiles, which are heavily influenced by Russian forces in densely populated areas, show that Russian forces are violating the laws of war significantly, and so far no one can do anything about it.

LEGAL REGULATION

The right to life is enshrined in Article 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: "Everyone has the right to life, liberty and personal integrity." The broader concept of the right to life is defined in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966. Article 6 states that the right to life is an inalienable right of every human being. This right is protected by law. No one can be arbitrarily deprived of life. In Ukraine, the right to life is enshrined in Article 27 of the Constitution of Ukraine: "Every person has the inalienable right to life. No one can be arbitrarily deprived of life. The duty of the state is to protect human life. Everyone has the right to protect his life and health, the life and health of other people from illegal encroachments."

CONCLUSION

The difficult period for Ukraine shows the life activities of citizens in the conditions of martial law, and therefore the concepts and practice of implementing the protection of human rights need improvement, which determines the perspective of the issue and forms vectors for further research. It is fundamentally important to realize and understand the need to ensure human rights under any circumstances.

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TRANSPLANTATION OF HUMAN ANATOMICAL MATERIALS: THE REALITIES OF WAR

UKRAINE NEEDS YOUR

SUPPORT

TRANSPLANTATION OF HUMAN ANATOMICAL MATERIALS: THE REALITIES OF WAR

INTRODUCTION

TRANSPLANTATION IS A SPECIAL METHOD OF TREATMENT, WHICH CONSISTS OF ORGAN TRANSPLANTS (THEIR PARTS), TISSUES, ANATOMICAL FORMATIONS, HUMAN OR ANIMALS' CELLS, FETAL MATERIALS OF MAN FROM THE DONOR TO THE RECIPIENT AND IS AIMED AT RESTORATION OF HUMAN HEALTH

PRE - WAR

- 1) A NEW LAW ON TRANSPLANTATION WAS ADOPTED
- 2) THERE WAS A THEORETICAL POSSIBILITY TO SAVE MUCH MORE LIVES OF UKRAINIANS
- 3) THERE WAS A NEED TO INTRODUCE CERTAIN CHANGES AND AMENDMENTS TO THE LEGISLATION THAT WOULD SIGNIFICANTLY IMPROVE SOME OF ITS PROVISIONS AND ENABLE THE NATIONAL TRANSPLANTATION SYSTEM TO BE MORE EFFECTIVE

THE WAR TIME

- 1) ABSENCE OF PLANNED CHANGES IN LEGISLATION
- 2) DURING THE WAR, DOCTORS SAVED EIGHT LIVES THANKS TO TRANSPLANTATION

IMPACT OF THE WAR

1

THE INCREASE IN THE NUMBER OF PEOPLE WHO NEED TRANSPLANTATION IS THE VICTIMS OF THE SHOOTING: CIVILIAN AND MILITARY

THE NEED TO SIMPLIFY AND SPEED UP ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURES

2

PRESENTED BY: DARIA SOLAROVA

POST-GRADUATE STUDENT, YAROSLAV MUDRYI NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY

SOLOHENKO Semen

Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Ukraine

ARMED CONFLICTS AND DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

Armed conflicts and domestic violence

Presented by: Semen Solonenko, post-graduate student, Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University

Armed conflicts worsen the situation of domestic violence further due to the negative impact of economic and social hardship, as well as psychological trauma.

! Domestic violence is one of the types of gender-based violence

Ukrainian legislation distinguishes 4 types of domestic violence

The most vulnerable segments of the population

- Women who are internally displaced or refugees
- Women in the countryside
- Women with disabilities
- Representatives of LGBT and other minorities.

! Women suffer more from cases of gender-based violence, which is often used in armed conflict. Men, in turn, suffer more from violence on the battlefield (directly in a military conflict).

Reasons

- ⊞ Increasing tolerance for violence
- ⊞ Exaggeration of the biological difference between the sexes, especially in patriarchal societies (increasing demand for warrior heroes, increasing the value of traditional masculine qualities)
- ⊞ Lack of adequate psychological assistance for persons who returned home after participating in the military conflict
- ⊞ Increasing the level of aggression
- ⊞ The desire for revenge
- ⊞ Hatred

ESSAYS. PERSONAL EXPERIENCE DURING THE WAR

CHERNENKO Mariia

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STUDYING DURING THE WAR

Aim: To reveal the problems and difficulties of studying, gaining knowledge during the war and analyze its influence on people's lives.

Results: Studying in peacetime has always been common and understandable, and, what is most important, well-organized. Students attended classes, had the opportunity to communicate face-to-face with friends, participate in many educational activities and study hard.

They had all the conditions for successful learning and creating a good future. But now everything has changed. Learning has taken on a whole new form and has become very difficult for pupils and students from Ukraine. Some Ukrainians are still under occupation in the towns.

Their daily worries and hopes are related to thinking about how to stay alive. It is now difficult for students in this situation to focus on studying at the university. Anxiety, lack of sleep, fear gather all their strength and prevent teenagers from learning and mastering the material well.

Also, many people have left the country and have to start a new life abroad. This is a huge change in their reality. Refugees have to start all over again in another country with completely different rules, laws, culture and even language.

For students, such changes are a great stress. They are trying to figure out how to live. Their main question today is: "Why?". Sadness and despair gripped the minds of teenagers. Now it is very difficult for them to focus on the teaching material.

But we need to develop, to look for new opportunities. Life goes on, we need to look for light in the dark, hold on to all the good that we see in the world every day to make it easier.

Conclusions: Studying during the war is not easy, and it is mostly a spiritual question. People are suffering from current problems and are afraid of their future. But studying could help us in future, so now teachers have to support students and we have to force ourselves to learn to return and help our Ukraine to rise from the ashes.

CHUDINA Yelizavieta

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TRAINING DURING WAR AND PEACE

This work is devoted to determining the peculiarities of studying at universities during the war and peace.

The purpose of this study is to determine the main problems of learning, prospects for distance education and methods of teaching.

It has determined the following tasks: to formulate theoretical principles of studying; to highlight the ways of learning where this is not available; to describe psychological state of teachers and students; to determine the role of education in today's life. On February 24, 2022, Russia launched a full-scale invasion of Ukraine. It changed everything. The president declared martial law.

Results. With the beginning of hostilities on the territory of Ukraine, students began forced vacations, later their studies continued. It is allowed to adjust the schedule for students who need it. If necessary, completed materials can be sent later. We perform tasks without deadlines. I believe that training is not the most necessary thing right now. If the student is in a combat zone, you need to take academic leave. After that, training will begin only next year. This option is not suitable for everyone. Students who do not take academic leave can apply to the administration. They will make changes to the schedule. After that, testing will take place. By the end of August, they must process the material that is in the curriculum of the course.

Learning is a way out of a situation that can save you from psychological pressure and inaction. Resuming training during the war is an important step for society as a whole and a great challenge for "tomorrow" in particular. That's why we need to be focused, agile, coordinated and resilient. It is psychologically difficult, because in addition to the fact that we have to accept that the country is at war, many relatives do not get in touch, we have to somehow learn the material. Of course, students feel the support, loyalty of teachers and faculty leadership. Despite the sirens, teachers conduct classes and students receive education.

A good education gives you the opportunity to make yourself strong to manage any situation. It keeps you informed of the norms and rules of the society in which you live, and gives you the opportunity to demand from those in power to correct their negligence or omissions. In particular, the leaders of social change are often highly educated young people. Education, combined with life experience, gives us the opportunity to influence important decisions and do so with better understanding and compassion for others, thereby improving the lives of others. Modern distance learning systems allow not only to conduct training, but also to control knowledge and assess student achievement.

To conclude, despite some difficulties, the educational process in Ukraine continues. This allows students to improve their professional skills, as well as distract from the daily news. New information obtained during training gives the opportunity to make informed decisions. Too often, leaders have to make these decisions quickly, without all the critical information, and they can be huge, not only for the person making them, but for groups of people or the nation as a whole.

DECHKO Anastasiia

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EDUCATION DURING WARTIME

War is a time of upheaval for the whole world. Every citizen of Ukraine – from a small child to a pensioner – feels the consequences of these terrible events. War changes your thinking, values, and lifestyle, it makes such adjustments that will forever leave an imprint in your life. War is like a teenage tattoo in a visible place, when you are grown-up and want to remove it, but you can't do it because it's got too deep, and now every day it reminds you of those events.

The **aim** of the work is to analyse the study environment during wartime.

Results. Student years are a conscious time for every person. At this time, education is a priority in life, which forms a highly qualified worker; but during the war, priorities change...

Studying during the war is a rather complicated process that requires certain efforts and, most importantly, conditions. If the student managed to move to a safer place, studying could help take the mind off the news, military events and constant stress. On the other hand, it is very difficult to concentrate on learning information or completing a certain task when you are constantly thinking about the war.

I faced such educational problems during the war: sirens against the background of lectures and seminars, which, in addition to causing anxiety, also distracted me from studying; lack of necessary educational materials due to moving to another city; problems with the Internet, which complicates the process of distance learning.

The situation is completely different with students who did not manage to leave the active war zones. They not only have problems with communication and the Internet, but also constant life-threatening conditions do not allow them to continue their studies normally.

At such moments, we must understand that education, of course, is necessary, but life is much more important.

The main thing to remember is that our life goes on and study can be a good way to distract from negative emotions. We can invest the acquired knowledge in helping Ukraine to bring our victory closer.

Conclusion. Education during wartime is not an easy, but a very necessary process for every student, it can benefit both the student and the country.

GNATIV Anastasiia

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LEARNING & TEACHING: DURING WAR & PEACE

Until February 24, 2022, I was a student of the Skovoroda National Pedagogical University, who attended the university and performed tasks. My biggest fears and experiences were school practice and everyday problems. But in one night everything changed.

The **aim** of the work is to analyse the study during the war. And here I am – still a university student, but now my experiences are no longer related to learning. Now all my thoughts from morning till night are occupied with the question: "Are my parents alive? Do they have enough food and water?", because they are in a very dangerous place.

Results. Learning is important and needed always and everywhere. That's for sure. But in such a difficult time, not all students and lectures have access to the Internet and the opportunity to teach or study.

And I'm talking now not only about the possibility of a person to go online. I am talking about our possible unstable moral and psychological situation.

Despite the difficult state of our native state, the administration and teachers of our university are doing everything possible to ensure that we, students, continue to acquire knowledge and receive our diplomas.

Students who have gone abroad have the opportunity to continue their studies at local universities and then return to their home university without any problems. And those students who stayed in Ukraine have the opportunity to study remotely. And I think that's right.

The most difficult thing now is probably for children studying in schools. Distance learning is not something that will be effective for children. But the schools of our country are doing everything possible to interest children in learning and give them new knowledge and skills.

Conclusion. War is scary and very difficult. None of us will be ready for this. But we are an indomitable and free people. We will fight for our country, for our freedom and for our lives. And even what we are learning now already shows everyone that we cannot be frightened and broken.

GUZIEVA Anna

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LEARNING & TEACHING DURING WAR AND PEACE

Sometimes, life throws up new obstacles for teachers. We are taught how to deal with them as professionals, nevertheless, you cannot be prepared for everything. A pandemic was an impediment to quality teaching in 2020, on the contrary, now it is worse - the full-scale war. Just as then it appears that our conscientious teachers are not lost and keep assisting pupils in harsh conditions.

The aim of our research is to take note of improving teaching and learning which would help to work more efficiently.

The results have shown that the Ministry of Education and Science advises conducting twice as less classes as in the pre-war period. This would encourage children to concentrate better on lessons and make it easier for teachers to prepare for lessons. The rest of the time should be devoted to working in an asynchronous mode such as communicating with children via messengers, working with online resources, attaching more exercises and tasks which involve psychological relief, techniques for resolving emotional states, etc. Students must not be condemned or indicated derelictions. Nowadays since children are encountering stress throughout the conflict that is the very reason why the assessment of knowledge should be positive and encouraging, even though not everything works out. Moreover, methods of working with students must be selected according to the subject, age of students and their interests. Teachers are highly advised to give preference to exploratory and creative methods of work.

Furthermore, it is strenuous to establish a group or collective form of work, as a result, it is better to focus on discussion and partnership options for training. Additionally, it would be forcefully suggested to hold individual meetings with newly arrived students in order to present the educational institution as an effective and safe educational space and / or create concise information sheets of similar content. Still, a feature of distance learning is the likelihood during online meetings of situations where the air alarm is activated. In such cases, teachers must calmly inform the students that an air alarm has been sounded, and therefore classes should be stopped; emphasize the need for students to go to a safe place; ask students to leave the conference.

For **the conclusions**, teachers had to look for new effective ways to present material to their students. Psychological tension and anxiety among students have also increased. However, the most important thing is to find an approach to everyone and create the most comfortable conditions that are possible in this situation. All children who have the opportunity to learn should be involved in the educational process.

IVANCHA Anhelina*H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine***TRAINING DURING THE WAR**

With the arrival of the war in our country, Ukrainian educators faced numerous challenges. Many of us had to fight for our lives, some lost relatives and friends. But despite the catastrophic consequences of hostilities for each of us, education and knowledge are still very relevant. The arrival of the war in Ukraine is a great sorrow for all of us. But continuing to learn for students in this difficult time is a must for each of us. We may have to rebuild our country after the war, using the knowledge gained. The **aim** of our research is to take note of training during the war.

Results. Difficulties in returning students to study may also be related to the living conditions in which they found themselves due to the war. Of course, there are problems with this. There may be a problem with the hardware. Besides there is an understanding of the situation that not all families who have moved within Ukraine, they do not live in very comfortable conditions. For example, if they live in some educational institutions there or in gyms temporarily.

Many IDPs do not have textbooks, have problems with the Internet, and classes may be interrupted due to air alarms. Continuing to study in such conditions requires great courage from both students and teachers. The war dealt a severe blow to all areas, and education was no exception. Destroyed educational institutions, whole regions are not able to resume learning even remotely. Millions of people, including students and teachers, have been forced to flee their homes. This is quite stressful in terms of moving and then what students need to study.

Conclusions. Educators have become accustomed to distance learning during the pandemic. But, during the summers, students are distracted, correspond in chat rooms instead of listening to the teacher. In such conditions it is quite difficult to concentrate. Of course, students have relaxed during this time, it is very difficult for them to return to study, except to see classmates. Training in such a difficult period is needed not only to acquire new knowledge. First of all, to help students cope with their experiences.

Also, communication with peers and friends helps a lot. Applicants understand that they are alone in their fears and experiences, and everyone feels such emotions. During the war, the functions of learning changed a little, now you need to learn not only literacy, but also how to arrange emotions, how to cope with their feelings and not to lose yourself.

IVKOVA Elyzaveta

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

PECULIARITIES OF STUDYING DURING THE WAR

The **aim** of the abstract is to structure the main theses regarding university studies during the war.

Results:

1. I believe that studying during the war is difficult and not entirely objective. All the time I was in Kharkiv under constant bombardment, often without access to the Internet and in terrible conditions.

2. Studying during the war did not allow me to concentrate on the material, it was not possible to prepare well for classes. At a time when there were constant explosions outdoors, my closest people were in danger: relatives in Donbass, my friend was under occupation from the first day of the war, without being online all this time. My mental health was broken, and the constant deadlines for tasks, so as trying not to have expired tasks, further depressed it.

3. Due to the fact that the transport in our city did not work and all the institutions were closed, it was a big problem to get necessary goods. Before the war, I used to come to the library to take books for my term paper. Unfortunately, these materials are not available on the Internet and my educational process became more complicated.

4. On the other hand, when I still managed to find the Internet and attend classes, it gave me the opportunity to get out of my comfort zone: I learned how to act even in non-standard and extreme conditions. Sometimes it even helped to distract and forget about the ongoing horrible events that affected us all.

5. During the war all of our people did a great act of unity, which, undoubtedly, have been shown during the educational process. The dean's office and the head of the group constantly tried to be in touch with everyone, they were interested and worried about everything being in order with us. Thus, it inspired and motivated me to overcome all difficulties.

Conclusions: Undoubtedly, studying in time of war is much worse than in peacetime. Some students from my group could not even participate in the educational process, as they were under occupation and did not have access to the Internet since the first day of the war. Such students had no opportunity to visit classes and missed a lot of study materials.

Thus, they have no motivation and will to come back to their pre-war schedule and study process. I realized that studying during the war gave a lot of negative emotions, but there were also good moments that are definitely worth paying attention to. While studying during the war, I greatly reestimated my values, learned to appreciate what we had before it, and set myself new goals for the future. In particular, I realized that my profession as a philologist of the Ukrainian language is extremely important at such a time, and I should improve myself in this direction. In addition, we have learned to appreciate such trifles as, for example, listening to a teacher's lecture, coming to the university for classes, gaining new knowledge, meeting classmates in the same class.

KOBCHENKO Sofia

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

LEARNING ENGLISH TIME OF THE WAR

The main **aim** of the abstract is to analyze the importance of learning English during the war.

The obtained **results** of the research are:

- 1)** Firstly, I learn English to increase my own language skills and for future professional experience in different countries;
- 2)** Secondly, to conduct English lessons with children as a tutor.

English is one of the most favourite languages I have ever taught. In my opinion, any foreign language helps to understand your own language. The English language also is one of the most important languages in the modern world: more than one billion people can understand and speak this language, so you will not have problems in communication with others.

You can travel to the United States of America, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, India and many countries for postgraduate education in the best universities in the world and don't be afraid that you can't get quality knowledge because of language barriers.

Even before the war, I spent a lot of time studying English: reading different literature, watching films and passing various courses. Since early childhood I enjoy the books by English writers: Winnie-the-Pooh, Robinson Crusoe later Sherlock Holmes and Romeo and Juliet.

Furthermore, nowadays English is also the language of science - most of scientific articles and magazines in the world are published in English. Consequently, it is impossible to be a good specialist or scientist and find highly paid job without knowing this language.

As for me, I also study English to realize my dream and help children in mastering new language. During the first year of the university, I was able to teach young children. When the war started, I was forced to move to another city and tried to continue my activity. It was especially difficult, because kids were very frightened, they seemed to be eager for every sound, but we didn't give up. Draw English alphabet together, taught numbers, made animals from modelling clay and sang different songs.

Sometimes we conducted classes on the street: learned the names of animals, plants, played in different games, learned and had some fun. After a month of such classes, children not only got involved in the process of learning, but also smiled again and rejoiced at every lesson. English turned into an object of their daily pleasure and distraction from the events around.

Conclusion. Based on the foregoing, it should be noted that no matter how hard it is, you need to continue learning, improving yourself and remember that English opens new opportunities in our life. By the way, there is a nice proverb: «A little knowledge is a dangerous thing».

KOVALOVA Daria

H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH DURING THE WAR

The English language is always relevant.

The **aim** of this research is to show the importance of studying a foreign language during war.

Results. Shops with English books, textbooks, dictionaries appeared more and more lately. Students more often choose specialties related to language learning. Different professions increasingly require knowledge of English.

World rating EF EPI presented, that Ukraine is in the 40-th out of 112 countries for knowledge of English. This is an average level of knowledge.

Many people despite the events try to study in educational institutions and are engaged in self-education. Ukrainians have free access to various sites for learning languages, including the English language during war.

People, who live abroad, need this knowledge. Some online schools make discounts for learning this language. These lessons distract from bad thoughts and also students learn something new.

We think that it is important to learn English at any time, because it is one of the most common languages in the world.

Conclusions. Learning the English language is always relevant. People want to learn it if they have such opportunities.

KOZACHEK Anastasia

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

STUDYING DURING THE WAR

Aim: To reveal the content of the problem of studying and getting education during the war.

The **result:** I could not even think that there would be a war in our country. On February 24, every Ukrainian woke up from explosions. The war destroyed the dreams of everyone, killed many of our heroes, whom we will remember forever. The war took us an opportunity for normal, full-fledged training.

Without training there will be no future. Now there is a distance study, but with our situation in the country, not everyone has the opportunity to join it. Many do not have light, the Internet even basic accessories for study. I cannot imagine how difficult it will be for everyone to catch up with the loss. But I am sure that everyone will cope and be a well-being person in the future.

When I started studying during the war, it was difficult for me to get into the world of study at first. I was in bad psychological condition, so at first, I was a great burden. But later I gathered with the forces.

In my opinion all students who have the opportunity to study should be involved in the educational process in order to make everyone feel and start to learn and be interested in something new, not just war.

In my opinion, students need to say what they are young, that in such difficult conditions they continue to study and achieve results.

Positive motivation and evaluation of the students are of great importance for the student in such a difficult time.

As for me, weak point of distance learning is that there is a great tension on my eyes. I wear glasses, so for me such form of study is not very good. And in general, there are such subjects that are better explained offline.

I am very grateful to the teachers that they also have the ability to go online and explain to us every topic.

Education gives knowledge, and knowledge is really great force. Knowledge provides a good platform from which everyone can evaluate abilities in a particular branch, and thus - to form skills that will potentially lead to professional success.

Conclusion: I am very glad that I have such an opportunity to study in such difficult time for Ukrainians. I hope that soon I will meet with my classmates in the walls of the university. We rebuild everything that destroyed our enemy. We will win.

Glory to Ukraine!

LIEBIEDIEVA Olha

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

TRAINING DURING THE WAR

The **aim** of the paper is to describe study conditions in wartime.

Results. Life of Ukrainians changed a lot with the beginning of the war in our country. Schoolchildren, graduates, undergraduates are in a difficult situation. Many young people under stress struggle to complete simple assignments. World Community gives Ukrainians the opportunity to study, take courses, study languages for free.

If to compare our possibilities to get education to and under time to enter, then certainly in the second case of studies is more difficult. Difficult atmosphere surrounds the man, problems with the internet, shortage of educational sources through the closed libraries or move. In my opinion, it all very influences on quality of our studies.

Consider that at this time self-development is important, if to develop, to improve, and afterwards to help others to become the best. It is extremely important to remember, that knowledge is given to us a good platform by means of that we can become successful, on condition that we will develop them and perfect.

In fact, the world around us is constantly changing and we must keep up with these changes through self-development. In the opposite case, we become barriers to this progress and examples of this in real life can be found. It is especially important if you are responsible for taking difficult decisions that can change the fate of many people.

In spite of hard times, I try not to lose productivity and grow. I am very glad that my studies have resumed at my university, although the moments are well known to miss, I try to do all tasks and projects in time.

Conclusions. So, I am convinced that you should study always and not fundamentally, whether you will read a useful book, take an online course, attend a lecture or enter the university. Education will expand your horizons and help you make a conscious choice for yourself and others. You want to live better, learn by yourself and focus on education and experience. Be wise.

LEBEDEVA Nadiia

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LEARNING DURING THE WAR

Aim. To reveal the content of the problem of learning during the war. It is a very difficult period for all of the students and teachers as well. No one could even think that in the 21st century we would be hiding in the rubble, starving and saying goodbye to life. These are the hard realities of our lives. Education during the war is a relevant topic for all students and schoolchildren. Is it normal? Everyone's answer is different. In this essay, I want to share my opinion about it. Let's start with the advantages.

Results. Firstly, training is an anti-stressful activity. It takes up most of our time, forcing us to concentrate on tasks. Doing even a small number of tasks leaves less time for bad thoughts and reading the news. Learning makes you get out of bed and start doing something. Education is now our main job!

Secondly, education gives us the opportunity to live at least a little different life than we are used to. It's a bit like the coronavirus. Some of us still continue to study remotely as we do during quarantine and limit ourselves to going out.

On the other hand, there are also disadvantages. Now I am in Mariupol. I think it's pointless to describe the events that have happened and are happening now. Our city has become very popular and the whole world knows about our city. It's a shame that at such a terrible price. It's horrible here, unbearable and every day we say goodbye to life and don't know what will happen tomorrow.

So not everyone has the opportunity to attend lectures, even in online form. A lot of my friends are now in the occupied territories; someone does not have communications, the Internet, and sufficient resources.

Therefore, some students study, and some do not. It's not fair. I don't know how to study now, because I just don't have that opportunity. Right now I'm writing this essay, and in the next district they're shooting, a really heavy shooting. Some professors are very demanding and don't understand the kind of situation some of us are in. I want to study! I want to learn, but I don't have the opportunity! And I'm very upset about that.

There is a lot of news these days and we have to read it in order to understand how controlled the situation in our country is. However, sometimes all these events are very confusing and you can't concentrate. It is impossible to devote enough time to study, because constant anxiety, news, possible arrivals – does not contribute to «normal» study.

Conclusion. Thus, studying during the war is a topical issue. I think that it is necessary to find an individual approach to each student and reduce the requirements as in peacetime. I strongly believe that everything will be fine soon and our country, our citizens, students, and pupils will return to their textbooks and teachers will drop their guns and continue to teach our future generation!

MAIOROVA Olha

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

WHY WE SHOULD LEARN ENGLISH IN WARTIME?

Language is a reflection of the culture of the country and the mentality of its inhabitants. By studying a foreign language, we begin to better understand its speakers, learn how social contacts are built in another country, and learn to interact with people whose thinking and perception of the world differ from ours.

The **purpose** of our work is to find out the main reasons for learning a foreign language during the war.

Results. During the study of a foreign language, new neural connections are created in the brain, the volume of grey matter grows, and memory and attention improve. The more languages a person learns, the faster and better he solves intellectual problems.

Knowledge of a second language greatly expands the opportunities to build a career in your home country and abroad.

Learning a new language creates distractions from the news, particularly in wartime. Keeping up to date with news is important, especially now. However, watching YouTube videos all day, scrolling social networks news and reading headlines are definitely bad for us psychologically. Even a very politically active person needs, from time to time, to stop thinking about the horrors of war, pandemic, or natural disasters.

Knowing foreign languages allows us to get information from various sources. It's crucial during a war when authoritarian regime propaganda is particularly active. Every country has its own interests, its traditions in communicating information. That's why it's useful to see different types of coverage for the same event.

Learning a foreign language helps reduce stress, learn something new and distracts from bad news.

A foreign language also gives us the opportunity to get in touch with our friends from countries involved in the conflict. We can express our support, and ask them to tell us their perspective.

It is important to understand what's written on signs protesters wave during anti-war demonstrations. It's interesting to hear the original words of the politicians. Knowing a foreign language removes filters and gives us a better representation of reality.

Conclusions. People who study the language during the war are characterized by better perception and stability, and the level of tension in this cohort of people is lower.

MAKSYMOVA Olena

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EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN CONDITIONS OF WAR

The **aim** of my work is to study the state of the educational process during the war. After all, with the beginning of the war, our humanity is living in new realities. Thousands of people were forced to leave their homes and go to safer places. All spheres of human life have changed.

The education sector has undergone special changes. Fear of constant danger, explosions and anticipation of the worst forced the suspension of the educational process for a while. Some facilities are closed and some accept temporary IDPs. There are also institutions that operate normally.

The **results** of my research show that the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, as well as other social organizations quickly found new effective ways and methods to solve these problems. Methodical recommendations for educators and teachers were created.

Many platforms for learning have been created and opened free of charge, the educational process for schoolchildren has been organized on Ukrainian television, and students are allowed to study asynchronously.

Even children who have left the country have the opportunity to continue their education in distance learning or in any other form that is safe for the child. As a result, the activities of educators and teachers in general have also reoriented. Now it is aimed primarily at the psychological support of children, and only then at the formation of new knowledge in them.

Every family now has a non-formal pedagogical education, as it is the parents who have to act as teachers in those regions where the education of children is impossible due to understandable circumstances.

In **conclusion**, I would like to say that the war has changed all areas of our lives, the education sector is no exception. However, educational institutions are looking for ways to adapt the educational process in times of war.

Therefore, the education, upbringing and development of children takes place under any circumstances.

MARKELOVA Alina

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

TRAINING DURING HOSTILITIES

The **aim**: I want to tell my own story about how I lived during the war in Ukraine. Share experiences of how we learn during the war, and share tips on how to psychologically maintain your health

The **results**: The last few months have been very difficult, more in a moral sense. Early in the morning of February 24, I, like millions of the Ukrainians, woke up to the horrific explosions in the city. Everyone had their plans, their dreams, their aspirations, from the very moment of life each of us turned upside down. Now we have other dreams - to wake up again in the morning from the warm sun, to see our cities in bloom, and finally return home.

The hardest thing for me was to hear it again, as 8 years ago, before entering the university, I lived all my life in Slavyansk, Donetsk region, Bilbasivka village. Then another date was terrible for us – on April 20, at night, on Easter, people were terribly killed at the checkpoint. The headlines say, "This is the bloodiest Slavic Easter." From the same day, it was scary to go outside, we fell asleep and woke up to the sounds of machine guns, explosions, it always seemed that it was somewhere nearby. In the morning of February, I still did not realize that I would see something a little scarier than those days. There was no desire to do anything, and we still have to finish our studies. This thought did not appear immediately, it was just very scary, every explosion seemed close.

At our university we treated the situation with understanding, each teacher is ready to explain to you studying material separately, if you did not have the opportunity to attend the on-line class. Everyone understands that you can't always send completed tasks on time, it can be weeks late, but everyone knows what time we live in. It is very difficult to do homework, to read something, because constant own thoughts are difficult to concentrate. If you still manage to learn, what happens for a while.

Each air alarm reminded us of the time we have to study and live in general. I found rest for myself in Ukrainian books by modern authors, now I read a lot, not only on the tasks of the university, but also just for myself.

Until April 18, I lived in Kharkiv, having no desire to leave, but it was still scary to stay. Now I am in a safer place, where the explosions are much further. I can finally continue my studies in peace. In fact, it is very scary to sit at the monitor screen for lectures and seminars when there is a war outside. When explosions are no longer part of a scary war movie, but your everyday life.

The **conclusions**: I believe that the war in Ukraine will end soon. We will rebuild our cities, our lives, our dreams, but unfortunately, we will never be able to forget this terrible time. We will never forgive; we will never forget! I want to believe that the next generation will not see this. After all, Ukraine has lived in peacetime for almost 100 years, we can do better. It will only get better!

MAZUROVSKA Yevheniia

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MY THOUGHTS ON LEARNING DURING THE WAR

Aim: share your thoughts and impressions about studying during the war.

Results. War is probably the worst thing that can happen in a person's life. Unfortunately, we now, in today's world, have to live in military conditions. At first I thought that training during the war was not possible. I was very worried about how the classes would go; I was afraid that due to external factors I would not be able to study.

And I did not understand at all how the training would take place. When I started studying after a long break, I realized that not everything was as bad as it seemed at first. In vain I was so worried and afraid. During my studies, I realized that it distracts me from external events. That is, as I delve deeper into my studies, I forget what is going on around me and feel a little better. Strange as it may sound, it calms me down.

Although sometimes explosions make it very difficult to be distracted even to study and you have to leave everything and run to the shelter. Of course, training during the war is radically different from training in peacetime.

First, at least because we work remotely and can't see each other in real life with teachers and classmates, which is very unfortunate.

Secondly, there are situations when there is no connection and the Internet for a long time, and there is no opportunity to attend classes and study, of course teachers understand the state of affairs and always make concessions to us, but I do not like when this situation occurs because I want to study, but I just can't. In this situation I like be snowed under.

Thirdly, you still can't be as calm, confident and focused when doing tasks as in peacetime, because you have to listen to what's going on around you and run to the shelter when you hear an air alarm, to save your life. And this distracts from learning, but in this case, life is more important. In general, I try to study at any free moment, and if I can't, then at least I read, it also gives me pleasure.

Conclusions. Learning during the war is radically different from learning in peacetime, because learning is a little harder. But I am glad that even in such conditions, as much as possible, learning takes place.

Because it calms down a bit, distracts, keeps you in shape, gives you confidence in the future and pushes you to move on. So I try at every opportunity be as busy as a bee. I believe that soon everything will be fine and there will be an opportunity to learn in a calm, peaceful environment and not worry about anything.

MOROZ Kateryna

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STUDY AT THE UNIVERSITY DURING THE WAR

The **aim** is to describe the study at the university during the war, emphasize the problems and difficulties encountered by students during their studies and to provide advice to facilitate the educational process.

Results. Studying at the university in peacetime, as a rule, is of a disciplinary nature: classes, meetings take place at a certain time, without delays. Students have the opportunity to get an education, deepen their knowledge, participate in university events, competitions, meet new people, make friends, but war is changing their way of life, forcing them to constantly worry and live in stress.

Ukrainian students are in different life circumstances. Some of them are forced to hide with their parents in shelters and bomb shelters several times a day, live in the subway, at the train station or in a refugee shelter. Many do not have light, communication, and therefore do not have the opportunity to join the learning process, pass the job, get grades.

Despite the explosions and sirens, students, who have the opportunity to get in touch, continue to study at Ukrainian universities remotely. Unfortunately, studying during the war is not effective, even if the students are in a more or less secure place. Stress, anxiety, and lack of sleep negatively affect attention and memory, which reduces the student's academic performance.

Students do not get enough sleep due to the sound of sirens, so now it is better to reduce the load, not to burden the learning process, setting many tasks, because most adults have a high level of anxiety, which under heavy load can eventually turn into anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder or burnout. It is important for teachers to listen to the student and help in case of problems, not to put pressure on students, because support and contact with the teacher is very important.

All students who have the opportunity to study should be involved in the educational process so that they are distracted from the bad news, start to be interested in something new again, and not just the war.

Finally, the most significant thing is to improve the mood and motivate students is to talk more often about who they are well done, that in such difficult conditions they continue to learn and achieve results. Positive words and high appreciation of students' efforts are of great importance to them.

Conclusions. Studying during the war is full of stress, so it is important to support students, motivate them to develop and not to stay in despair, and not to burden the learning process so as not to damage the mental and physical health of students.

OLIYNYK Oksana

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University,
Ukraine

LEARNING ENGLISH TIME OF THE WAR

My **aim** is analyzing the importance of learning English at the time of the war.

Results:

- 1) to increasing own level of English.
- 2) knowledge of English for traveling abroad.

1) at the moment there are a huge number of different materials that can help you learn English quickly and improve your level. For example, I read books, listen to music and watch movies in English. This is a great way to hone my language skills and feel more confident in communication, because in the future I want to participate in international conferences or seminars to improve my professional activities.

2) English language is important for personal development, broadening horizons and employment opportunities. Considering the difficult period that has occurred in our country, most people go abroad. If you are fluent in English, this is a good chance to study at university.

Also, knowledge of English increases the chances of getting a job in an international company or a company that cooperates with other countries.

Knowledge of English will allow me to easily communicate with hotel staff and understand information boards and announcements at airports and train stations, as most of this information is provided in English.

Knowledge of this language is an advantage for you for visiting galleries and museums on your own. This is an opportunity to learn about the culture and traditions of the country directly from the locals.

Conclusion

From the above I can conclude: no matter how difficult it is, but we must continue to learn, improve our level of education for the future.

OVCHARENKO Anastasiia

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LEARNING ENGLISH TIME OF THE WAR

The aim of the thesis

Based on the problem above, the aim is to find out what differences are in the educational process during the peaceful time and during the war and how to cope with new challenges.

Results of the thesis

The author really expects that this thesis will be useful for the following groups: 1. For teachers of all educational institutions of Ukraine and foreign teachers working with Ukrainian refugees. 2. For Ukrainian schoolchildren and students studying in military conditions.

To learn in safe conditions – everyone can.

Learning, when missiles fly over your head, is a challenge to the realities of the modern world. “New russkiy mir” came to Ukraine and put the people before absolutely new difficulties.

Education also had to take a new challenge and form a humane attitude to students' education during a military threat.

Our country had a full-scale war and radically changed the state of things. From the government management to the specifics of the educational process.

It was necessary to quickly re-orient the military situation in everything: economy, medicine, education.

We are accustomed to the idea that learning is the safest and most comfortable learning of knowledge by the student.

But the state of distance learning and teaching in Ukraine faced the following challenges:

- physical inability of the teacher and student to be safe during training (combat actions in the region or interruption of the educational process by threats of air attacks);
- the negative emotional state of the participants of the educational process, caused by war (panic attacks, paranoid thoughts about constant threat, insomnia, stress, rapid fatigue and inattention to the educational material);
- complete absence of internet connection in regions where fighting is taking place, or unstable internet connection on the territory of the country;
- these new physical, emotional and technical negatives required new approaches in the educational environment.

What can be done?

1) To change the role of the knowledge controller teacher to the psychologist teacher.

Under conditions of constant stress, it is necessary to develop a mutual humane attitude between participants of the educational process. At remote lessons possible tears, panic, fear, negative memories.

Now students need more emotional discharge and additional words. A teacher must become a friend-psychologist.

The process of acquiring new knowledge comes second.

2) To optimize the educational material.

Choose the main topics, compose them and explain them easily for students.

So, we reduce the material and make it easier to perceive during the war.

Thus, the war that the Russian Federation brought to the territory of Ukraine has formed new changes in the educational process of Ukrainian students.

This is humanization of learning and reduction of the volume of educational material. These innovations will help minimize the emotional shock that Ukrainian students have experienced since the beginning of Russia's full-scale military invasion of Ukraine.

Conclusions

Therefore, it could be assumed that this thesis will help to effectively plan educational material for students during the war and improve their psychological state during the course of their studies.

PARTALA Sofiia

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

STUDIES AND TEACHING: DURING WAR AND PEACE

The **aim** of my work is to study the state of the educational process during the war and peace. All of humanity has faced a difficult test, called "Covid-19" - the pandemic of coronavirus disease in 2019. This disease has claimed the lives of millions of people. In order to save lives, a distance learning program was introduced in the educational institution. My university was no exception, then I studied in the 2nd year of the Faculty of Preschool Education, underwent pedagogical practice in kindergarten.

The **result** of my research shows that the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine creates all conditions for children to continue their education during the war.

Years went by, and the year 2022 began, which changed the lives of Ukrainians, on February 24, when the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation into the territory of my country, Ukraine, began. I will never forget how at 5 o'clock in the morning the first shots were fired, which signaled the beginning of the war, from that moment my life changed to before and after. Many homes were destroyed by Russian army missiles, and countless people came face to face with the grief called war. The war makes its adjustments in the lives of innocent people.

Now, the alarm is not to check, but to warn people about the danger, air alarm, shelling that you need to go to the shelter. The basement of a five-story building in Kharkiv became a shelter for my family. For many people, the subway is a safe haven. Even during the war, the education of schoolchildren and students continues. As with Covid-19, students can watch video lessons from Ukrainian teachers from the All-Ukrainian Online School. Also, children receive educational material, assignments from teachers in the application for calls and messaging "Viber".

But there are cases when parents teach their children on their own, this is relevant for younger students. Currently, I am studying in the 4th year of the Faculty of Preschool Education, the last year to achieve a bachelor's degree. Training takes place in distance learning, video classes are held in the program for video conferencing, "Zoom" and "Meet". Students place the completed tasks in the learning management system "Moodle".

The **conclusion** of my research is, I believe that it is necessary to continue education for schoolchildren and students in this difficult time, it is necessary because, the younger generation, prosperous youth is the future of the country, which may rebuild our country after the war, using the knowledge gained.

PETROVYCH Anna

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

STUDYING DURING THE WAR

Aim: Share the experience about studying during the war, reveal the pros and cons of studying in different conditions using an example: civilian life and wartime.

Results: Today, we are faced with a war that brings destruction, grief and pain. A lot of activity helps to adapt to the conditions of war. But how do the students study during the war?

I would like to talk about studying during the war, about pros and cons. Let's start with the pros, our country continues to grow, students continue to learn, to finish university experts in their field.

What is more, studying distracts from unpleasant thoughts, does not let you get bored and raises will power.

Unfortunately, there are more disadvantages than advantages. Many students can not continue their education due to gunfire and explosions, as they sit in a basement, or are in the occupied territories.

Some students simply do not have the Internet, and since most of our education is connected to the Internet, they cannot continue their education either.

And do not forget about the fact that each of us is now in stressful situation and therefore the perception and memorization of the material also is not as good as it was before the war.

Another disadvantage is that not every refugee carried a gadget that would be able to be useful in the study, as not everyone is able to buy even a simple notebook for abstracts.

Conclusion:

All in all, students should not forget about studying, even during the war, but unfortunately, the conditions that some students stay in, are not allow to work productively, to study the material and do the homework.

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LEARNING AND TEACHING: DURING WAR AND PEACE

Aim: Find out if education is possible during the war, name the difficulties and possible proposals to solve these difficulties.

Result: The country in which we live is going through extremely difficult times. The events that have recently become commonplace could only be imagined in the worst nightmare. But even in such circumstances, we must remain strong and do what we can to support each other and strengthen our faith in victory.

Representatives of educational institutions are better able to continue their education. We already had the experience of learning in extreme conditions when we first encountered the difficulties of distance learning. Therefore, learning from new difficulties is no longer so problematic for us. Most already have online learning experience. But of course, there are some features too.

First of all, war is a great burden of negative emotions and stress. There are many examples when people were even left without homes and all the necessities of life or were forced to leave cities to villages where there is no stable internet or abroad and left most of their valuables at home. Such students may find it surprisingly difficult to find opportunities to continue their studies.

For those who stay at home, it may be difficult in place. At times when the sounds of sirens or explosions reach your ears, it is impossible to think about learning. There is a problem with poor concentration and attention, and the processes of thinking and remembering are also reduced. This should be understood and taken into account.

Conclusion: In times of war, education in educational institutions should be conducted so as not to waste time, but it should be as free from unnecessary stress. One of the best options for organizing the learning process is a combination of tasks for self-study and meetings with teachers online for consultation.

Now learning is a good opportunity to distract yourself from negative thoughts and make some tricks for yourself. So, let's learn, it's important at all times!

RUCHKO Alina

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STUDYING IN WARTIME

The **aim** is point studying in wartime. to The 24th of February 2022 changed every Ukrainian. One moment divided life into "before" and "after". It has become clear that peacetime has opened up many ways to realize our potential, while war has taken away everything. This affected any field of activity: economics, politics, business and, in particular, education.

Result. Initially, the educational process was suspended, but it was resumed a month after the start of a full-scale invasion of the aggressor country. The form of education, of course, was chosen distance learning. We had acquainted with this option during the Covid-19, which allowed us to quickly adapt to new conditions. However, it would be interesting to see what features the spring semester of 2022 comparing with the previous period.

The first problem that students faced was the unstable Internet. Students joined the conferences by the mobile Internet when there was no Wi-Fi. Another thing was disconnection of energy supply for indefinite term. In one case it took 2 hours, in another - 2 days. Therefore, students and teachers could only wait.

The second and most difficult problem was psychological pressure. There were more questions than answers to this problem. Air-raid alarm, which is heard very often; news, from which ants on the body, and uncertainty about the future – all this undoubtedly affected the emotional state. Many people were forced to leave their homes and seek refuge in other areas of Ukraine, or other countries. There they were safe, but the anxiety for others and their homeland did not leave for a moment.

One can argue for a long time whether it was an imitation or a real training. It is worth noting that everyone both teachers and students for their part did everything possible to continue to do their job in this difficult situation in spite of the war. Perhaps this can be explained by the fact that Ukrainians as a nation are a symbol of indomitability and strong will.

Each of Ukrainian students understands that an educated nation means an independent nation, that is why we continue to learn even now. We attend classes online, do homework, get involved in additional scientific and practical work. A student from Kharkiv even defended his dissertation, although he was on the front line.

Conclusion. Thus, the Ukrainian-Russian war has brought certain features in the field of education. Students has faced a number of problems, both emotional and technical. Moreover, the desire to learn even in such conditions remained.

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STUDENTS' MOTIVATION IN DISTANCE LEARNING DURING THE WAR

In our country, since February 24, every citizen's life has been conditionally divided into “before” and “after”. Many students and academic staff have struggled with the decision to partially return to their past lives and continue the educational process. The **aim** of the paper is to consider students' motivation in distance learning during the war.

Results. However, we do not pretend that nothing is happening. We are not silent, we raise the topic of war in many aspects and speeches, written and printed works, and we discuss them collectively.

In the problem of students' motivation in distance learning during the war, not only the physical aspects have played a huge role, but also the psychological state of each of the participants of the learning process.

We believe that running the learning process is the best solution at this time. For mental health, each of the students and academic staff must learn and teach not to close themselves off and wait with terror for the next day, but rather try to make the world a better place, starting with themselves.

According to the world-famous American psychologist Dale Carnegie, “There is no better cure for mental wounds than self-employment.” He gave many incredible examples that fully support his theory and give no room for conspiracy theorists.

It is important for the students to realize that even in such challenging times they are bringing tremendous value to themselves and this world. The students are learning to become professionals in the future and help other people. Consequently, the students must not skip seminars and abuse the students' right to learn, being unexcused absent and citing life-threatening events.

Many students (especially from the occupied territories) need the professional help of a psychologist. After all, it is a huge stress and each person copes with it differently. It is very important to be able to find the strength to move forward with courage and the awareness that life goes on.

Conclusions. This is a very difficult time for all of the participants in the learning process. However, what is important is the fact that the students and academic staff are patriots. We believe in our victory! Glory to Ukraine!

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TRAINING OF A PHILOLOGIST DURING WAR AND PEACE

Aim. Different situations make adjustments to our lives. And the war changed our lives in various areas. Today I will talk about the training of philologists during the war and peace. The aim of the work is to highlight the peculiarities of teaching a philologist during the war and peacetime.

Results. Learning is an important part of every student's life. This was the situation in the country that we studied both in person and remotely. For some, distance learning is more convenient, and for others – face-to-face learning. But when the war broke out, all students were forced to study remotely, whether they wanted to or not. There are many disciplines in the field of philology that are difficult to master remotely.

For example, when studying the discipline "Old Slavonic language", especially the section of phonetics, you need to listen carefully to the teacher and pronounce all the sounds correctly, to hear their aspects by ear.

This is difficult to do during distance learning, as there may be unstable Internet coverage, problems with sound reproduction due to technical reasons, and so on. In peacetime, one could easily concentrate one's efforts on learning.

This is difficult to do during a war. It is difficult to force yourself not to think about the situation in the country, it is difficult to study with sad thoughts, to focus on educational activities.

On the one hand, studying helps to distract a little from the situation in the country, but when the classes are over, you sink into your thoughts again. And for some reason it turns out that everything is good, everything is calm, but you screw yourself to the bad.

Conclusion. Training during the war is not easy, but it is necessary. Every day when you go to class, you live with the thought in your head that soon everything will end, that the situation in the country will improve.

Learning during the war has many aspects to which students adapt in order to acquire quality knowledge and become a professional in their field.

ZINCHENKO Valeria

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TRAINING DURING THE WAR

The **aim** of the paper is to consider training during the war. Never before, during the war, have students been in such a difficult and diverse environment. Some have to read a textbook in a bomb shelter, some, despite interruptions to the Internet, study remotely.

There are also students whose universities have been burned or seized by the occupiers. Most students do not continue their education where they are used to, not in their city or town. It is not always possible to study in such horrible, dangerous conditions. If there are too many problems, you need to think about life, health, and you can make up for it later.

Result. In wartime, a feature of distance learning is the likelihood during online meetings of situations where the air alarm is activated. And when you break up with a couple and then come back, it's hard to get back to work. It is morally difficult to study when you know that people are dying in other parts of your country.

Frankly speaking, at first it was difficult to understand how in such a situation in the country you can consciously make decisions and learn, when the soul was constantly anxious...

However, after the first online meeting with classmates and teachers, I realized that we are a real force and we can do anything! Despite everything, we are not discouraged, because we are Ukrainians and learning will only make us stronger!

During the distance learning, there were problems with mobile communications and the Internet, which negatively affects the preparation for couples. It is also difficult to concentrate when a siren sounds or propellers fly in the sky and so on.

I try to attend online classes, because now lowering my hands is not an option. It is difficult for all Ukrainians. And it is much harder for those who are in cities where terrible fighting is going on. People can't even leave because they are trapped. However, we must be strong and never despair.

Thanks to distance learning, most students were able to return to a more or less old life, which is filled with emotions, feelings, worries, routine, which everyone so missed. I am convinced that each of us has rethought our own reality during these horrible weeks, but life goes on and everyone has to do their job: someone to work, someone to keep our peace, and someone to learn.

Conclusion. It is impossible to sit idle, because very soon life will return to normal and we will need knowledge not only theoretically but also practically.

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